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Dissertation

**QUANTUM IMAGING OF BIOLOGICAL SPECIMENS USING
ENTANGLED PHOTONS**

by

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QUANTUM IMAGING OF BIOLOGICAL SPECIMENS USING ENTANGLED PHOTONS

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ABSTRACT

Over the last decade, two-photon microscopy and optical coherence tomography (OCT) have emerged as two of the most widespread techniques for performing high-resolution, three-dimensional optical imaging of the internal structure of biological specimens. Two-photon microscopy relies on the use of dye molecules as markers that only fluoresce when they accidentally absorb two laser photons simultaneously. To enhance the probability of absorption, and thus provide more efficient imaging, expensive femtosecond-pulsed lasers are typically employed. OCT, on the other hand, is a form of range finding that makes use of photons one-at-a-time and the second-order coherence properties of a classical laser source to enable sectioning of specimens. Each imaging modality is enabled by distinct properties of the light source and ultimately yields information about structure and/or refractive index properties of the specimen. An ability to measure changes in these physical properties provides a means to track pathological processes or evaluate the viability and integrity of biological specimens.

In this work, we explore the merits and challenges of using a source of entangled photons to enable analogous non-classical two-photon imaging techniques. The configuration for two-

photon microscopy is a case in which the object interacts with both beams simultaneously. However, since entangled photons are guaranteed to be emitted pair wise, it has been hypothesized that they should be absorbed more readily so that imaging can be accomplished at reduced light levels. This would permit extended functional imaging of light-sensitive specimens. Alternatively, using photon pairs where one of the photons scatters from the object then interferes at a beam splitter with the second photon of the pair used as a reference, describes a configuration analogous to OCT but makes use of fourth-order, rather than second-order interference effects. This method, which we call quantum optical coherence tomography (QOCT), has the distinct advantage of cancelling even-order dispersion from the specimen. We further provide a method for polarization-sensitive QOCT, in which a change in the polarization state of light scattered from a specimen due to birefringence is detected. This provides added contrast for identifying structure or pathology in thick samples where dispersion plagues conventional imaging modalities.

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Nomenclature

Common Variables

A	area [m ²]
E	energy [eV]
f	focal length [m]
i	current [A]
I	optical intensity [W/m ²]
\mathbf{k}	wave vector [m ⁻¹]
L	length [m]
n	refractive index
\bar{n}	average refractive index
R	rate [s ⁻¹]
T	temperature [K]
V	volume [m ³]
W	photocathode work function [eV]

β	propagation constant [m ⁻¹]
η	quantum efficiency
λ	wavelength [m]
Λ	poling period [m ⁻¹]
ν	frequency [Hz]
τ	time delay [s]
Φ	photon flux [photons/s]
ω	angular frequency [s ⁻¹]
χ	electron affinity [eV]

Constants

c	speed of light
e	electron charge
h	Planck's constant
k_B	Boltzmann's constant

1 Introduction

Two-photon microscopy and optical coherence tomography have proven to be among the most successful techniques in biomedical imaging. By using these non-invasive optical techniques, it is possible to identify microscopic structure as well as other material properties from deep within biological tissue. Interestingly, each imaging modality is enabled by specific properties of the laser source. For example, the wavelength-tunable titanium:sapphire laser lies at the heart of most two-photon microscopy systems. This laser system is capable of generating laser pulses with femtosecond time duration, thus increasing the probability that two photons, necessary to excite a signal, will be temporally coincident at the sample. Optical coherence tomography (OCT), on the other hand, is a form of range-finding that makes use of the second-order coherence properties of an optical source. The position of interfaces within biological tissue can be determined via interference techniques with a resolution governed by the coherence length of the source. It is beneficial, therefore, to make use of sources with short coherence length (and consequently broad spectrum) to increase resolution.

Over the past several decades, a number of nonclassical (quantum) sources of light have been developed [Teich and Saleh(1988), Teich and Saleh(1990)]. One of these sources operates via spontaneous parametric down-conversion (SPDC) [Klyshko(1967), Harris et al.(1967)Harris, Oshman, and Byer, Giallorenzi and Tang(1968), Kleinman(1968), Burnham and Weinberg(1970), Klyshko(1988), Larchuk et al.(1995a)Larchuk, Teich, and Saleh] which is a nonlinear optical process that generates entangled beams of light. Such light has been utilized to demonstrate a number of two-photon interference effects [Ghosh et al.(1986)Ghosh, Hong,

Ou, and Mandel, Ghosh and Mandel(1987), Hong et al.(1987)Hong, Ou, and Mandel, Rarity et al.(1990)Rarity, Tapster, Jakeman, Larchuk, Campos, Teich, and Saleh] that cannot be observed using traditional light sources [Zeilinger(1999), Fry and Walther(2000)]. Entangled-photon pairs generated by SPDC have already found applications in optical measurements [Klyshko(1977), Migdall et al.(1998)Migdall, Datla, Sergienko, Orszak, and Shih], spectroscopy [Saleh et al.(1998)Saleh, Jost, Fei, and Teich, Fei et al.(1997)Fei, Jost, Popescu, Saleh, and Teich], imaging [Jost et al.(1998)Jost, Sergienko, Abouraddy, Saleh, and Teich, Saleh et al.(2000)Saleh, Abouraddy, Sergienko, and Teich, Abouraddy et al.(2001a)Abouraddy, Saleh, Sergienko, and Teich, Abouraddy et al.(2001b)Abouraddy, Saleh, Sergienko, and Teich, Abouraddy et al.(2002a)Abouraddy, Saleh, Sergienko, and Teich, Lugiato et al.(2002)Lugiato, Gatti, and Brambilla], and quantum information [Ekert(1991), Ekert et al.(1992)Ekert, Rarity, Tapster, and Palma, Rarity and Tapster(1996), Brendel et al.(1999)Brendel, Gisin, Tittel, and Zbinden, Sergienko et al.(1999)Sergienko, Atatüre, Walton, Jaeger, Saleh, and Teich, Jennewein et al.(2000)Jennewein, Simon, Weihs, Weinfurter, and Zeilinger]. The aim of this dissertation work is to determine whether the properties of this source of nonclassical light can provide advantages for biomedical imaging.

We begin with a brief description of the underlying processes that enable both two-photon microscopy and optical coherence tomography. We then consider analogous imaging configurations which utilize entangled photons as the source and highlight the major differences between our techniques and the state-of-the-art. It becomes obvious that entangled-photon photoemission is a precursor to entangled-photon microscopy. Photoemission provides a convenient experimental method to evaluate the delivery of entangled-photon pairs to a sample. In chapters 2 and 3, we compare photoemission results a titanium:sapphire laser

source [Booth et al.(2003a)Booth, Sergienko, Saleh, and Teich] and a source of entangled photons. We identify some of the challenges that must be overcome to realize an entangled-photon microscopy system. One such obstacle turns out to be the limited available flux of entangled photons from standard nonlinear optical crystals. In an effort to address this challenge, we briefly consider alternate methods for generating high-flux entangled photons. In this study, we uncover some interesting physical effects [Booth et al.(2002)Booth, Atatüre, Di Giuseppe, Sergienko, Saleh, and Teich] that turn out to be of interest to the quantum-optics community.

The remainder of the dissertation is devoted to the study of quantum-optical coherence tomography (QOCT) [Abouraddy et al.(2002b)Abouraddy, Nasr, Saleh, Sergienko, and Teich, Nasr et al.(2003)Nasr, Saleh, Sergienko, and Teich] which shows clear promise for biomedical imaging. We extend current efforts in this field by providing a method for polarization-sensitive QOCT (PS-QOCT) [Booth et al.(2003b)Booth, Di Giuseppe, Sergienko, Saleh, and Teich] where polarization effects can be exploited to add contrast for imaging structure or identifying pathology in biological samples. We provide a general matrix theory for PS-QOCT and outline areas for future experimental and theoretical work in this field.

1.1 Two-photon imaging techniques

1.1.1 Two-photon microscopy

Of particular interest in light microscopy, is the use of fluorescent molecules to create contrast in microscopic imaging. Since fluorescent molecules can be specifically targeted to

cellular organelles, they provide a useful tool to locate cellular structure and track changes in cell morphology or physiology. When a fluorophore is optically excited, it will emit fluorescent light that can be easily detected and displayed as an image.

Fluorescent light that is emitted from deep within a sample, however, is often scattered by out-of-plane tissue before it is collected by the imaging objective. Furthermore, out-of-focus fluorescence light contributes to a high background signal that competes with in-focus fluorescence and thus reduces contrast. As a consequence, when using conventional microscopes, scientists must resort to thin specimen preparation or reduce imaging depth to tens of microns for good image quality. Confocal imaging techniques conceived by Minsky in 1957 [Minsky(1957)], where pinhole detectors are used to eliminate out-of-focus fluorescence, allow for deeper penetration into samples and have led to significant advances in biological imaging over the last several decades. The desire to image ever deeper into tissue, while still maintaining a high signal-to-noise ratio in the image, continues to drive advances in modern microscopy.

It turns out that by probing the sample with two photons, it is also possible to optically excite a fluorescent molecule. This method of two-photon excitation is presented conceptually in Fig. 1.1. Since two photons are absorbed by the fluorophore, the absorption process is nonlinear, i.e. it depends on light intensity to an order higher than first order. The condition for high-light intensity is easily achieved by focusing laser light through an objective lens in a microscope system. To further increase the probability of two coincident photons at the sample, however, pulsed-laser light is typically used to increase the number of photons per unit interval of time. Since two photons interact with the sample, longer wavelength (lower energy per photon) light can be used. This is advantageous since longer

wavelength light is scattered less by tissue and thus allows for good signal-to-noise levels deep into biological samples [Denk et al.(1990)Denk, Strickler, and Webb]. Furthermore, since the two photons interact with the sample only at the focal point, fluorescence is emitted from a very small volume and permits optical sectioning of the sample. The sectioning capability of two-photon excitation in a microscopy system is illustrated in Fig. 1.2.

Figure 1.1: One-photon and two-photon absorption. One-photon absorption occurs in one step while two-photon absorption occurs in two steps through an intermediate level. The final excited state is the same in both cases, but the sample is exposed to lower energy/photon light under two-photon excitation.

The excitation of fluorescent molecules by two photons was introduced in its current form in the early 1990s [Denk et al.(1990)Denk, Strickler, and Webb] and has since become a widely used and accepted method in imaging. Early two-photon microscopy (TPM) studies revealed that cells escaped many damaging effects of short wavelength excitation [Potter et al.(1996)Potter, Fraser, and Pine], but as the two-photon process ultimately relies on

the accidental arrival of photons pairs, one must inevitably increase the overall flux at the sample to increase the probability of absorption and ensure a detectable fluorescent signal. Furthermore, incident light power must be further increased to extend the probe depth into biological tissue. Even though the sample is probed with lower energy/photon light, there is some evidence of a reduction in cell viability due to the two-photon absorption of coenzymes such as NADP-H and flavins [Schneckenburger et al.(2000)Schneckenburger, Hendinger, Sailer, Gschwend, Strauss, Bauer, and Schütze] or by changes in cell membrane permeability [Ridsdale and Webb(1993),König et al.(1995)König, Liang, Berns, and Tromberg]. For TPM studies that employ single-point illumination or fast line scanning in a diffraction-limited spot at high powers, there may also be heating effects, particularly at excitation wavelengths where there is appreciable water absorption. With careful wavelength selection and reduced powers, however, these effects can be minimized.

The current technology for TPM can be advanced through improvement of the hardware such as with the use of novel scanning optics or more sensitive optical detectors. Alternatively, the introduction of fluorescent molecules specially suited to two-photon transitions [Albota et al.(1998)Albota, Xu, and Webb] can enhance the absorption process and improve the efficiency of the technique. One fact remains, that is, the titanium:sapphire (ti:sapphire) laser remains the core technology for two-photon microscopy and has undergone only few improvements over the last several years. The introduction of solid-state pump lasers such as the Millennia (Spectra-Physics) and the Verdi (Coherent) has eliminated the need for costly and troublesome argon gas lasers traditionally used to pump the ti:sapphire laser. A solid-state pump affords easier maintenance and system stability in the long term which is important for long imaging studies. The ti:sapphire laser has

Figure 1.2: One-photon and two-photon excitation in a sample. Note the diffuse zone of one-photon excitation above and below the focal plane in contrast to the small excitation volume achieved with two-photon excitation. The small excitation volume in TPM allows for optical sectioning of biological samples without the use of detector pinholes.

been upgraded with broad-wavelength range mirror sets to allow for continuous wavelength tuning from 700 - 950 nm. This avoids the use of multiple mirror sets that were typically required to cover this wavelength range. The core ti:sapphire technology, however, remains the same and, at a base price of ~\$150K, is an expensive laser system that can be beyond the financial reach of some research laboratories interested in two-photon imaging.

While less expensive continuous wave (cw) lasers can excite a two-photon signal [Hell et al.(1998)Hell, Booth, Wilms, Schnetter, Kirsch, Arndt-Jovin, and Jovin], the underlying process still relies on the accidental, but simultaneous arrival of two photons. The use of entangled photons for exciting fluorescent molecules in microscopy [Teich and Saleh(1998)]

is expected to yield several advantages over conventional two-photon fluorescence excitation with a ti:sapphire laser, including lower requisite light levels for comparable fluorescence signal. Since entangled photons are generated in matched pairs, the *accidental* arrival of two photons at the sample is no longer required to effect a transition. This may admit a reduction in the incident photon flux so that sensitive biological specimens may be investigated. Furthermore, the generation of entangled photons does not require the use of an expensive pulsed-laser system and thus removes a large financial hurdle to the widespread use of two-photon microscopy techniques. The application of entangled photons to induce fluorescence and other two-photon signals has currently not been measured.

1.1.2 Optical coherence tomography

Optical coherence tomography (OCT) has become a well-established imaging technique [Huang et al.(1991)Huang, Swanson, Lin, Schuman, Stinson, Chang, Hee, Flotte, Gregory, Puliafito et al., Fujimoto et al.(1995)Fujimoto, Brezinski, Tearney, Boppart, Bouma, Hee, Southern, and Swanson, Fercher(1996), Schmidt(1999)] with applications in ophthalmology [Hee et al.(1995)Hee, Izatt, Swanson, Huang, Schuman, Lin, Puliafito, and Fujimoto], intravascular measurements [Brezinski and Fujimoto(1999), Fujimoto et al.(1999)Fujimoto, Boppart, Tearney, Bouma, Pitris, and Brezinski], and polarization measurements of tissues with collagen or other elastin fibers [Hee et al.(1992)Hee, Huang, Swanson, and Fujimoto, de Boer et al.(1999)de Boer, Srinivas, Park, Pham, Chen, Milner, and Nelson]. It is a form of range-finding that makes use of the second-order coherence properties of a classical optical source to effectively section a reflective sample with a resolution governed by the coherence length of the source. OCT makes use of light sources with short coherence length and therefore

large bandwidth so that interference can only occur over a short path-length difference between the sample and reference arms of an interferometer. A comparison of short and long coherence length sources is provided in Fig. 1.3.

LONG COHERENCE = MONOCHROMATIC

SHORT COHERENCE = BROADBAND

Figure 1.3: A comparison of short and long coherence length light sources. Imaging by optical coherence tomography utilizes light of short coherence length and therefore large bandwidth. A short coherence length ensures that light from the sample and reference arms only interfere over a short path-length difference.

The basic configuration of optical coherence tomography is illustrated in Fig. 1.4(a). In this realization, a broadband source is divided into two beams via a beam splitter, for example, to create two arms of an interferometer. The light in the upper reference arm reflects from a mirror whereas that in the lower sample arm reflects from a layered sample. The light reflected in each of these arms is recombined at a beam splitter and the second-

order (ordinary, classical) interference pattern $I(\tau)$ is monitored by a single detector. To carry out an experiment, the reference arm is scanned, thus modifying the path length $c\tau$. When the path-length delay to a particular layer in the sample matches the path-length delay in the reference arm, interference is observed. Each layer of the sample provides a return whose magnitude is proportional to the square of the reflectance of that layer. A sketch of a typical interferogram (or amplitude scan, A-scan) observed at the detector is illustrated in Fig. 1.4(b).

In the absence of material dispersion, the coherence length of the probe beam is determined by the width of the field autocorrelation function, given by the inverse Fourier transform of the power spectrum of the source. Therefore, the width of the autocorrelation function, which determines the axial resolution, is inversely proportional to the bandwidth of the source $\Delta\lambda$ and is given, for a Gaussian spectral distribution, by

$$\Delta z = \frac{2 \ln 2}{\pi} \frac{\lambda_0^2}{\Delta\lambda}, \quad (1.1)$$

where λ_0 is the central wavelength of the source. Broadband sources are therefore essential for good axial resolution and much work is under way to design new sources that push the limits of axial resolution beyond those currently achievable in OCT. The use of superfluorescent light sources [Paschotta et al.(1997)Paschotta, Nilsson, Tropper, and Hanna], state of the art titanium:sapphire lasers [Drexler et al.(1999)Drexler, Morgner, Kärtner, Pitris, Boppart, Li, Ippen, and Fujimoto], and laser-pumped photonic crystal fibers [Povazay et al.(2002)Povazay, Bizheva, Unterhuber, Hermann, Sattamann, Fercher, Drexler, Apolonski, Wadsworth, Knight et al.] have extended the resolution limit to the sub-micrometer range. As broad-bandwidth sources are developed to improve the reso-

lution of OCT techniques, the loss of resolution by material dispersion has become more pronounced.

The deleterious effects of dispersion broadening have recently emphasized [Drexler et al.(2001)Drexler, Morgner, Ghanta, Kärtner, Schuman, and Fujimoto]. In the particular case of ophthalmologic imaging, one of the most important applications of OCT, the retinal structure is located behind a comparatively large body of dispersive ocular media [Hitzenberger et al.(1999)Hitzenberger, Baumgartner, Drexler, and Fercher]. Dispersion increases the width of the coherence envelope of the probe beam and results in a reduction in axial resolution and fringe visibility [Hitzenberger et al.(2002)Hitzenberger, Baumgartner, Drexler, and Fercher]. Current techniques for depth-dependent dispersion compensation include the use of dispersion-compensating elements in the optical set-up [Hitzenberger et al.(1999)Hitzenberger, Baumgartner, Drexler, and Fercher,Smith et al.(2002)Smith, Zvyagin, and Sampson] or employ *a posteriori* numerical methods [Fercher et al.(2001)Fercher, Hitzenberger, Sticker, Zawadzki, Karamata, and Lasser,Fercher et al.(2002)Fercher, Hitzenberger, Sticker, Zawadzki, Karamata, and Lasser]. For these techniques to work, however, the object dispersion must be known and well characterized so that the appropriate optical element or numerical algorithm can be implemented. To further improve the sensitivity of OCT, techniques for handling dispersion must continue to be implemented.

Clearly, the axial resolution limit for OCT is intimately linked to the coherence properties of the source. Each photon that comprises an entangled pair is inherently broadband and thus meets the requirements for high axial resolution. However, unlike classical sources, entangled-photon fourth-order interference effects cancel even-order dispersion from a sample [Franson(1992),Steinberg et al.(1992)Steinberg, Kwiat, and Chiao,Larchuk

et al.(1995b)Larchuk, Teich, and Saleh]. This unique property of entangled photons can extend the depth to which optical sectioning may be carried out in biological samples. In this dissertation work, we present a new technique for quantum-optical coherence tomography that is sensitive to a change in the polarization state of light scattered from a specimen due to birefringence. This provides added contrast for identifying structure or pathology in thick samples where dispersion plagues conventional OCT.

1.2 Generation and properties of entangled photons

For successful frequency conversion in a nonlinear crystal, it is essential that the relative phase between the interacting waves vanish. In the second-order nonlinear bulk crystals most often used for spontaneous parametric down-conversion(SPDC) [Burnham and Weinberg(1970), Peřina et al.(1994)Peřina, Hradil, and Jurčo], *birefringent* phase-matching is used to correct for the phase difference [Giordmaine(1962), Maker et al.(1962)Maker, Terhune, Nisenoff, and Savage]. Birefringence, the difference in refractive index for each polarization of the interacting waves, serves to correct the mismatch in phase and ensure effective coupling among the waves. We briefly consider the case of birefringent phase matching in bulk crystals. Other methods for phase matching and enhancing the flux of SPDC will be considered in chapter 4.

In the particular case of uniaxial crystals, the interacting fields can be ordinarily (o) or extraordinarily (e) polarized [Dmitriev et al.(1995)Dmitriev, Gurzadyan, and Nikogosyan], with each polarization providing a different dispersion relation as illustrated in Fig. 1.5(a). The refractive index of the ordinary beam n_o does not depend on the propagation direction,

unlike the extraordinary beam refractive index n_e . By adjusting the crystal angle with respect to the incoming pump beam, the difference in these indices changes, thus altering the possible solutions to the well-known phase-matching equations for energy and momentum conservation,

$$\begin{aligned}\omega_s + \omega_i &= \omega_p && \text{(energy)} \\ \mathbf{k}_s + \mathbf{k}_i &= \mathbf{k}_p && \text{(momentum)},\end{aligned}\tag{1.2}$$

where ω_j is the angular frequency and \mathbf{k}_j is the wavevector for the pump, signal, and idler photons, $j = p, s,$ and $i,$ respectively. These equations must be solved simultaneously and have many solutions which define the possible frequencies and directions for the signal and idler photons that constitute an entangled pair. Figure 1.5(b) shows an example of scalar collinear wavevector matching that yields degenerate signal and idler photons ($\omega_s = \omega_i = \omega_p/2$). Note, however, that the energy contained in the pump photon need not be split equally into the signal and idler photons, rather it can be distributed in any proportion leading to non-degenerate signal and idler. Also, since the photons have uniform probability of emission around the propagation direction, a cone of entangled photons emerges from the crystal as illustrated in Fig. 1.5(c). There are two types of SPDC as illustrated in Fig. 1.6. In type-I SPDC the signal and idler photons emerge with parallel polarization whereas in type-II SPDC, the signal and idler photons emerge with orthogonal polarizations. In type-II SPDC, two emission cones are evident due to walk-off of the e-polarized photons resulting from the intrinsic crystal birefringence.

Some properties of SPDC are summarized in Fig. 1.7. When the signal and idler photons carry identical energy/photon equal to half the energy in the original pump photon, i.e.

$E_{s,i} = E_p/2$, the pairs are said to be degenerate. In general, however, the energy/photon of the signal and idler are not equal in which case they are referred to as non-degenerate. When the signal and idler photons propagate in the same direction as the pump, they are said to be collinear. Alternatively, signal and idler photons that emerge at an angle from the propagation direction of the pump are non-collinear. For many of the experiments described in this work, we limit ourselves to the case of collinear, degenerate SPDC.

1.3 Entangled-photon imaging techniques

The spatial and spectral entanglement of the signal and idler photons that comprise an entangled-photon pair are a consequence of the multiple solutions to the phase-matching conditions that govern their generation. This entanglement between the signal and idler photons allows for the construction of distributed imaging configurations where objects can be placed in both beams or in only one beam [Abouraddy et al.(2002a)Abouraddy, Saleh, Sergienko, and Teich]. The case where the sample interacts with both beams describes a configuration for entangled-photon microscopy. The signal and idler photons are simultaneously absorbed by the sample and fluorescent light at a shorter wavelength emerges to provide contrast for imaging as illustrated in Fig. 1.8(a). Alternatively, using photon pairs where one of the photons interacts with the sample then interferes with the second photon of the pair at a beam splitter describes a configuration for tomographic imaging as illustrated in Fig. 1.8(b). Information about the sample structure or refractive index properties can be determined via interferometric techniques and coincidence detection of the signal and idler photons.

1.3.1 Entangled-photon microscopy and photoemission

As a first step to developing imaging techniques with entangled photons, we chose to begin experiments utilizing a configuration where the sample is also the detector. If the detector is a two-photon absorber, it becomes possible to characterize properties of the entangled light and optimize the optical system required to deliver the light to the sample. A two-photon absorber can be realized using a photomultiplier tube (PMT), where following absorption of a photon pair, photoemission from the semiconductor lattice of the photocathode yields an electron which can be internally amplified and detected as current at the detector output. A photoemission system provides a distinct advantage over a system that measures the emitted fluorescence after absorption, since every photoelectron has the potential to be measured as current. Since fluorescent light is emitted isotropically over a 4π -solid angle [see Fig. 1.8(a)], only a small portion can ever be collected and measured. If entangled-photon photoemission proves successful, the use of entangled photons for fluorescence imaging simply follows by natural progression.

The idea that materials can undergo transitions via the absorption of two photons has existed in the literature since the early 1900s [Göppert-Mayer(1931)]. The effect, in fact, was first observed through photoemission in semiconductors by Sonnenberg *et al.* [Sonnenberg *et al.*(1964)Sonnenberg, Heffner, and Spicer] and in sodium metal by Teich *et al.* [Teich *et al.*(1964)Teich, Schroeer, and Wolga]. Although a PMT is typically used for detecting light when each incident photon is of sufficient energy to liberate an electron, by careful selection of the photocathode material this sensitive detector can be utilized for measuring photoemission resulting from the absorption of two photons. In this application for two-

photon photoemission, it is important to select a photocathode work function W that exceeds the energy of single photons of light in the two-photon source, i.e., $h\nu < W$. In such an instance, the photocathode material will be transparent to a single photon and respond only after the simultaneous absorption of two photons $2h\nu > W$, as illustrated in Fig. 1.9(a).

Since photoelectrons emitted at the photocathode experience an identical electric field, they are all accelerated towards the detector anode with no significant loss in other directions. A PMT system also has large internal gain through an electron cascade in the multiplier dynodes, as shown in Fig. 1.9(b). This fact, coupled with the enhanced collection efficiency over fluorescent-type experiments, affords greater sensitivity for the detection of two photons. Moreover, as we are unsure of the best optical system for delivery of entangled photons to a sample, the detected signal may be weak at the experimental outset. A sensitive, high-gain PMT system, in this sense, will increase our chance of experimental success in providing valuable information about the absorption of entangled photons.

1.3.2 Quantum-optical coherence tomography

Quantum optical coherence tomography (QOCT) is implemented by making use of a non-classical source of light, two detectors, and fourth-order quantum interference [Hong et al.(1987)Hong, Ou, and Mandel]. Sample dispersion is cancelled by virtue of the anti-correlation of the frequency components in the pair of beams that comprise the nonclassical source of light used in the experimental apparatus. For reflection from a particular layer, each spectral component above the center frequency in one beam is matched by an anti-correlated spectral component below the center frequency in the companion beam. Although spectral

components may be delayed in one (or both) beams via dispersion, the deviations cancel via interference involving both sample and reference beams.

As with conventional OCT, the interferometer contains a sample arm and a reference arm as illustrated in Fig. 1.10(a). One beam from the SPDC source is used as the sample beam and is reflected from layers in the sample. The other beam is used as a reference and reflects from a mirror at a controllable delay $c\tau$. Both beams travel through the interferometer and interfere on a beam splitter. The light from the output ports of the beam splitter are then directed to two detectors, whose coincidence rate R_c is monitored. To carry out a QOCT experiment, the path-length delay $c\tau$ is scanned via the adjustable mirror in the reference arm. When the optical path lengths of the reference and sample arms are equal, the coincidence rate exhibits a sharp dip as a result of quantum-destructive interference. This reduction in coincidence rate indicates the presence of a layer at that range (depth) in the sample and thereby provides an amplitude or A-scan image of the sample. A sketch of the QOCT interferogram is provided in Fig. 1.10(b). Unlike the conventional OCT interferogram, the QOCT interferogram reveals peaks (or dips) between sample returns. These features in the interferogram can provide information about the dispersion in interstitial layers of the sample. The dispersion-immune dips of the QOCT interferogram are typically narrower than those of conventional OCT, providing improved resolution.

Quantum-optical coherence tomography (QOCT) with entangled photons will offer several advantages over conventional OCT. Most importantly, the group-velocity dispersion between layers will not cause deterioration of the signal making it possible to increase the probe depth into a biological sample. In this dissertation, we explore how polarization effects

can add further contrast for QOCT imaging. In chapter 5, we develop a general matrix theory for polarization-sensitive QOCT (PS-QOCT). In chapter 6, we begin the construction of a PS-QOCT system centered around a pulse-pumped type-II QOCT system. We present some preliminary data and address some challenges involved in the eventual realization of a PS-QOCT system. We conclude the dissertation with some area for future work.

Figure 1.4: (a) Optical coherence tomography using an interferometer with partially coherent light generated by a broadband source such as a superluminescent diode (SLD) or one beam from spontaneous parametric down-conversion. (b) The interferogram is a record of the intensity I as a function of the mirror displacement $c\tau$.

Figure 1.5: Birefringent phase matching in bulk optical crystals. (a) When the crystal is correctly oriented, differences in the refractive indices $n_{o,e}$ for ordinary (o) and extraordinary (e) waves corrects for the phase mismatch between waves to enable efficient frequency conversion. (b) Wavevector matching for collinear, degenerate down-conversion. (c) Phase matching is achieved by correctly orienting the crystal optical axis with the input pump polarization. Due to azimuthal symmetry, a cone of down-converted light emerges from the crystal.

Figure 1.6: Schematic of (a) type-I and (b) type-II spontaneous parametric down-conversion. In type-I, the signal and idler photons emerge with parallel polarization whereas in type-II, the signal and idler photons emerge with orthogonal polarizations and can therefore be used for polarization-sensitive measurements.

Figure 1.7: Properties of SPDC. When the energy/photon (represented by the arrow length) for the signal and idler photons are equal, this is referred to as degenerate SPDC. When the energy/photon are not equal, the photons are non-degenerate. The signal and idler photons can copropagate with the pump, a case described as collinear. When the photons emerge from the nonlinear crystal at an angle with respect to the pump, this is referred to as non-collinear.

Figure 1.8: Optical configurations for imaging with two photons. (a) The sample is placed in both the signal and idler beams. The absorption of photon pairs in the sample gives rise to a fluorescence signal that is detected and used to yield spatial information about the sample. (b) The sample is placed in one of the beams. One beam probes the sample then interferes with the second beam at a beam splitter to yield information through coincidence detection using two detectors.

Figure 1.9: Photomultiplier tube with a semitransparent photocathode. (a) If the combined energy of the incoming light $2h\nu$ is absorbed by the photocathode (area of detail) with work function W , then an electron can be raised from the valence band into the vacuum. (b) A sketch of a photomultiplier tube which shows the internal electron multiplier dynodes responsible for secondary emission and the large electron gain typical of these types of optical detectors.

Figure 1.10: (a) Quantum optical coherence tomography using spontaneous parametric down-conversion light generated in a nonlinear crystal (NLC). (b) The interferogram in this case is a record of the photon coincidence rate R_c as a function of the mirror displacement $c\tau$.

2 Photoemission

2.1 The photoelectric effect

The photoelectric effect was first explained by Einstein in 1905 [Einstein(1905)] and it was for this work that he received the 1921 Nobel Prize in Physics. Photoelectron emission, or photoemission, is the result of the external photoeffect in which the absorbed energy $h\nu$ of a single photon by the photoemissive material (photocathode) results in the emission of a free electron (photoelectron) from the material. These photoelectrons contribute to a measurable current i that is proportional to the incident flux Φ of photons at the photocathode through the simple expression

$$i = \eta e \Phi, \tag{2.1}$$

where η is the detector quantum efficiency and e is the electron charge. Since any photoelectron emitted from the photocathode has the chance to be detected at the anode, photoemission provides a sensitive system for measuring low-light signals.

Most modern photodetectors utilize a semiconductor as their photoemissive material. Semiconductor materials typically have quantum efficiencies η of up to 30% in contrast to metals where the efficiency for photoemission might only reach 1%. In semiconductor materials, negatively-charged electrons can only occupy energy levels within well-defined bands separated by forbidden bands. For intrinsic semiconductors, this means that electrons must be excited from the valence band to above the bottom of the conduction band in order to contribute to the photocurrent [Grum and Becherer(1979)]. This will occur only if the absorbed photon has an energy greater than the photoelectric work function of the material

W , defined as the difference in energy between the vacuum level and the Fermi level of the material. A typical semiconductor band model is presented in Fig. 2.1(a) [Saleh and Teich(1991a)].

It is important to note that these energy bands are not necessarily sharply defined as illustrated in Fig. 2.1(a). In order to correctly describe the occupation of the different energy states of the electrons, it is necessary to consider the statistics of the electron energy that follows a Fermi-Dirac distribution under the conditions of thermal equilibrium. The Fermi function $f(E)$ describes the probability that a given state of energy E is occupied by an electron, and is given by

$$f(E) = \frac{1}{\exp [(E - E_f)/k_B T] + 1}, \quad (2.2)$$

where k_B is Boltzmann's constant, E_f is the Fermi level defined as having a fifty percent probability of occupancy by an electron, and T is the absolute temperature. In a semiconductor, the Fermi level is located in the energy gap [see Fig. 2.1(a)] which makes it possible for a photon with energy less than the work function to be absorbed by the material to promote an electron to the vacuum level. Clearly, this Fermi tail distribution of electrons above the valence band becomes important when analyzing the photocurrent generated by incident photons with energy considerably less than the work function. This is exactly the case for two-photon and entangled-photon photoemission studies.

Since the relative position of this level is dictated by the thermal state, cooling the detector effectively shifts the position of the Fermi level towards the valence band. This shift decreases the number of available photons that can be emitted by a photon of energy $h\nu$, thus reducing the overall current. One-photon photoemission can be minimized by

Figure 2.1: (a) Single-photon photoelectron emission from a semiconductor. A photon of energy $h\nu$ incident on a semiconductor photocathode can release a free electron from the valence band and raise it above the vacuum level. The photocathode work function W is defined as the difference in energy between the vacuum level and the Fermi level of the material. An electron at the top of the valence band can receive a maximum kinetic energy $E_{\max} = h\nu - (E_g + \chi)$, where E_g is the energy gap and χ is the electron affinity of the material. The resultant photocurrent i is linearly proportional to the input flux Φ , scaled by the quantum efficiency η of the detection process. The electron charge is given by e . (b) A plot of the responsivity of the Hamamatsu R464 potassium caesium antimonide (K_2CsSb) photocathode [PMT(1998)]. The responsivity of this photocathode is reduced for wavelengths that are greater than ~ 650 nm. For optical sources that are beyond this wavelength cutoff, only electrons that are present in the Fermi tail can contribute to the measured photocurrent.

choosing the photon energy to be just greater than half the work function and by reducing the temperature of the photocathode material [Teich et al.(1964)Teich, Schroerer, and Wolga, Teich and Wolga(1967)]. Even with these accommodations, the photocurrent from electrons in the Fermi tail contributes a significant source of noise and must be considered in any analysis of the measured signal.

2.2 Two-photon detectors

We have seen that photomultiplier tubes (PMTs) combine the external photoelectric effect with low noise secondary electron multiplication to provide high internal gain. Although a PMT is typically used for detecting light when each individual incident photon is of sufficient energy to liberate an electron, by careful selection of the photocathode material this sensitive detector can be utilized for measuring two-photon photoemission. The idea of two-photon absorption was first predicted by Maria Göppert-Mayer in 1931 [Göppert-Mayer(1931)] and the effect was first observed through photoemission in semiconductors by Sonnenberg *et al.* [Sonnenberg et al.(1964)Sonnenberg, Heffner, and Spicer] and in sodium metal by Teich *et al.* [Teich et al.(1964)Teich, Schroerer, and Wolga].

In two-photon photoemission, it is important to select a photocathode work function W that exceeds the energy of single photons of light in the two-photon source, i.e. $h\nu < W$. The correct PMT can be selected by studying its responsivity versus wavelength curve. As an example, a plot of the responsivity of the Hamamatsu R464 potassium caesium antimonide (K_2CsSb) photocathode [PMT(1998)] is given in Fig. 2.1(b). Since the responsivity of this photocathode is reduced for wavelengths that are greater than ~ 650 nm, it is suitable for

measuring two-photon photoemission with light sources greater than this wavelength cut-off. In such an instance, the photocathode material will be nearly transparent to a single photon and respond only after the simultaneous absorption of two photons, i.e. $2h\nu > W$. Band structure diagrams that illustrate two-photon and entangled-photon photoemission, as well as the dependency of the measured photocurrent on photon flux, are presented in Fig. 2.2(a) and (b), respectively.

Another important consideration amongst the antimonide photocathodes is the relative difference between the band gap energy and the electron affinity of the material [see Fig. 2.1(a)]. For example, although the sum of the band gap energy and the electron affinity is 2.0 eV for caesium antimonide Cs_3Sb and sodium potassium antimonide Na_2KSb photocathodes, the band gap energies are 1.6 eV and 1.0 eV, respectively. If the band gap is larger than the energy of a single photon, no one-photon transition may occur and the absorption can only be through a virtual energy state. However, if the band gap is smaller than the energy of a single photon, but less than the work function energy, photoemission may occur through an inter-band transition [Hattori et al.(2000)Hattori, Kawashima, Daikoku, Inouye, and Nakatsuka]. In this latter case, the electrons will reach the vacuum level via a two-step process using a real state. Typically, the lifetime of an electron in a real state is longer than for a virtual state thus increasing the likelihood of a two-photon transition. Materials that show promise for a real state transition given our excitation wavelength are both Na_2KSb and K_2CsSb .

There are several commercially available photocathode materials with spectral cut-offs from 650 - 850 nm. We decided to begin experiments with the Hamamatsu R464 PMT, which combines a semitransparent potassium antimonide (K_2CsSb) photocathode with a

Figure 2.2: (a) Two-photon photoemission from a semiconductor photocathode. If the combined energy of the incoming light $2h\nu$ is absorbed by the photocathode, then an electron can be raised from the valence band into the vacuum. The equation for E_{\max} needs to be changed to reflect the interaction of $2h\nu$ with the material. The resultant photocurrent i is related to the square of the incident photon flux density photons/sec.cm² scaled by the quantum efficiency η_r for the independent, random arrival of photons at the photocathode. (b) Entangled-photon photoemission from a semiconductor photocathode. The emission of a photoelectron results from the combined energy $2h\nu$ of an entangled-photon pair. Since the arrival of the second photon has unity probability, the resultant photocurrent i is linearly proportional to the input flux Φ , scaled by the quantum efficiency η_e of the detection process. The electron charge is given by e .

high gain box-and-grid dynode arrangement to provide a current gain better than 10^6 . More importantly, the spectral cut-off is at 650 nm after which the response quickly falls and the photocathode becomes transparent to the incoming radiation. The active area of the photocathode is 5×8 mm which will allow for slight misalignments of the incoming light. At the end of this chapter, we also present data for other PMT models to ensure that we have selected the best available photocathode material for two-photon transitions.

2.3 Two-photon photoemission

Two-photon photoemission was first reported from sodium metal by Teich *et al.* [Teich et al.(1964)Teich, Schroerer, and Wolga] over thirty-five years ago. These investigations utilized a photomultiplier tube with a specially designed sodium first surface. Using phase-sensitive detection methods, the results from this experiment yielded an induced photocurrent versus incident radiation power that was a straight line of slope 2 on a doubly logarithmic plot. This quadratic dependence of the photoelectric current on incident power is indicative of two-photon photoemission and has since been reproduced by many groups in metals and semiconductors. We will first reproduce these experiments and confirm that we have a sensitive system for the measurement of two-photon photoemission.

Typically the photocurrent measured in two-photon photoemission experiments is a superposition of real two-photon photocurrent and residual one-photon photocurrent. Recall that the origins of the residual one-photon effect are thermally excited electrons in the photocathode, often called Fermi tail electrons as described by the Fermi-Dirac distribution of Eq. (2.2). The one-photon effect can be minimized via cooling the photocathode or

operating at sufficiently long wavelengths so that only the few Fermi electrons at the extreme of the distribution can be emitted.

To begin a description of the photocurrent, first consider a process which consists solely of two-photon photoemission. In this case, the photocurrent would be described by

$$i_r = \eta_r \left(\frac{\Phi}{A} \right) e\Phi, \quad (2.3)$$

where η_r is a constant of proportionality with units $\text{cm}^{-2} \cdot \text{sec}$ and A is the area of incident light on the photodetector. Observe that the photocurrent is a function of Φ^2 and that there is an area dependence for the photocurrent. By defocusing, or removing the lens from the system, one can readily see that the effect could be eliminated for large A . For subsequent calculations, we assume that the incident light is focused to a diffraction-limited spot on the photodetector.

However, the photocurrent measured in the PMT is comprised of a number of sources. We must include a constant background term representing detector electronic noise, a linear term arising from Fermi-tail electrons, and a quadratic term for the two-photon effect represented in Eq. 2.3, so that

$$i_p = a + \eta_f e \Phi + \frac{\eta_r e}{A} \Phi^2, \quad (2.4)$$

where the constant a represents the measured background noise level and η_f represents the efficiency of single-photon photoemission from the Fermi tail.

2.3.1 Reducing the residual one-photon noise

We begin our experimental effort by measuring the residual one-photon noise using the set-up provided in Fig. 2.3. To enable lock-in detection, we directed the ti:sapphire laser output

to a mechanical chopper set to a reference frequency of 150 Hz. Calibrated neutral density (ND) filters were used to attenuate the laser power and a long-pass filter (LP 780) used to isolate the PMT from stray room light. The PMT (Hamamatsu model R464) was contained in a thermoelectric housing (Hamamatsu model C4877) to control the temperature and the voltage was set to 1400 V which corresponds to a mean gain of $\sim 10^8$. The PMT output was connected to a lock-in amplifier (Stanford Research Systems model 850) referenced to the mechanical chopper frequency. The photocurrent was measured over a 3-minute acquisition time using a lock-in amplifier low-pass filter bandwidth of 26 mHz. For each experiment, the average photocurrent and standard deviation are recorded as a function of input laser power.

Figure 2.3: Experimental setup for one-photon photoemission. The pulsed output of a ti:sapphire is directed to the Hamamatsu R464 PMT. The PMT signal is then directed to a lock-in amplifier that is referenced to the frequency $f_{ref} = 150$ Hz of a mechanical chopper. Neutral density (ND) filters are used to attenuate the laser power and a filter (LP 780) isolates the detector from stray room light.

Temperature dependence

A doubly logarithmic plot of photoelectric current versus incident power is provided in Fig. 2.4 for 300 K (circles), 272 K (triangles), and 253 K (squares). The ti:sapphire laser was tuned to a wavelength of 800 nm ($h\nu = 1.55$ eV) for all temperature values. The error bars indicate the standard deviation for each data point and the solid lines represent a linear fit to each data set using the measured background current at each temperature. If we consider a ratio of each of the signals, we find that by reducing the temperature from 300 K to 273 K a reduction of the residual one-photon photoemission signal by a factor of ~ 2 can be realized. By reducing the temperature a further 20 K, we observe a similar reduction factor of ~ 2.3 . For the temperature range of the cooled housing, then, we can realize an overall reduction of the residual one-photon photoemission to be 4.6.

Wavelength dependence

A doubly logarithmic plot of photoelectric current versus incident input power to the Hamamatsu R464 PMT acquired for 800 nm (circles) and 845 nm (squares) light at room temperature is provided in Fig. 2.5. By tuning the incident wavelength across this range, it is possible to reduce the magnitude of the current by ~ 2.7 times. If the two-photon photoemission signal in semiconductors is insensitive to both temperature and wavelength, as is the case for metals, it would be possible to reduce the contaminating effects of residual one-photon photoemission by over an order-of-magnitude by both cooling the detector and using longer wavelength sources.

2.3.2 Measurement of two-photon photoemission

We performed two-photon photoemission experiments at several temperatures and wavelengths using an experimental configuration provided in Fig. 2.6. Calibrated neutral density

Figure 2.4: One-photon photoemission: Doubly logarithmic plot of photoelectric current versus input power to the Hamamatsu R464 PMT acquired at room temperature (300 K, circles), at 0°C (273 K, triangles), and at -20°C (253 K, squares). The error bars indicate the standard deviation for each data point and the solid lines represent a linear fit to each data set using the measured background current from the PMT.

(ND) filters were used to attenuate the laser power and a long-pass filter (LP 780) to isolate the detector from stray room light. The PMT voltage was set to 1400 V which corresponds to a mean gain of $\sim 10^8$. The PMT output was connected to a lock-in amplifier (Stanford Research Systems model 850) and the photocurrent was measured over a 3-minute acquisition time using a mechanical chopper at a reference frequency of 150 Hz and a lock-in amplifier set to a low-pass filter bandwidth of 26 mHz. Finally, the average photocurrent and standard deviation were recorded as a function of input power.

Figure 2.5: One-photon photoemission: Doubly logarithmic plot of photoelectric current versus input power to the Hamamatsu R464 PMT acquired for 800 nm (circles) and 845 nm (squares) incident on the photocathode at room temperature. The error bars indicate the standard deviation for each data point and the solid lines represent a linear fit to each data set using the measured background current from the PMT.

Temperature dependence

Results for two-photon photoemission using the Hamamatsu R464 PMT are presented in Fig. 2.7. To evaluate the temperature dependency of the two-photon photocurrent, data was acquired at room temperature (triangles), 0°C (squares), and -20°C (circles) with the ti:sapphire laser tuned to 800 nm. At higher powers, where the signal is dominated almost entirely by two-photon photoemission, the data for each temperature nearly overlaps. The data for room temperature (triangles) lies marginally to the right of the data for the cooled

Figure 2.6: Experimental setup for two-photon photoemission. The set-up is identical to that for one-photon photoemission, however, the pulsed output of the ti:sapphire laser is focused through a lens ($f = 88.3$ mm) on to the photocathode of the PMT.

temperatures which we believe to be a result of heating effects in the photocathode. At room temperature, there is no circulating cooling water that would otherwise temperature stabilize the photocathode. Data that is acquired at 0°C (squares) and -20°C (circles) clearly follows the dashed line indicating the two-photon component to the signal.

Wavelength dependence

Two-photon photoemission results at 800 nm ($h\nu = 1.55$ eV, circles) and 845 nm ($h\nu = 1.47$ eV, squares) recorded at room temperature are provided in Fig. 2.8. As expected using longer wavelength (lower photon energy) light reduces the magnitude of the two-photon signal as indicated by the shift of the dashed line that represents the two-photon component to the signal. In the next section, we provide a quantitative measure of the two-quantum yield for several commercially available photomultiplier tubes. This will determine whether we are using the best PMT for measuring two-photon photoemission.

Figure 2.7: Two-photon photoemission: Doubly logarithmic plot of photoelectric current versus incident laser power for the R464 PMT at room temperature (triangles), 0°C (squares), and -20°C (circles). The ti:sapphire laser source was tuned to a wavelength of 800 nm. The error bars indicate the standard deviation for each data point and the solid lines represent a polynomial fit to each data set using the measured background current from the PMT. The dashed line indicates slope 2 behavior that is the hallmark of two-photon photoemission.

Figure 2.8: Two-photon photoemission: Doubly logarithmic plot of photoelectric current versus input power to the Hamamatsu R464 PMT acquired for 800 nm (circles) and 845 nm (squares) incident on the photocathode at room temperature. The error bars indicate the standard deviation for each data point and the dashed lines indicate the slope 2 component to the signal.

2.4 Two-quantum yield measurement

As techniques that employ two-photon effects become increasingly important, such as recent work that obtains information about interface, surface, and image-potential states in various materials [Schuppler et al.(1992)Schuppler, Fischer, Fauster, and Steinmann, Wang et al.(1995)Wang, Paiella, and Osgood, Jr., Fauster(2002), Töben et al.(2003)Töben, Hannappel, Eichberger, Möller, Gundlach, Ernstorfer, and Willig], it becomes important to have a measure of the strength or efficiency of two-photon effects. We utilize the previously defined *two-quantum yield* $\Lambda(\lambda, T)$ expressed in A/W as a value for the efficiency of two-photon photoemission [Teich et al.(1964)Teich, Schroerer, and Wolga, Teich and Wolga(1968)]. This value considers both the wavelength λ of the incident light, as well as the temperature T of the detector. Since a second-order effect is under consideration, Λ is proportional to the intensity I_o of the incident light in W/cm^2 . We have measured the two-quantum yield for three commercially available photomultiplier tubes (PMTs). These PMTs are the Hamamatsu R464, R2557, and 1P28 with photocathodes comprised of potassium cesium antimonide (K_2CsSb), sodium potassium antimonide (Na_2KSb), and cesium antimonide (Cs_3Sb), respectively. Our findings are tabulated in Table 2.1.

We find that the R2557 PMT with a sodium potassium antimonide photocathode provides the best two-quantum yield of the PMT detectors we measured. However, at room temperature a detectable two-photon signal is only possible for wavelengths longer than 845 nm. Even at this wavelength, the two-photon signal could only be observed across a narrow range of incident power due to the large magnitude of residual one-photon photoemission. For room temperature operation at wavelengths where we plan to conduct

PMT MODEL*	MATERIAL	λ	T	$\Lambda(\lambda, T)$
R464	K_2CsSb	800 nm	300 K	$6.30 \times 10^{-7} I_o$
			273 K	$12.3 \times 10^{-7} I_o$
			253 K	$11.9 \times 10^{-7} I_o$
		830 nm	300 K	$2.30 \times 10^{-7} I_o$
			273 K	$4.20 \times 10^{-7} I_o$
		845 nm	300 K	$2.42 \times 10^{-7} I_o$
253 K	$5.78 \times 10^{-7} I_o$			
R2557	Na_2KSb	845 nm	300 K	$19.6 \times 10^{-7} I_o$
1P28	Cs_3Sb	845 nm	300 K	$3.85 \times 10^{-9} I_o$

Table 2.1: Two-quantum yield $\Lambda(\lambda, T)$ for several commercially available photocathode materials in units of A/W for I_o expressed in W/cm^2 . The value for Λ has been corrected for the transmittance ($\beta = 0.7$) of the multialkali photocathode [Ghosh(1980)] and the Fourier coefficient ($2/\pi$) resulting from only measuring the first harmonic of the signal with our lock-in detector. The spot size on the detector was taken to be $2.5 \times 10^{-5} \text{ cm}^2$.

*Hamamatsu Photonics K.K.

entangled-photon photoemission experiments, the R464 with a potassium cesium antimonide photocathode is the best PMT since it has the lowest residual one-photon signal of all the tubes. For this PMT, it is possible to measure the two-photon signal across at least an order of magnitude under these conditions. As we have seen, this range of incident power can be extended by cooling the PMT.

2.5 Single-photon counting

One major drawback of the lock-in detection system in our experimental set-up is that the mechanical chopper has a duty cycle of 50%, thus reducing the incident photon flux by one half. When utilizing a source of entangled photons for photoemission, we want to avoid this loss and thereby choose to replace the lock-in detection system with a single-photon counting (SPC) unit (Becker & Hickl GmbH). The SPC unit can be synchronized directly to the 82-MHz repetition rate of the laser pulse train from the ti:sapphire laser so that all light becomes incident on the photocathode. We repeat several of the previous experiments here to provide data that can be compared to entangled-photon photoemission data in the next chapter.

Results for two-photon photoemission using the ti:sapphire laser are presented in Fig. 2.9. Each data point (solid circle) represents the total counts per 10-second acquisition time with a PMT voltage V_{pmt} of 1400 V. The dashed lines represent the linear residual one-photon photoemission (slope 1) and the quadratic two-photon photoemission (slope 2) components to the measured signal. The sum of these components, given by the solid line, provides an accurate description of the two-photon photoemission data.

To reduce the effect of Fermi-tail noise, we measured the ordinary two-photon photoemission signal after cooling the PMT to -20°C . The data acquisition parameters were otherwise identical to those for data acquired at room temperature. The results for two-photon photoemission in a cooled PMT are presented as solid squares in Fig. 2.10. As for the previous figure, the dashed lines represent the linear residual one-photon photoemission (slope 1) and the quadratic two-photon photoemission (slope 2) components to the measured

signal. The linear Fermi-tail contribution has been reduced by a factor of 10 by cooling the PMT whereas the quadratic two-photon photoemission curve is unaffected by detector cooling. Data acquired after PMT cooling should enable the contributions from entangled photons to become more evident, assuming that the absorption of entangled photons is not temperature dependent.

We present subsequent plots in the next chapter that contain data for entangled-photon photoemission together with data for two-photon photoemission for direct comparison under similar experimental conditions.

Figure 2.9: Two-photon photoemission: Doubly logarithmic plot of counts vs. power for a $2-f$ optical system with the PMT at room temperature. The dashed lines represent the slope 1 and slope 2 components to the signal. The sum of these components, given by the solid line, provides an accurate description of the two-photon photoemission data.

Figure 2.10: Two-photon photoemission: Doubly logarithmic plot of counts vs. power for a $2-f$ optical system with the PMT cooled to -20°C . The Fermi-tail contribution has been reduced by a factor of 10 by cooling the PMT. The dashed lines represent the slope 1 and slope 2 components to the signal. The sum of these components, given by the solid line, provides an accurate description of the two-photon photoemission data.

3 Entangled-Photon Photoemission

3.1 The entangled-photon photoemission signal

Due to the paired nature of entangled photons, in contrast to a classical source governed by Poisson statistics, we expect a linear rather than quadratic dependence for the measured signal on the incident power [Friberg et al.(1985)Friberg, Hong, and Mandel, Javanainen and Gould(1990), Fei et al.(1997)Fei, Jost, Popescu, Saleh, and Teich]. The measured photocurrent signal S_e resulting from entangled-photon photoemission is comprised of three components, given by

$$S_e = a + \eta_f e \Phi_e + \eta_e e \Phi_e, \quad (3.1)$$

where a is the background dc noise level, η_f is the single-photon (Fermi tail) efficiency, η_e is the entangled-photon photoemission efficiency, e is the electron charge, and Φ_e is the flux of entangled photons. From Eq. (3.1), it is immediately evident that with two terms that are linear in photon flux, it is impossible to uniquely determine the Fermi-tail and entangled-photon photoemission efficiencies. A single measurement can only provide a bulk combined photoemission efficiency ($\eta_f + \eta_e$).

As it turns out, there are two ways in which the flux of entangled-photon pairs can be adjusted. One can either put attenuation filters in the pump beam prior to the nonlinear crystal (NLC) which has the effect of removing pump photons available for down-conversion, or one can directly place attenuation filters in the entangled photons after their generation in the nonlinear crystal. The choice of placing filters in the pump beam or in the SPDC beams causes the measured signal to be linear or quadratic with the input flux, respectively.

We thereby have a means to perform two independent measurements from which the values of η_f and η_e can uniquely determined.

The dependency of the photoemission signal for various experimental configurations is explained through Fig. 3.1. Since the generation of entangled-photon pairs by spontaneous parametric down-conversion (SPDC) depends linearly on the input photon flux $\Phi_{2\omega}$, reducing this input flux by the amount $T_{2\omega}$ will thereby delete entangled-photon pairs by the same factor. The attenuation of entangled-photon pairs is therefore linear so that the signal S_{pump} simply follows the amount by which the input pump beam is attenuated via $T_{2\omega}$ [see Fig. 3.1(a)].

The case when attenuation filters are inserted directly in the entangled-photon pairs after the nonlinear crystal is shown in Fig. 3.1(b). In this case, the attenuation of entangled-photon pairs depends on the individual transmittance T_ω of each photon that comprises a entangled-photon pair. This leads to a quadratic dependence of the signal S_{pairs} on the filter parameter T_ω since the loss of either of the twins results in the loss of the entire entangled-photon pair.

It is important to draw the distinction between the squared-law phenomenon when placing filters after the nonlinear crystal in our experiments and the squared-law effect when measuring ordinary two-photon photoemission as illustrated in Fig. 3.1(c). In this latter case, it is the independent arrival and subsequent absorption of photons at the detector that result in the squared-law behavior. This is the hallmark of ordinary two-photon processes, including both ordinary two-photon photoemission and fluorescence. For our experiments, the measured signal follows a squared-law behavior due to the filtering of entangled-photon pairs. The absorption mechanism is distinct for entangled-photon pairs and has a linear

Figure 3.1: Effect of filter position on measured photocurrent. The behavior of the measured signal is dependent on the choice of filter position in the experiment. For entangled-photon photoemission in (a) attenuation filters are placed in the pump beam prior to the nonlinear crystal. In this case, the signal S_{pump} depends linearly on the experimental filter parameter $T_{2\omega}$. For entangled-photon photoemission in (b) attenuation filters are placed in the SPDC beams. In this case, the signal S_{pairs} depends on the square of the filter parameter T_{ω}^2 since both photons of the pair must be transmitted for the pair to survive. For ordinary two-photon photoemission in (c) the squared dependency is due to the detection process and not because of filters in the system.

dependence on the incident photon-pair flux at the detector.

In our experiments, we consider the transmission parameter T_e , so it becomes useful to generalize Eq. (3.1) to

$$S_{\text{pump}} = a + bT_eP_e + cT_eP_e, \quad (3.2)$$

$$S_{\text{pairs}} = a + bT_eP_e + cT_e^2P_e, \quad (3.3)$$

where the first equation applies to the case where filters are placed in the pump before the crystal ($T_e = T_{2\omega}$) and the second equation applies to filters placed after the crystal in the entangled-photon pairs ($T_e = T_\omega$). The coefficient a is the measured background dc noise level, whereas the coefficients b and c contain the product of the electron charge e and efficiency for each process divided by $h\nu$ as evident from Eq. (3.1). The value P_e represents the maximum measured entangled-photon power for the experiment. Note that T_e that multiplies the constant c is in the first or second power depending on whether we consider S_{pump} or S_{pairs} , respectively. This fact allows the coefficients b and c to be uniquely determined.

A typical experimental protocol for entangled-photon photoemission is as follows. The first experiment utilizes attenuation filters after the nonlinear crystal. After the dc background signal a has been measured, the photocurrent signal S_{pairs} is recorded as a function of the filter parameter T_e . A fit to this data uniquely determines the remaining two coefficients b and c . Then a second experiment that utilizes filters in the pump beam before the nonlinear crystal is conducted. It is expected that this data can be fit using the same coefficients a , b , and c , but altering the final term to be linear in transmission T_e . If, by making this simple change in the order for T_e , we are able to fit the data for S_{pump} , then we

have indeed measured entangled-photon photoemission. If we fail to fit the data accurately, then the experimental data most probably represents ordinary two-photon photoemission.

3.2 The potential to measure entangled-photon photoemission

The measurement of entangled-photon photoemission will be contaminated by single-photon Fermi-tail noise. Since this contribution to the photocurrent is also linear in power, it becomes important to determine whether entangled-photon photoemission can still be measured in the presence of strong Fermi-tail noise. With this in mind, we have used the data from ordinary two-photon photoemission in the previous chapter to evaluate the strength of the Fermi tail noise and determine whether it is still possible to observe contributions from entangled-photon photoemission.

In our experiments, the measured photoemission signal results from several sources that are included in the equation

$$y = a + bx + cx^{1 \text{ or } 2} + dx^2. \quad (3.4)$$

Here y represents the total measured photocurrent signal and x represents the incident power P or photon flux Φ , for example. The constant a is the measured background noise level, b is the coefficient for residual Fermi-tail photoemission, c is the entangled-photon coefficient that multiplies x to the first or second order depending on whether filters are placed in the pump beam or entangled photons, respectively, and d is the ordinary two-photon coefficient that multiplies a quadratic dependency in x . This final term is the hallmark of ordinary two-photon processes. We choose to normalize Eq. (3.4) by the coefficient b so that the ratio

c/b now provides a measure of the relative strength of the entangled-photon contribution (c) over the residual Fermi-tail contribution (b).

Using Eq. (3.4), we can easily fit the measured photocurrent signal presented in Fig. 2.9 to determine values for a , b , and d . This fit is indicated by a solid line in the plot and follows the expression

$$\begin{aligned} y &= a + bx + 0x + dx^2 \\ &= 78 + 150x + 0x + 0.155x^2, \end{aligned} \tag{3.5}$$

where y represents the measured photocurrent signal and x represents the incident power P in this case. Since we are only using the titanium:sapphire pulsed-laser source and no nonlinear crystal in this particular experiment, there are no entangled photons present and $c = 0$. The normalized curve (y/b) for ordinary two-photon photoemission in Fig. 3.2 (solid line) now serves as a basis for comparison when evaluating the expected entangled-photon photoemission for three special cases.

In Fig. 3.2, we provide curves for cases where the entangled-photon coefficient is 100 times greater than the Fermi-tail coefficient ($c/b = 100$), equal to the Fermi-tail coefficient ($c/b = 1$), and 100 times smaller than the Fermi-tail coefficient ($c/b = 0.01$). Figure 3.2(a) presents the case when filters are placed before the nonlinear crystal and the exponent in the third term of Eq. (3.4) is linear in x . It is evident from this plot that there will be evidence of entangled-photon photoemission even when the Fermi-tail contribution is equal to the contribution from entangled photons (open triangles). Clearly, as the strength of the entangled-photon contribution to the signal increases (open squares), there is a marked departure from the ordinary two-photon photoemission curve (solid line). In Fig. 3.2(b),

Figure 3.2: The expected entangled-photon photocurrent signal for cases where the entangled-photon coefficient is 100 times greater than the Fermi-tail coefficient (dashed curve, $c/b = 100$), equal to the Fermi-tail coefficient (dash-dot curve, $c/b = 1$), and 100 times smaller than the Fermi-tail coefficient (solid curve, $c/b = 0.01$) when (a) filters are placed before the nonlinear crystal (linear dependency) and (b) filters are placed after the nonlinear crystal (quadratic dependency). It is evident that when filters are even in the presence of strong Fermi-tail noise, entangled-photon photoemission can be distinguished from ordinary two-photon photoemission (solid circles).

we present the case where filters are placed after the nonlinear crystal and the exponent in the third term of Eq. (3.4) is quadratic in x . In this case, even when the entangled-photon contribution is much less than that for residual Fermi-tail contributions ($c/b = 0.01$), it is possible to determine whether entangled-photon photoemission exists (open circles). We can conclude, therefore, that it will be possible to determine the presence of entangled-photon photoemission in our experimental set-up even with a strong Fermi-tail noise.

3.3 Measurement of entangled-photon photoemission

3.3.1 $2-f$ optical system

We conducted entangled-photon photoemission experiments using the setup presented in Fig. 3.3. In this setup, the pump source for SPDC is the frequency-doubled output of the Spectra-Physics titanium:sapphire laser (~ 100 fs pulses at an 82 MHz repetition rate) centered at a wavelength of 400 nm with a maximum power of approximately 750 mW. The 400-nm light is first directed into a half-wave plate and a Glan-Taylor prism (PBS) to optimize the beam polarization for maximal type-I collinear down-conversion in a 25-mm thick lithium iodate crystal. Since the pump beam and entangled-photon pairs are polarized on orthogonal axes in type-I down-conversion [see Fig 1.6(a)], the pump is easily removed by means of a second Glan-Taylor prism rotated at 90° with respect to the first prism . Any residual pump-beam leakage through this second prism is then removed by means of a (RG 630) long-pass filter (pump removal). A $2-f$ optical system is built by inserting a lens at a distance f from the nonlinear crystal and PMT photocathode. A long-pass filter (RG 780) is used to isolate the PMT detector from stray room light. Finally, the PMT output is directed to a single-photon counting (SPC) unit (Becker & Hickl GmbH) that is synchronized to the laser-pulse repetition rate of 82 MHz. When conducting an experiment, we can attenuate the pump beam by rotating the half-wave plate against the first polarizing prism (pump attenuator) or attenuate the SDPC using calibrated neutral density (ND) wratten filters directly in the beam path (SPDC attenuator).

Figure 3.4 is a doubly logarithmic plot that displays the signal counts for entangled-photon photoemission (open circles) and ordinary two-photon photoemission (closed circles)

Figure 3.3: Experimental setup for entangled-photon photoemission. The 400-nm pump from the second-harmonic generator (SHG) is directed via mirrors (M) to the nonlinear crystal (NLC) aligned for maximal type-I SPDC. This pump beam can be attenuated by rotating the half-wave plate before the polarizing beam splitter (PBS). The entangled photons at 800 nm can be attenuated by inserting calibrated neutral density (ND) filters prior to being focused ($f = 88.3$ mm) onto the photomultiplier tube (PMT). A filter (LP 780) isolates the PMT from stray room light. Finally, the PMT signal is directed to a single photon counter (SPC) that is synchronized to the laser repetition rate. The dashed line indicates the beam path for the ti:sapphire beam when conducting an ordinary two-photon photoemission experiment.

Figure 3.4: Entangled-photon photoemission: Doubly logarithmic plot of counts vs. power for a $2-f$ optical system with the PMT at room temperature. The experimental data for entangled photons (open circles) is presented with the data for photoemission using the ti:sapphire laser (solid circles). The dashed line represents the slope 1 component to the two-photon signal. The maximum achievable entangled-photon power was measured to be 67 nW.

versus input power at room temperature. In each case, the signal counts are acquired over 10 seconds with the PMT voltage V_{pmt} set to 1400 V. For the entangled-photon photoemission experiment here, the filters are placed after the nonlinear crystal directly in the entangled-photon pairs (SPDC attenuator). Recall that, in this case, we expect a quadratic dependency for the photocurrent signal. The entangled-photon power on the abscissa is computed simply as the product of T_e and the maximum measured entangled-photon power $P_e = 67$ nW. The dashed line represents the slope 1 component to the two-photon photoe-

mission signal.

Figure 3.5: Best fit to entangled-photon photoemission: Linear plot of counts vs. power for a $2f$ optical system with the PMT at room temperature. The experimental data for entangled-photon photoemission (open circles) is presented with theoretical curves where the ratio of the entangled-photon coefficient to the Fermi-tail coefficient (c/b) is 0.015 (dashed curve), 0.010 (dash-dot curve), 0.005 (dotted curve), and zero (solid curve).

Although the data for entangled-photon photoemission lies above the data for ordinary two-photon photoemission, there is no clear deviation from the ordinary two-photon photoemission curve as predicted by Fig. 3.2(b). Since the entangled-photon photocurrent appears minimal, it is not useful to continue with an experiment to attenuate the pump beam prior to the nonlinear crystal. Instead, we investigate whether the measured data for entangled-photon photoemission can be fit using curves similar to those in Fig. 3.2(b). In

Fig. 3.5, we plot the measured data together with theoretical curves where the ratio of the entangled-photon coefficient to the Fermi-tail coefficient (c/b) is 0.015 (dashed curve), 0.010 (dash-dot curve), 0.005 (dotted curve), and zero (solid curve). It is clear from this figure that there is a departure from an ordinary two-photon photoemission signal (compare data with curve for $c/b = 0.0$) and that the entangled-photon contribution most probably lies between 0.005 and 0.01, that is, has a strength that is 0.5 - 1% that of the Fermi-tail noise.

Figure 3.6: Entangled-photon photoemission: Doubly logarithmic plot of counts vs. power for a $2-f$ optical system with the PMT cooled to -20°C . The experimental data for entangled photons (open squares) is presented with the data for photoemission using the ti:sapphire laser (solid squares). The dashed line represents the slope 1 component to the two-photon signal. The maximum achievable entangled-photon power was measured to be 67 nW.

In Fig. 3.6, we present data (open squares) where the PMT has been cooled to -20°C . Since only the Fermi-tail component to the signal is reduced upon cooling the PMT, the ratio c/b will subsequently increase, and the entangled-photon photocurrent become easier to observe. In this experiment, however, there doesn't appear to be any enhancement in the entangled-photon photoemission signal. In fact, there has been a reduction in the signal by an amount equal to that observed in ordinary two-photon photoemission for a cooled PMT (see Fig. 2.10). This finding suggests that the signal is predominantly due to Fermi-tail photoemission, and that any presence of entangled-photon photoemission is swamped by noise.

3.3.2 Imaging optical system

By using a $2-f$ system in the previous section, only collinear degenerate photons are spatially coincident on the photocathode. In an effort to increase the overall flux of entangled photons and to take advantage of non-degenerate transitions, i.e. transitions in the photocathode that are not made in equal energy steps, we performed photoemission experiments that placed the nonlinear crystal in an imaging configuration with respect to the photomultiplier tube photocathode. In this configuration, we can use degenerate and non-degenerate photon pairs and thus exploit the higher absorption cross-section predicted for non-degenerate transitions. This higher absorption cross-section for non-degenerate pairs has been theoretically shown to be an order of magnitude higher for transitions in hydrogen atoms [Fei et al.(1997)Fei, Jost, Popescu, Saleh, and Teich].

The experimental setup, which we present in Fig. 3.7, is very similar to the setup used in the previous experiments, however, the lens is moved away from the PMT and located

Figure 3.7: Experimental setup for entangled-photon photoemission using an imaging configuration. The 400-nm pump from the second-harmonic generator (SHG) is directed to the nonlinear crystal (NLC) aligned for maximal type-I SPDC. This pump beam can be attenuated by rotating the half-wave plate before the polarizing beam splitter (PBS). The entangled photons at 800 nm can be attenuated by inserting calibrated neutral density (ND) filters prior to being focused ($f = 88.3$ mm) onto the photomultiplier tube (PMT). A filter (LP 780) isolates the PMT from stray room light. Finally, the PMT signal is directed to a single photon counter (SPC) that is synchronized to the laser repetition rate.

at a position whereby the imaging equation can be satisfied. For the chosen distances of 350 mm and 120 mm, there is an overall demagnification factor of ~ 3 . To be able to compare entangled-photon photoemission with ordinary two-photon photoemission, we needed to include a second lens in the beam from the titanium:sapphire laser to create a focussed spot in the nonlinear crystal. This spot in the nonlinear crystal is subsequently imaged onto the photocathode in an effort to acquire data for ordinary two-photon photoemission. As in the previous experiments, we begin with an experiment where the entangled-photon pairs are

attenuated . In this setup, however, we were able to increase the overall power of entangled photons to 83 nW.

Figure 3.8: Entangled-photon photoemission: Doubly logarithmic plot of counts vs. power for an imaging system with the PMT at room temperature. The experimental data for entangled photons (open circles) is presented with the data for photoemission using the ti:sapphire laser (solid circles). The dashed line represents the slope 1 component to the two-photon signal. The maximum achievable entangled-photon power was measured to be 83 nW.

The results for room temperature entangled-photon photoemission (open circles) using an imaging configuration are presented together with ordinary two-photon photoemission (solid circles) in Fig. 3.8. It is immediately evident that the strength of the ordinary two-photon photoemission signal is reduced. This is evident from the lack of a significant

quadratic dependency to the signal at high powers and is most likely a consequence of a reduced laser intensity on the PMT. Since we are utilizing an imaging configuration for the titanium:sapphire beam, the focal spot is no longer diffraction limited on the PMT photocathode. Since the data for entangled-photon photoemission was acquired by attenuating the SPDC after the nonlinear crystal, we expect a quadratic dependency in the measured signal. As for data acquired with the $2-f$ system, the data lies above that for ordinary two-photon photoemission, but there is clearly no quadratic dependency in the signal. We conclude that an optical imaging configuration does not provide any advantage for observing entangled-photon photoemission and noise dominates the measured signal at room temperature.

The results for entangled-photon photoemission (open squares) and ordinary two-photon photoemission (solid squares) for a cooled PMT are presented in Fig. 3.9. In the case of a cooled PMT, we see the expected improvement in the ordinary two-photon photoemission signal as evidenced from a stronger quadratic dependency to this signal. The data for entangled-photon photoemission, however, remains linear and is reduced by an amount equivalent to the linear component of the ordinary two-photon signal. This behavior, in the absence of an enhanced quadratic component to the entangled-photon photoemission signal, suggests that entangled photons are only absorbed as single photons. Upon cooling, the measured signal is identical to that for residual one-photon photoemission presented in the previous chapter indicating the signal is due to Fermi-tail noise.

Figure 3.9: Entangled-photon photoemission: Doubly logarithmic plot of counts vs. power for an imaging system with the PMT cooled to -20°C . The experimental data for entangled photons (open squares) is presented with the data for photoemission using the ti:sapphire laser (solid squares). The dashed line represents the slope 1 component to the two-photon signal. The maximum achievable entangled-photon power was measured to be 83 nW.

3.4 Conclusion

By an analysis of ordinary two-photon photoemission, we concluded that entangled-photon photoemission should be distinguishable from Fermi-tail noise components. This is possible via an experiment where the entangled-photon pairs are attenuated with neutral density filters. In such an experiment, each photon must be transmitted through the filter for the pair to survive. This imparts a quadratic dependency on the measured signal thus making

it possible to distinguish from the Fermi-tail noise.

We conducted experiments that placed the nonlinear crystal and PMT photocathode in a $2-f$ and imaging configuration. In each case, we were unable to definitively measure a photoemission signal resulting from entangled photons. Upon PMT cooling, the photoemission signal is reduced by an order of magnitude. A similar reduction in signal is measured when utilizing the ti:sapphire laser source and indicates that one-photon Fermi tail effects dominate the signal and not the absorption of photon pairs.

From Fig. 3.4, it appears that we might benefit from a higher power of entangled photons. With a higher power, we could determine whether any quadratic component to the photoemission signal were due to entangled photons or to ordinary two-photon effects. This could be verified by conducting the second experiment where the pump beam is attenuated. For future work, we will consider the use of periodically-poled lithium niobate (PPLN) as a source for down-conversion. Such crystals are already in use for second-harmonic generation and are slowly emerging as new sources of down-converted light [Tanzilli et al.(2001)Tanzilli, Riedmatten, Tittel, Zbinden, Baldi, Micheli, Ostrowsky, and Gisin,Banaszek et al.(2001)Banaszek, U'Ren, and Walmsley]. Periodically poled sources show promise due to the increase in the efficiency of entangled-photon generation and may provide increased power for our photoemission experiments.

The early indication is that the use of entangled photons may not prove useful for biological imaging. If further experiments do not show a distinct advantage for the entangled-photon source, the feasibility of inducing fluorescence in biological samples will certainly prove difficult.

4 High-Flux Sources

In the previous chapter, we concluded that with a higher entangled-photon power, we would have a better chance to determine whether any quadratic component to the photoemission signal was due to entangled photons or to ordinary two-photon effects. In this chapter, we briefly describe two ways that the entangled-photon power might be increased.

4.1 Cavity-enhanced SPDC

One method that might be employed to enhance the available SPDC power is to utilize a resonant cavity for the SPDC pump wavelength. As is shown in Fig. 4.1, such a configuration places a crystal for second-harmonic generation (SHG) as well as a crystal for SPDC (NLC) in the same cavity. The cavity is pumped from an external laser via a dichroic mirror and focused into the SHG crystal by a lens. After a single pass through the SHG crystal, the laser pump is removed from the cavity via a second dichroic mirror. The SHG light is transmitted through each of these dichroic mirrors and is resonant in the cavity since the mirrors associated with the cavity have very high reflectance at this wavelength. The resonant-enhanced SHG light act as a strong pump to increase SPDC generation in the NLC. Since the cavity mirrors are highly transmissive for the SPDC wavelength, the entangled-photon output exits the cavity in collinear fashion.

Due to losses resulting from the many optical elements in this configuration, we might only expect an enhancement of the SPDC power by a factor ~ 1.3 . This enhancement is still not sufficient to observe entangled-photon photoemission. A more promising method

Figure 4.1: Resonator-enhanced SPDC. The pump power available for SPDC is increased within the cavity. An enhanced pump power subsequently increases the generation of SPDC in the nonlinear crystal (NLC).

for generating high-flux SPDC is presented in the next section.

4.2 Quasi-phase matched SPDC

When a nonlinear medium does not exhibit sufficient birefringence at the interacting wavelengths, birefringent phase matching is no longer possible. As an alternative to birefringent phase-matching, waveguide structures can also be utilized to achieve wave coupling [Shen(1984)]. Coupled-mode theory describes the power transfer among guided waves and relies on matching the propagation constants of the interacting fields along the direction of travel, rather than the wavevector for each optical wave. By careful selection of the waveguide dimensions and other properties such as the index profile, the modal structure of the interacting waves can be altered such that efficient frequency mixing can be realized

within the waveguide.

Yet another method to correct for phase mismatch is to introduce periodic structure into the nonlinear medium, which results in what is termed *quasi-phase matching* (QPM). This approach was independently proposed by Armstrong *et al.* [Armstrong et al.(1962)Armstrong, Bloembergen, Ducuing, and Pershan] and Franken and Ward [Franken and Ward(1963)] in the early 1960's. Of particular interest is a technique for modulating the sign of the second-order nonlinearity throughout the medium to produce a so-called *periodically poled material*. Since any interaction within the transparency region of such a periodically poled material can be non-critically phase matched at a specific temperature via QPM, it is possible to utilize the largest value of the effective nonlinear coefficient for a given material and thus increase the overall conversion efficiency. In the family of commonly used nonlinear media, lithium niobate (LiNbO_3) boasts one of the largest nonlinear coefficients d_{33} for all beams having extraordinary polarization; it is approximately 6 times greater than the d_{31} coefficient used in birefringent phase-matching [Baldi et al.(1995)Baldi, Aschieri, Nouh, Micheli, Ostrowsky, Delacourt, and Papuchon]. The result is a theoretical enhancement of $(2d_{33}/\pi d_{31})^2 \sim 20$ for QPM over birefringent phase-matching [Myers et al.(1995)Myers, Eckardt, Fejer, Byer, Bosenberg, and Pierce]. Many of the advantages of QPM in lithium niobate have been outlined elsewhere [Fejer et al.(1992)Fejer, Magel, Jundt, and Byer] and results show that periodically poled lithium niobate (PPLN) is a natural choice for many experiments.

The enhancement in nonlinear-interaction efficiency promised by the use of PPLN has raised interest in the quantum-optics community where there has been a growing interest in new ultrabright sources of entangled photons [Tanzilli et al.(2001)Tanzilli, Riedmatten,

Tittel, Zbinden, Baldi, Micheli, Ostrowsky, and Gisin]. Entangled photons, which may be generated through the process of spontaneous parametric down-conversion (SPDC) in a crystal with $\chi^{(2)}$ nonlinearity, has long been in the spotlight for quantum-optics experiments [Peřina et al.(1994)Peřina, Hradil, and Jurčo, Mandel and Wolf(1995)]. SPDC, however, suffers from low conversion efficiency, on the order of 10^{-9} entangled-photon pairs per mode per pump photon, which ultimately limits their use in many practical applications. Lithium niobate offers the promise of increased photon-pair production and, with the integration of a waveguide structure, control of the spatial characteristics of the down-converted photons while still maintaining a substantial increase in conversion efficiency [Tanzilli et al.(2001)Tanzilli, Riedmatten, Tittel, Zbinden, Baldi, Micheli, Ostrowsky, and Gisin, Banaszek et al.(2001)Banaszek, U'Ren, and Walmsley]. Since the interaction volume in a waveguide is typically smaller than that in a bulk crystal, it might be thought that this would result in reduced conversion efficiency. However, if comparable pump power is delivered into the waveguide, the photon-pair flux would be identical to that in the bulk crystal for the same $\chi^{(2)}$ nonlinearity.

In QPM, it is possible to couple an interaction through the largest value of the effective nonlinear coefficient $\chi^{(2)}$ for a given material and thus increase the overall conversion efficiency. For lithium niobate (LiNbO_3), the largest coefficient for nonlinear interaction occurs with all beams polarized on the extraordinary axis of the crystal. In this orientation, the equation for momentum conservation can never be satisfied birefringently (see Fig. 4.2(b)) and requires the introduction of a QPM grating vector K_m to satisfy momentum conservation

$$\mathbf{k}_s + \mathbf{k}_i + K_m = \mathbf{k}_p \tag{4.1}$$

Figure 4.2: Quasi-phase matching in periodically poled materials. (a) The periodic inversion of the sign of nonlinearity is shown by the shaded regions and yields a grating vector given by $K_m = 2\pi m/\Lambda$. (b) Scalar quasi-phase matching is accomplished through the grating vector K_m which is introduced by the periodic inversion Λ of the nonlinear susceptibility. (c) Quasi-phase matching for the $e \rightarrow e + e$ interaction in lithium niobate utilizes the largest coefficient of nonlinearity d_{33} .

where m is the order of the periodic inversion, $K_m = 2\pi m/\Lambda$, and Λ is the domain reversal period.

A proposed experimental setup for observing SPDC through a QPM interaction in bulk periodically poled lithium niobate is presented in Fig. 4.3. To set the correct phase-matching parameters a 1064-nm cw pump can be used to observe second-harmonic generation at 532 nm. Once the SHG signal at 532 nm has been optimized for PPLN temperature, input polarization angle, and crystal angle, a chopped 532-nm (dashed green line) can then be used as a pump for SPDC. After the pump beam has been filtered out using a set of filters (RG 780 and BP 1064/25), the SPDC signal at 1064 nm can be measured at a germanium

Figure 4.3: Proposed experimental setup for QPM in PPLN.

detector using lock-in detection.

In recent months, ongoing work in the Quantum Imaging Laboratory to explore the use of PPLN sources for quantum communication schemes has yielded results where the PPLN output has been imaged directly onto a CCD camera. One example of such data is shown in Fig. 4.4 where the PPLN, temperature tuned to 200°C , is pumped with a 532-nm cw source to create non-degenerate SPDC at 812 nm and 1550 nm. By using a bandpass filter centered at $810/\Delta 70$ nm the down-conversion, the visible portion of the SPDC is readily apparent at the center of the image. The thin outer ring in the image corresponds to a secondary type-I interaction in the PPLN ($e \rightarrow o + o$) that coexists with the stronger interaction, where all polarizations for pump, signal, and idler are extraordinarily polarized ($e \rightarrow e + e$).

4.3 Counterpropagating SPDC

It turns out that the use of a waveguide structure, in conjunction with periodic poling, offers yet another critically important feature: the possibility of generating counterpropagating signal and idler photons. Counter-propagation has been previously considered in the context of surface birefringence in nanostructure semiconductors [Rossi and Berger(2002)].

In this section, we consider the conditions required for generating counterpropagating photon beams by quasi-phase matching in waveguides with periodic nonlinearity and we explore the unique properties of this source of light. Such a source of entangled photons would be immediately useful in quantum-interference experiments that make use of spatial filters [Atatüre et al.(2002)Atatüre, Di Giuseppe, Shaw, Saleh, Sergienko, and Teich]. Such filters are often used to restore visibility in these kinds of experiments but they carry the price of a significant reduction in the photon-pair rate.

4.3.1 SPDC in a single-mode waveguide

By virtue of a relatively weak interaction, time-dependent perturbation theory leads to a two-photon state generated by SPDC at the crystal output that is given by [Klyshko(1980)]

$$|\Psi^{(2)}\rangle \sim \int_V dV \int dt \chi^{(2)}(z) \hat{E}_p^{(+)}(\mathbf{r}, t) \hat{E}_s^{(-)}(\mathbf{r}, t) \hat{E}_i^{(-)}(\mathbf{r}, t) |0\rangle, \quad (4.2)$$

where V is the interaction volume, $\chi^{(2)}$ is the second-order susceptibility of the medium, \mathbf{r} is the position vector, and $\hat{E}_j^{(\pm)}$ is the positive- or negative-frequency part of the pump, signal, or idler electric-field operator ($j = p, s, i$), respectively. In a waveguide, the single-mode signal and idler fields can be described by

$$\hat{E}_j^{(-)}(\mathbf{r}, t) = \int d\omega_j u_0(\mathbf{x}; \omega_j) e^{-i\beta_j z} e^{i\omega_j t} \hat{a}_j^\dagger(\omega_j, \beta_j), \quad (4.3)$$

where u_0 corresponds to the fundamental mode of the waveguide, \mathbf{x} is the transverse position vector, $\beta_j = \beta_j(\omega)$ are the propagation constants, and \hat{a}_j^\dagger are the creation operators, with $j = s, i$, respectively. As long as the propagation constants for signal and idler fields, β_s and β_i , are larger than a critical propagation constant β_c , determined by the waveguide properties, there is only one fundamental mode available for the propagation of each of the signal and idler fields. If such a condition is met for both the signal and idler fields, then this corresponds to a single-mode waveguide for these fields, as illustrated in Fig. 4.5 for an arbitrary pump field. This assumption is retained throughout the remainder of this paper.

If it is assumed, furthermore, that the complex pump field is classical:

$$E_p(\mathbf{r}, t) = \int d\omega_p \mathcal{E}_p(\mathbf{x}; \omega_p) e^{i\beta_p z} e^{-i\omega_p t}, \quad (4.4)$$

where \mathcal{E}_p is the transverse and spectral profile of the pump wave, Eqs. (4.2) - (4.4) then lead to a two-photon quantum state given by

$$\begin{aligned} |\Psi^{(2)}\rangle \sim \int_A d\mathbf{x} dz \int dt \int d\omega_p d\omega_s d\omega_i \mathcal{E}_p(\mathbf{x}; \omega_p) u_0(\mathbf{x}; \omega_s) u_0(\mathbf{x}; \omega_i) \\ \times \chi^{(2)}(z) e^{i\Delta\beta z} e^{-i(\omega_p - \omega_s - \omega_i)t} \hat{a}_s^\dagger(\omega_s, \beta_s) \hat{a}_i^\dagger(\omega_i, \beta_i) |0\rangle, \end{aligned} \quad (4.5)$$

where A is the transverse plane spanned by the vector \mathbf{x} and where

$$\Delta\beta = \beta_p - \beta_s - \beta_i \quad (4.6)$$

is the phase mismatch between the three fields that must vanish for perfect phase-matching.

We can further simplify Eq. (4.5) by carrying out the integration over t . This yields the condition

$$\omega_p - \omega_s - \omega_i = 0 \quad (4.7)$$

and, using the Fourier-transform definition

$$\tilde{\chi}^{(2)}(\Delta\beta) = \int dz e^{iz\Delta\beta} \chi^{(2)}(z), \quad (4.8)$$

we obtain

$$|\Psi^{(2)}\rangle \sim \int d\mathbf{x} \int d\omega_s d\omega_i \mathcal{E}_p(\mathbf{x}; \omega_s + \omega_i) u_0(\mathbf{x}; \omega_s) u_0(\mathbf{x}; \omega_i) \tilde{\chi}^{(2)}(\Delta\beta) \hat{a}_s^\dagger(\omega_s, \beta_s) \hat{a}_i^\dagger(\omega_i, \beta_i) |0\rangle \quad (4.9)$$

for the two-photon state describing down-converted light in a single-mode waveguide structure.

Finally, applying the creation operators to the vacuum yields

$$|\Psi^{(2)}\rangle \sim \int d\omega_s d\omega_i \Phi(\omega_s, \omega_i) |1\rangle_{\omega_s} |1\rangle_{\omega_i}, \quad (4.10)$$

with a state function Φ [Di Giuseppe et al.(2002)Di Giuseppe, Atatüre, Shaw, Sergienko, Saleh, and Teich] given by

$$\Phi(\omega_s, \omega_i) = \int_A d\mathbf{x} \mathcal{E}_p(\mathbf{x}; \omega_s + \omega_i) u_0(\mathbf{x}; \omega_s) u_0(\mathbf{x}; \omega_i) \tilde{\chi}^{(2)}(\Delta\beta). \quad (4.11)$$

The ket $|1\rangle_{\omega_s} |1\rangle_{\omega_i}$ represents a single photon in the frequency mode ω_s and a single photon in the frequency mode ω_i with corresponding propagation constants β_s and β_i , respectively. Since the down-converted light is guided in only a single spatial mode, the magnitude-squared of the state function, $|\Phi(\omega_s, \omega_i)|^2$, represents the spectrum of the SPDC, which will be considered subsequently.

The theory presented to this point is general and can be applied to any structure with an arbitrary nonlinearity profile. In this paper, we focus on a second-order susceptibility that is periodically modulated in the z -direction, so that $\chi^{(2)}(z)$ can be written as a Fourier

series and takes the form

$$\chi^{(2)}(z) = \chi_0^{(2)} \sum_m G_m e^{iK_m z}. \quad (4.12)$$

Here m corresponds to the m^{th} component of the Fourier expansion with coefficient G_m and wavenumber $K_m = 2\pi m/\Lambda$, where Λ is the periodicity of the modulation. Since the phase mismatch $\Delta\beta$ among the propagation constants of the three fields is most often not zero, we must use the contribution K_m , associated with the modulation of the nonlinearity in the material, to achieve perfect quasi-phase matching in the waveguide [$\Delta\beta = K_m$ in Eq. (4.6)]. We may therefore define a phase mismatch $\Delta\beta'$ in the presence of the grating vector K_m given by

$$\Delta\beta' = \beta_p - \beta_s - \beta_i - K_m. \quad (4.13)$$

When $\Delta\beta' = 0$, this is referred to as perfect *quasi*-phase matching.

For a nonlinearity with a single periodicity, $K_{\pm m} = \pm K_m$ so that negative values of m may also yield meaningful solutions to the QPM conditions given in Eq. (4.13). In conjunction with the multiple signal-idler wavelength combinations generated with SPDC, contributions from both positive and negative values of m can be simultaneously realized. This is in contradistinction to three-wave mixing problems such as second harmonic generation [Fejer et al.(1992)Fejer, Magel, Jundt, and Byer], where the two input fields are fixed and yield only one output field. In this latter case, the grating vector corresponding to the negative value of m is not utilized since it does not yield a simultaneous phase-matching solution.

4.3.2 Counterpropagating SPDC in a PPLN waveguide

We continue our analysis by considering the specific example of a PPLN waveguide and proceed to describe some interesting properties of single-mode, counterpropagating signal and idler beams, under various conditions.

Without loss of generality, we consider a waveguide in two dimensions [Saleh and Teich(1991b)]: x as the transverse (guiding) dimension and z as the longitudinal (propagating) dimension. We further assume that the pump field in Eq. (4.4) is a monochromatic unguided and undepleted plane wave with a transverse spatial profile given by:

$$\mathcal{E}_p(x; \omega_p) = A_p \cos[(k_p \sin \theta)x], \quad (4.14)$$

where A_p is a constant and k_p is the pump wavenumber. Such a field can be realized by illuminating the waveguide with two identical coherent fields at angles $\pm\theta$ from the z -axis. An illustration of a planar dielectric waveguide structure pumped in this geometry is shown in Fig. 4.6. Since the power of the pump beam can be increased to any desired level, loss of pump beam energy is not critical for effective operation. Our example of an unguided pump beam is distinct from a scheme for copropagating difference frequency generation, in which both the pump beam and signal photon are guided and a copropagating idler photon is allowed to radiate into the substrate [Baldi et al.(1995)Baldi, Aschieri, Nouh, Micheli, Ostrowsky, Delacourt, and Papuchon].

To compute tuning curves from Eq. (4.7) and Eq. (4.13), where the pump beam is incident on the waveguide structure at an angle θ , we use $\beta_p = k_p \cos \theta$. We allow the propagation constant β_i for the idler field to take on a negative value to permit counter-propagation. Finally, to compute the specific values of β_j for each field, we use the set

of Sellmeier equations for lithium niobate [Dmitriev et al.(1995)Dmitriev, Gurzadyan, and Nikogosyan] to determine the refractive index for extra-ordinarily polarized (e) waves in the $e \rightarrow e + e$ interaction under consideration. Although Eq. (4.13) only describes perfect phase-matching ($\Delta\beta' = 0$), we are nonetheless able to determine many interesting properties of counterpropagating signal and idler photons. These are presented as tuning curves, representing various properties of the down-converted light as a function of the pump-beam incidence angle.

To investigate the relationship of the poling period and the pump-beam incidence angle for quasi-phase matching, we first consider only the degenerate case where the pump field gives rise to counterpropagating signal and idler photons at twice the pump wavelength ($\lambda_s = \lambda_i = 2\lambda_p = 1064$ nm). Figure 4.7 shows the required poling period Λ that allows for perfect QPM at any pump-beam incidence angle. Immediately evident from this plot is that for a pump beam that is coupled into the PPLN waveguide at 65° , one would require a poling period on the order of the pump wavelength ($0.5 \mu\text{m}$). This observation remains true for pump-beam incidence angles less than 65° , including the case for normal incidence at 0° . Since the smallest poling period experimentally achievable with lithium niobate is currently $\sim 4 \mu\text{m}$ [Batchko et al.(1999)Batchko, Fejer, Byer, Woll, Wallenstein, Shur, and Erman], this configuration is not currently realizable.

To experimentally realize phase-matching for counterpropagating fields in an optical parametric oscillator or amplifier (OPO/OPA) at angles near normal incidence, researchers have been forced to utilize materials such as gallium arsenide, in which it is possible to construct sub-micron multilayer or asymmetric quantum-well domain structures using semiconductor growth techniques. The second-order susceptibility can then be spatially modulated

between contiguous layers at the dimension required to successfully achieve phase-matching. By varying the pump beam angle in such devices, QPM may be realized over large tuning ranges in OPOs and OPAs [Ding et al.(1995)Ding, Lee, and Khurgin].

The use of an unguided pump avoids the necessity for sub-micron poling periods to achieve counter-propagation in PPLN waveguides. To illustrate this, consider the particular first-order poling period $\Lambda = 6.8 \mu\text{m}$ that corresponds to second harmonic generation at 532 nm and, therefore, degenerate down-conversion to 1064 nm. For this poling period, we find from Fig. 4.7 that if we pump the waveguide at an angle of $\sim 88.2^\circ$, we can generate counterpropagating signal and idler beams. When the pump beam is at 90° , $\Lambda \rightarrow \infty$ ($K_m \rightarrow 0$) so that QPM is no longer required for down-conversion and a birefringent interaction will result in counterpropagating signal and idler photons [Fejer et al.(1992)Fejer, Magel, Jundt, and Byer].

Most interesting is nondegenerate down-conversion where we select, as a particular example, the signal-idler combination of 810 nm and 1550 nm, respectively. From the tuning curves in Fig. 4.8 we find that for the same poling period considered in Fig. 4.7, $\Lambda = 6.8 \mu\text{m}$, one can satisfy QPM at two pump angles, namely $\sim 70.4^\circ$ and $\sim 74.6^\circ$, as a result of the dual-directionality of the grating vector K_m . Since there are two angles that satisfy QPM for nondegenerate down-conversion, we expect that for a single angle, the dual-directionality of the grating vector would allow for different nondegenerate wavelength combinations. In Fig. 4.9(a), all possible signal-idler wavelength combinations are plotted as the pump-beam incidence angle is varied from 65° to 90° . For this plot, the poling period is fixed at $\Lambda = 6.8 \mu\text{m}$ and the corresponding tuning curves are plotted for grating vector values with order $m = 0, \pm 1, \pm 2, \text{ and } \pm 3$. The selection of tuning curves for experimental implemen-

tation is dependent on the nature of the periodicity of the nonlinearity and on the strength of the coefficients G_m in Eq. (4.12).

As an example, a $\chi^{(2)}$ that is modulated as a square wave in the z -direction, as illustrated in Fig. 4.6, has dominant Fourier components of order ± 1 , for which tuning curves are shown in Fig. 4.9(b). If we consider an example where the pump beam angle is 80° , there are signal-idler wavelength combinations of approximately 880 nm/1350 nm ($m = -1$, dashed curve, open circles) and 930 nm/1240 nm ($m = +1$, solid curve, solid circles). This quantum state can be represented by

$$|\Psi^{(2)}\rangle \sim c_1|880, 1350\rangle + c_2|930, 1240\rangle, \quad (4.15)$$

where the constants c_1 and c_2 are determined mainly by the pump properties. By simply selecting the pump-beam incidence angle to be 74.6° , for example, the two-photon quantum state given above can be readily tuned to new signal-idler wavelength combinations of 810 nm/1550 nm and 860 nm/1380 nm.

The generation of a superposition of two counterpropagating nondegenerate photons pairs occurs naturally within the PPLN waveguide structure and this is a novel property as it stands. Beyond changing the pump-beam incidence angle, control over the down-converted light is further afforded by adjusting the poling period. As the poling period is reduced, the difference between the two signal wavelengths and the two idler wavelengths turns out to increase, i.e., the curves separate from one another. As one increases the poling period or chooses the longer third-order poling period, the signal photons and idler photons become more similar in wavelength, i.e., the curves approach each other.

4.3.3 SPDC Spectrum in a PPLN waveguide

The preceding section considered only the idealized phase-matching conditions provided by Eq. (4.13). In this section, we consider effects on the spatio-temporal distribution of down-converted light imparted by the finite crystal length and the modal structure of the waveguide. The spectrum of down-conversion at the output of the waveguide is computed from the magnitude-squared of the state function given in Eq. (4.11).

As a specific example, and for convenience of calculation, we consider the TE modes of a planar graded-index (GRIN) slab waveguide as illustrated in Fig. 4.6, with a parabolic index profile [Saleh and Teich(1991b)] along the transverse x -axis given by

$$n^2(x) = n_0^2 [1 - \alpha^2 x^2], \quad (4.16)$$

where n_0 is the maximum core index and $n_0\alpha^2$ is the rate of change of refractive index with position, $dn(x)/dx$. For this case, the fundamental transverse mode becomes [Ghatak and Thyagarajan(1998)]

$$u_0(x; \omega_j) = C \exp\left[-\frac{(\gamma_j x)^2}{2}\right], \quad (4.17)$$

where C is a constant and where

$$\gamma_j = \left[\frac{n_0\omega_j}{c} \alpha\right]^{\frac{1}{2}}, \quad \beta_j = \frac{n_0\omega_j}{c} \left[1 - \frac{c}{n_0\omega_j} \alpha\right]^{\frac{1}{2}}. \quad (4.18)$$

Single-mode operation is achieved when

$$\beta_{s,i} > \beta_c = \frac{n_0\omega_{s,i}}{c} \left[1 - \frac{3c}{n_0\omega_j} \alpha\right]^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (4.19)$$

and we assume that the down-converted light couples only to the fundamental mode of the parabolic waveguide.

By substituting into Eq. (4.11) the transverse mode profile given by Eq. (4.17), the unguided pump field given by Eq. (4.14), and the first-order periodic nonlinearity found from Eq. (4.12), we find the following expression for the state function:

$$\Phi(\omega_s, \omega_i) = A \sqrt{\frac{\pi}{\gamma_{\text{eff}}^2}} e^{-\frac{\zeta^2}{4\gamma_{\text{eff}}^2}} \left\{ \text{sinc}\left[\left(\Delta\beta + \frac{2\pi}{\Lambda}\right) \frac{L}{2}\right] e^{-i(\Delta\beta + \frac{2\pi}{\Lambda}) \frac{L}{2}} + \text{sinc}\left[\left(\Delta\beta - \frac{2\pi}{\Lambda}\right) \frac{L}{2}\right] e^{-i(\Delta\beta - \frac{2\pi}{\Lambda}) \frac{L}{2}} \right\}, \quad (4.20)$$

where A is a constant, $\zeta = [n_0(\omega_s + \omega_i)/c] \sin \theta$, $\gamma_{\text{eff}}^2 = (1/2)(\gamma_s^2 + \gamma_i^2)$, and L is the crystal length. Effectively, the SPDC bandwidth is modulated by the prefactor $[\pi/(\gamma_s^2 + \gamma_i^2)]^{1/2} \exp(-\zeta^2/4\gamma_{\text{eff}}^2)$ associated with the waveguide and will therefore differ from that for bulk media. The spectral profile of the photon pairs can therefore be altered by the waveguide parameters. For the waveguide parameters in the parabolic index-profile example presented here, however, the value of this pre-factor remains nearly constant over the computed bandwidth, so that waveguide effects can be ignored, at least for the fundamental mode. If the waveguide operating conditions admit multiple modes, however, the SPDC bandwidth may be more sensitive to the waveguide properties.

We now consider the SPDC bandwidth, measured as the full-width -half-maximum (FWHM) of the SPDC spectrum obtained from the magnitude square of Eq. 4.20, for several interesting configurations in a PPLN waveguide. Figure 4.10 presents a set of plots that show the SPDC spectrum for (a) degenerate, copropagating ($\theta = 0^\circ$), (b) degenerate, counterpropagating ($\theta = 88.2^\circ$), (c) nondegenerate, copropagating ($\Lambda = 7.4 \mu\text{m}$, $\theta = 0^\circ$), and (d) nondegenerate, counterpropagating ($\theta = 69.7^\circ$) down-converted photons. In all cases, the PPLN waveguide is taken to have an interaction length $L = 1 \text{ mm}$, a poling period of $6.8 \mu\text{m}$ (unless otherwise specified), and the pump wavelength is again taken to be 532 nm .

It is immediately obvious that the bandwidths for the counterpropagating cases are narrower than those for the copropagating cases [compare Figs. 4.10(b) and 4.10(d) with Figs. 4.10(a) and 4.10(c)]. This narrow bandwidth arises since the sum, rather than the difference, of the propagation constants appears in the expression for $\Delta\beta'$ [Fejer et al.(1992)Fejer, Magel, Jundt, and Byer]. For degenerate signal and idler photons, the reduction in bandwidth from 130 nm for the copropagating case to 0.23 nm in the counterpropagating case is almost three orders-of-magnitude. This is far in excess of the one order-of-magnitude reduction in bandwidth available via surface birefringence in a semiconductor waveguide [Rossi and Berger(2002)]. The pronounced bandwidth reduction in our PPLN structure arises from the strong dispersion of lithium niobate. The narrow bandwidth of the signal and idler supports the approximate discrete-frequency representation provided in Eq. (4.15) and indicates that nearly discrete down-conversion wavelengths can indeed be realized experimentally without having to resort to the use of narrow spectral filters.

To highlight the distinction between the copropagating and counterpropagating cases, we present a plot of the SPDC bandwidth ratio versus normalized signal wavelength ($\lambda_s/2\lambda_p$) in Fig. 4.11. The SPDC bandwidth ratio is obtained by dividing the FWHM bandwidth for each central signal wavelength by the FWHM bandwidth at $\lambda_s = 880$ nm, which is the shortest wavelength used for this simulation. The PPLN waveguide is taken to have an interaction length $L = 1$ mm and again $\lambda_p = 532$ nm. This plot illustrates the relative increase in bandwidth for copropagating and counterpropagating photons as the nonlinear interaction approaches degeneracy ($\lambda_s/2\lambda_p = 1.00$). This trend is similar in birefringent phase-matching and arises from a change in the refractive index sum or difference for signal and idler photons. The change, however, is much more pronounced for copropagating

photons. Note that the bandwidth ratio (and the bandwidth) of the counterpropagating photons is always less than that for copropagating photons and changes far less as the signal-idler wavelength combination changes.

Just as we did for the analysis presented in Sec. 4.3.2, we generate tuning curves that illustrate all possible signal-idler combinations for various pump-beam incidence angles. Figure 4.12 shows the tuning curve obtained for copropagating signal and idler photons in a 1-mm PPLN waveguide when the spectral distribution of the down-converted light is incorporated in the model. To generate such a curve for copropagating photons, it is necessary to increase the poling period in the simulation to $7.4 \mu\text{m}$ so that nondegenerate solutions can be found as the pump-beam incidence angle is varied. The grating vector K_m is taken to be positive ($m = 1$) to facilitate comparison with previous work in the field. The plot reveals the large bandwidth near degeneracy (1064 nm) and the spectral characteristics of the down-converted light for all wavelength combinations.

Finally, in Fig. 4.13, we present a tuning curve for counterpropagating signal and idler photons in a 1-mm PPLN waveguide with a poling period of $6.8 \mu\text{m}$. In analogy with the analysis carried out in Sec. 4.3.2, we consider both the positive and negative spatial components of the grating vector ($m = \pm 1$). The resulting plot is similar to that presented in Fig. 4.9(b) but now incorporates the spectral distribution of the down-converted light. Since the bandwidth of the down-converted light is narrow for all signal-idler wavelength combinations, and does not change appreciably as the photons approach degeneracy, the curves remain narrow for all pump-beam incidence angles.

Figure 4.4: CCD image of the output from a 532-nm pumped PPLN with a poling period of 20.3 μm . The PPLN was contained in a temperature-controlled oven at 200°C and the SPDC output was passed through a bandpass filter centered at 810/ Δ 70 nm with a before being imaged on a CCD camera. Image courtesy of H. Guillet De Chatellus and G. Di Giuseppe.

Figure 4.5: Schematic of a slab waveguide structure with modulated nonlinearity (illustrated as striations). The pump has an arbitrary spatial profile whereas the signal and idler beams are assumed to occupy the fundamental TE electric-field modes of the waveguide.

Figure 4.6: Schematic of a PPLN slab waveguide with the plane-wave pump beams incident at the angles of incidence $\pm\theta$. The pump is unguided whereas the counterpropagating signal and idler beams are assumed to populate the fundamental mode of the waveguide. The medium comprising the waveguide is taken to have a parabolic index profile $n(x)$ as shown in the inset and to have a nonlinear susceptibility $\chi^{(2)}(z)$ that has a single period. The illustration shows a square-wave modulation of $\chi^{(2)}$; the arrows indicate regions of positive and negative values of the nonlinear coefficient.

Figure 4.7: Degenerate tuning curve for perfect QPM ($\Delta\beta' = 0$): Poling period Λ ($m = 1$) vs. pump-beam incidence angle θ for degenerate down-conversion in a PPLN waveguide with counterpropagating signal and idler photons at $\lambda_s = \lambda_i = 1064$ nm. The pump wavelength $\lambda_p = 532$ nm.

Figure 4.8: Nondegenerate tuning curve for perfect QPM ($\Delta\beta' = 0$): Poling period Λ ($m = \pm 1$) vs. pump-beam incidence angle θ for nondegenerate down-conversion in a PPLN waveguide with counterpropagating signal and idler photons at $\lambda_s = 810$ nm and $\lambda_i = 1550$ nm. The pump wavelength $\lambda_p = 532$ nm.

Figure 4.9: Tuning curves for perfect QPM ($\Delta\beta' = 0$) with various values of m : (a) Signal and idler wavelengths vs. pump-beam incidence angle θ for grating vector orders $m = 0, \pm 1, \pm 2$, and ± 3 in a PPLN waveguide with a poling period $\Lambda = 6.8 \mu\text{m}$. (b) Subset of tuning curves in (a) for $m = \pm 1$ with the poling period $\Lambda = 6.8 \mu\text{m}$. The signal photon propagates in the positive z -direction and the idler photon counterpropagates in the negative z -direction as shown by the inset. The pump wavelength $\lambda_p = 532 \text{ nm}$ in both (a) and (b). Positive and negative values of m are indicated by solid and dashed curves, respectively. The case where $m = 0$ is indicated by a dotted curve. Circles in (b) indicate the two signal-idler combinations possible for a pump-beam incidence angle of 80° : 880 nm/1350 nm ($m = -1$, dashed curve, open circles) and 930 nm/1240 nm ($m = +1$, solid curve, solid circles). Since these plots only consider the case of perfect QPM, they lack the spectral information of the signal and idler photons, which will be presented in Fig. 4.13.

Figure 4.10: SPDC spectrum vs. signal wavelength λ_s for phase-matching conditions that allow (a) degenerate, copropagating ($\theta = 0^\circ$); (b) degenerate, counterpropagating ($\theta = 88.2^\circ$); (c) nondegenerate, copropagating ($\Lambda = 7.4 \mu\text{m}$, $\theta = 0^\circ$); and (d) nondegenerate, counterpropagating ($\theta = 69.7^\circ$) signal and idler photons in a PPLN waveguide of 1-mm length. The directions of propagation for the signal and idler photons in the various cases is shown by the insets. Note the different abscissa scales for the copropagating and counterpropagating panels. The full-width-half-maximum (FWHM) for the copropagating case is 130 nm for degenerate photons versus 7.3 nm for a nondegenerate signal photon at 810 nm. In the counterpropagating case, the FWHM for degenerate photons is 0.23 nm versus 0.13 nm for a nondegenerate signal photon at 810 nm. The poling period in (a), (b), and (d) is $\Lambda = 6.8 \mu\text{m}$, whereas for (c) it is $\Lambda = 7.4 \mu\text{m}$ to achieve a nondegenerate solution for a 0° angle of incidence. The pump wavelength $\lambda_p = 532 \text{ nm}$ and the nondegenerate idler photon $\lambda_i = 1550 \text{ nm}$.

Figure 4.11: SPDC bandwidth ratio vs. normalized signal wavelength. The bandwidth ratio is obtained by dividing by the bandwidth at $\lambda_s = 880$ nm (0.83 on the abscissa), which is the shortest wavelength used for this simulation. The signal wavelength is normalized to the degenerate wavelength $2\lambda_p = 1064$ nm. The pump wavelength $\lambda_p = 532$ nm. This plot illustrates the relative increase in bandwidth for copropagating and counterpropagating photons as the nonlinear interaction approaches degeneracy at $\lambda_s/2\lambda_p = 1.00$.

Figure 4.12: Spectrum of signal and idler vs. pump-beam incidence angle for copropagating beams in a 1-mm PPLN waveguide with a poling period $\Lambda = 7.4 \mu\text{m}$ and positive grating vector K_m ($m = 1$). The pump wavelength $\lambda_p = 532 \text{ nm}$.

Figure 4.13: Spectrum of signal and idler vs. pump-beam incidence angle for counterpropagating beams in a 1-mm PPLN waveguide with a poling period $\Lambda = 6.8 \mu\text{m}$ and $m = \pm 1$. The pump wavelength $\lambda_p = 532 \text{ nm}$. The narrow bandwidth of the down-converted light is evident for all signal and idler combinations and does not change appreciably as the photons approach degeneracy, unlike the results shown in Fig. 4.12 for copropagating beams. Although this plot includes all the information pertaining to the spectrum of the down-converted light, it is visually indistinguishable from the plot presented in Fig. 4.9(b).

4.3.4 SPDC in a cladding-pumped nonlinear fiber

Copropagating entangled photons generated by spontaneous parametric down-conversion have previously been observed in periodically poled silica fibers (PPSFs) by directly coupling of the pump beam [Bonfrate et al.(1999)Bonfrate, Pruneri, Kazansky, Tapster, and

Rarity]. Although the effective nonlinearity d_{eff} in silica is less than that for lithium niobate, PPSFs offer a longer interaction length L , a higher damage intensity threshold I , and a lower refractive index n so that they achieve a comparable figure of merit $d_{\text{eff}}^2 L^2 I / n^3$. The shortest poling period currently available in a D-shaped silica fiber is $\Lambda = 25 \mu\text{m}$, which was used for second-harmonic generation at 422 nm with an average conversion efficiency of $\sim 0.22\%$ [Kazansky and Pruneri(1997)]. It is expected that this efficiency would be able to be increased by a factor of 100 by improvements in poling techniques.

Figure 4.14: Meridional cross-section of an optical fiber with a periodically modulated nonlinear medium $\chi^{(2)}$ that comprises the core. The pump beam is guided within the fiber cladding. By coupling to the core, spontaneous parametric down-conversion yields counterpropagating signal and idler photons.

As an alternate to the periodically poled silica fiber and to the PPLN waveguide example presented in Secs. 4.3.2 and 4.3.3, we present a novel configuration in which we propose the use of a periodically poled nonlinear optical fiber to generate counterpropagating signal

and idler photons. In a scheme analogous to that of a fiber laser, the pump beam (which is guided in the fiber cladding) couples to the core medium as it propagates. Since the core medium has a modulated nonlinearity, as depicted in Fig. 4.14, counterpropagating entangled photons can be generated. With improvement in the conversion efficiency, the use of cladding-pumped nonlinear fibers such as described above should prove an effective source of counterpropagating entangled photons for quantum-optics experiments and technologies.

Figure 4.15: All-fiber quantum communication scheme.

One application of an all-fiber source might appear in quantum communication where source-to-fiber coupling losses are often large. Figure 4.15 presents a scheme whereby counterpropagating entangled photons generated in a poled nonlinear portion of the fiber then propagate to two parties, commonly referred to as (A)lice and (B)ob), without the need for coupling optics between the source and fiber. The narrow bandwidth that is naturally inherent to counterpropagating SPDC means that dispersion in the fiber will be minimized

over longer-distance communication.

4.4 Conclusion

In Sec. 4.3.1, we discussed the conditions for achieving spontaneous parametric down-conversion in a waveguide with periodic nonlinearity. We extended this discussion in Sec. 4.3.2 and found that an unguided pump beam in a periodically poled lithium niobate waveguide could give rise to counterpropagating signal and idler photons. In Sec. 4.3.3, we considered a particular waveguide structure and computed the spectrum of the down-converted light for several interesting and important cases. The theoretical results indicate that counterpropagating beams have a narrower bandwidth than copropagating beams, which makes it possible to generate a superposition of two or more counterpropagating nondegenerate photon pairs. The quantum state generated thereby exhibits *discrete* frequency entanglement and can be readily altered in several ways: by tuning the pump-beam incidence angle, by appropriately changing the pump field profile using, e.g., a superposition of pump angles, and by engineering the periodicity of the nonlinearity. Such a quantum state cannot be generated in bulk nonlinear media, nor in media with periodic structures, but they are generated naturally in media with both periodic nonlinearity and a waveguiding structure. Although we primarily discussed theoretical results for a PPLN waveguide, the results are general and will also apply, for example, to a periodically poled cladding-pumped fiber with $\chi^{(2)}$ nonlinearity. Many other novel configurations for the generation of counterpropagating signal and idler photons can be envisioned.

It may also be possible to admix other levels of subtlety into the quantum states de-

scribed in this paper. By carefully selecting an appropriate nonlinear medium and crystal cut axes, for example, polarization entanglement can be incorporated into the down-converted photons. It has been shown in potassium titanyl phosphate (KTP) that it is possible to create type-II second harmonic conversion by use of the d_{24} nonlinear coefficient for z -cut crystals with the beam propagation along the x -axis [Wang et al.(1999)Wang, Pasiskevicius, Hellström, Laurell, and Karlsson]. Further studies along these lines will certainly reveal other such new and interesting materials, implementations, and devices.

There is still much work to be done before the complexities of quasi-phase matching in nonlinear crystals is fully understood. We continue to explore the use of entangled photons for quantum optical coherence in the remaining chapters. Since this technique does not require the simultaneous absorption of photon pairs, but rather relies on interference techniques, it holds more promise for biomedical imaging in the short term.

5 Polarization-Sensitive Quantum Optical Coherence Tomography

Ongoing research in the field of quantum-optical coherence tomography (QOCT) [Abouraddy et al.(2002b)Abouraddy, Nasr, Saleh, Sergienko, and Teich, Nasr et al.(2003)Nasr, Saleh, Sergienko, and Teich] is aimed at exploring the advantages afforded by dispersion cancellation and resolution enhancement. In this chapter, we generalize these QOCT methods and describe a method for polarization-sensitive QOCT (PS-QOCT) measurements, where one can also detect a change in the polarization state of light reflected from a layered sample [Hee et al.(1992)Hee, Huang, Swanson, and Fujimoto]. This state change arises from scattering and birefringence in the sample and is enhanced in specimens that have an organized linear structure. Since many biological tissues exhibit birefringence, for example, the fibrous tissue of tendons, muscle, nerve, or cartilage, the technique of PS-QOCT can be a powerful technique for detecting a change in functionality, integrity, or viability of biological material.

5.1 General matrix theory for PS-QOCT

We present the theory for PS-QOCT according to the simplified diagram for an experimental setup given in Fig. 5.1. Using a Jones-matrix formalism similar to that in Ref. [Abouraddy et al.(2002c)Abouraddy, Toussaint, Jr., Saleh, Sergienko, and Teich], we start by defining a

twin-photon Jones vector \mathbf{J}_{in}

$$\mathbf{J}_{\text{in}} = \begin{bmatrix} \hat{a}_s(\omega) \mathbf{e}_s \\ \hat{a}_i(\omega') \mathbf{e}_i \end{bmatrix}, \quad (5.1)$$

where $\hat{a}_s(\omega)$ and $\hat{a}_i(\omega')$ are the annihilation operators for the signal-frequency mode ω and the idler-frequency mode ω' , respectively. The vectorial polarization information for the signal and idler field modes are contained in \mathbf{e}_j , ($j = s, i$). For example, if we utilize collinear type-II SPDC from a second-order nonlinear crystal (NLC) to generate a pair of orthogonally polarized photons, the \mathbf{e}_j reduce to the familiar Jones vectors:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{e}_s &= \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} && \text{(vertical)} \\ \mathbf{e}_i &= \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} && \text{(horizontal)} \end{aligned} \quad (5.2)$$

for signal and idler, respectively.

The twin photons collinearly impinge on the input port of a polarizing beam splitter (PBS) from which the signal photon is reflected into the sample arm and the idler photon is transmitted into the reference arm. We assume that the polarization in each arm is independent of that in the other arm until the final beam splitter. We also assume that all optical elements within the interferometer are linear and deterministic.

The delay accumulated by the signal and idler beams in each path is represented by the 2×2 matrix

$$\mathbf{D} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{d}_1(\omega) & 0 \\ 0 & \mathbf{d}_2(\omega') \end{bmatrix}, \quad (5.3)$$

where $\mathbf{d}_1(\omega)$ and $\mathbf{d}_2(\omega')$ represent the Jones matrices that describe the delay for the sample and reference arms, respectively. The polarization state in each arm is represented by the

Figure 5.1: Conceptual diagram of polarization-sensitive quantum-optical coherence tomography (PS-QOCT). The system is based on a Mach-Zehnder interferometer in which twin photons from SPDC, represented by the vector \mathbf{J}_{in} , are separated into two arms at a polarizing beam splitter (PBS). The signal photon at angular frequency ω travels in the sample arm and experiences a path delay \mathbf{d}_1 as well as an arbitrary polarization rotation described by \mathbf{U}_1 . The reference arm contains the idler photon at angular frequency ω' which experiences a path delay \mathbf{d}_2 and a user-selected polarization rotation \mathbf{U}_2 . Paths ① and ② impinge on a final beam splitter (BS) which mixes the spatial/polarization modes into paths ③ and ④. \mathbf{J}_{out} represents the final twin-photon Jones vector from which the fields at the detectors and the final coincidence rate are computed.

matrix

$$\mathbf{U} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{U}_1(\omega) & 0 \\ 0 & \mathbf{U}_2(\omega') \end{bmatrix}. \quad (5.4)$$

In the experimental realization of PS-QOCT, the matrix $\mathbf{U}_1(\omega)$ represents the properties of the sample *plus* any other polarization elements in the sample arm, whereas $\mathbf{U}_2(\omega')$ represents the user-selected polarization state in the reference arm.

The mixing of the polarizations from each path, which occurs at the final beam splitter, is represented by the transformation matrix

$$\mathbf{T}_{\text{BS}} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{T}_{31} & \mathbf{T}_{32} \\ \mathbf{T}_{41} & \mathbf{T}_{42} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (5.5)$$

where each element \mathbf{T}_{kl} ($k = 3, 4$ and $l = 1, 2$) is a 2×2 matrix that represents the mixing of independent polarization modes from the input paths ① and ② prior to detection in paths ③ and ④. For example, \mathbf{T}_{31} is the Jones matrix that represents the transformation of input spatial mode 1 into output spatial mode 3.

The Jones vector \mathbf{J}_{out} that describes the field operators at the output of the final beam splitter, can be computed from the product of the previously defined matrices in Eqs. (5.3) – (5.5) as

$$\mathbf{J}_{\text{out}} = \mathbf{T}_{\text{BS}} \mathbf{U} \mathbf{D} \mathbf{J}_{\text{in}} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{T}_{31} \mathbf{U}_1 \mathbf{d}_1 & \mathbf{T}_{32} \mathbf{U}_2 \mathbf{d}_2 \\ \mathbf{T}_{41} \mathbf{U}_1 \mathbf{d}_1 & \mathbf{T}_{42} \mathbf{U}_2 \mathbf{d}_2 \end{bmatrix} \mathbf{J}_{\text{in}}. \quad (5.6)$$

From this equation, the fields in paths ③ and ④ arriving at each of the two detectors can be written in the time domain as

$$\hat{\mathbf{E}}_3^{(+)}(t_3) = \int d\omega e^{-i\omega t_3} \hat{a}_s(\omega) \mathbf{e}_{3s} + \int d\omega' e^{-i\omega' t_3} \hat{a}_i(\omega') \mathbf{e}_{3i} \quad (5.7)$$

$$\hat{\mathbf{E}}_4^{(+)}(t_4) = \int d\omega e^{-i\omega t_4} \hat{a}_s(\omega) \mathbf{e}_{4s} + \int d\omega' e^{-i\omega' t_4} \hat{a}_i(\omega') \mathbf{e}_{4i}, \quad (5.8)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbf{e}_{3s} &= \mathbf{T}_{31} \mathbf{U}_1 \mathbf{d}_1 \mathbf{e}_s & \mathbf{e}_{3i} &= \mathbf{T}_{32} \mathbf{U}_2 \mathbf{d}_2 \mathbf{e}_i \\
\mathbf{e}_{4s} &= \mathbf{T}_{41} \mathbf{U}_1 \mathbf{d}_1 \mathbf{e}_s & \mathbf{e}_{4i} &= \mathbf{T}_{42} \mathbf{U}_2 \mathbf{d}_2 \mathbf{e}_i
\end{aligned} \tag{5.9}$$

describes each of the transformations of the signal and idler polarizations that contribute to the final fields in ③ and ④ at the detectors.

From the field at each of the detectors, the two-photon amplitude can be written as

$$A_{jk}(t_3, t_4) = \langle 0 | \hat{E}_{3j}^{(+)}(t_3) \hat{E}_{4k}^{(+)}(t_4) | \Psi \rangle, \tag{5.10}$$

where j and k represent two orthogonal polarization bases such as horizontal/vertical (H/V), right/left circular (R/L), or (45°/-45°). The ket $|\Psi\rangle$ represents the two-photon state at the output of the nonlinear crystal, defined as

$$|\Psi\rangle = \int d\Omega \Phi(\Omega) \hat{a}_s^\dagger(\omega_0 + \Omega) \hat{a}_i^\dagger(\omega_0 - \Omega) |0\rangle, \tag{5.11}$$

where $\Phi(\Omega)$ is the state function [Di Giuseppe et al.(2002)Di Giuseppe, Atatüre, Shaw, Sergienko, Saleh, and Teich] that governs the spatio-temporal properties of the signal and idler photons at angular frequency $\omega_0 \pm \Omega$. If the state function $\Phi(\Omega)$ is symmetric about the center frequency or $\Phi(-\Omega) = \Phi(\Omega)$, the SPDC spectrum becomes $|\Phi(\Omega)|^2$.

We assume that the detection apparatus is slow and independent of polarization so that the final coincidence rate R is computed as the magnitude-square of the two-photon amplitude summed over each polarization mode, integrated over time:

$$R = \int dt_3 \int dt_4 \sum_j \sum_k |A_{jk}(t_3, t_4)|^2. \tag{5.12}$$

5.2 Simplified configuration for PS-QOCT

It is now useful to consider a specific experimental configuration from which we can define expressions for the Jones matrices in Eqs. (5.3) – (5.5) and calculate the quantum interferogram. One particular experimental configuration for PS-QOCT is based on the Mach-Zehnder interferometer and is shown in Fig. 5.2.

A narrow-band pump laser at a wavelength of 400 nm pumps a 1.5-mm-thick β -barium borate (BBO) nonlinear crystal (NLC) oriented for type-II, collinear SPDC with a center wavelength of 800 nm. The pump beam is removed from the SDPC by use of a highly reflective mirror (HR 400) centered at the pump wavelength concatenated with a long pass filter (LP 695). The vertical and horizontal components in the SPDC beam are separated by a polarizing beam splitter (PBS) into the reference arm and sample arm of a Mach-Zehnder interferometer. The reference arm consists of a variable path-length delay comprised of a half-wave plate (HWP), a second polarizing beam splitter (PBS), a quarter-wave plate (Q), and a translational mirror. The final polarization of the reference beam (indicated as \odot) can be oriented to either vertical or horizontal by a linear rotator prior to the final beam splitter (BS). The sample arm consists of a beam splitter and a quarter-wave plate (Q) so that circularly polarized light is normally incident on the sample. The back-reflected light from the sample, which in general has elliptical polarization, mixes with the delayed reference beam at the final beam splitter (BS). The outputs from the BS are directed to two single-photon counting detectors. The coincidence rate $R(\tau)$ for photons arriving at the two detectors, as a function of the path-length delay $c\tau$, are recorded in a time window determined by a coincidence-counting detection circuit (indicated as \otimes).

Figure 5.2: Possible implementation of polarization-sensitive quantum-optical coherence tomography (PS-QOCT). A narrow-band pump laser at a wavelength of 400 nm pumps a 1.5-mm-thick β -barium borate (BBO) nonlinear crystal (NLC) oriented for type-II, collinear SPDC with a center wavelength of 800 nm. The pump beam is removed from the SDPC by use of a highly reflective mirror (HR 400) centered at the pump wavelength concatenated with a long pass filter (LP 695). The vertical and horizontal components in the SPDC beam are separated by a polarizing beam splitter (PBS) into the reference arm and sample arm of a Mach-Zehnder interferometer. The components of the interferometer and coincidence detection scheme are discussed in the text.

The elements of the Jones matrix in Eq. (5.3), representing the delay in each path, are given simply by $\mathbf{d}_1(\omega) = \mathbf{I} e^{i\omega z_1/c}$ and $\mathbf{d}_2(\omega') = \mathbf{I} e^{i\omega' z_2/c}$, where \mathbf{I} is the identity matrix, c is the speed of light in the medium, and z_1, z_2 are the path lengths in the sample and reference arms, respectively. We define a path-delay difference $\tau = (z_1 - z_2)/c$ that becomes our experimental parameter in the final expression for the measured coincidence rate $R(\tau)$. We assume that the final beam splitter faithfully transmits and reflects each input polarization mode. The elements of \mathbf{T}_{BS} in Eq. (5.5) thus become $\mathbf{T}_{31} = \mathbf{T}_{42}^\dagger = t\mathbf{I}$ and $\mathbf{T}_{32} = -\mathbf{T}_{41}^\dagger = r^*\mathbf{I}$, where \dagger designates a matrix transpose and conjugation, and t and r represent the amplitude transmittance and reflectance of the beam splitter, respectively.

Without having to specify the elements of \mathbf{U} in Eq. (5.4), an expression for the measured coincidence rate as a function of the path-delay difference τ is calculated to be

$$R(\tau) \propto \Lambda_0 - \mathcal{V}_{\text{BS}} \text{Re}[\Lambda(2\tau)], \quad (5.13)$$

where Λ_0 and $\Lambda(\tau)$ are defined as

$$\Lambda_0 = \int d\Omega |\Phi(\Omega)|^2 (\mathbf{e}_s^\dagger \mathbf{U}_1^\dagger \mathbf{U}_1 \mathbf{e}_s) (\mathbf{e}_i^\dagger \mathbf{U}_2^\dagger \mathbf{U}_2 \mathbf{e}_i) \quad (5.14)$$

and

$$\Lambda(\tau) = \int d\Omega |\Phi(\Omega)|^2 F(\omega_0 + \Omega) F^*(\omega_0 - \Omega) e^{i\Omega\tau}, \quad (5.15)$$

representing constant and varying contributions to the quantum interferogram, respectively.

The function $F(\omega)$, which includes all of the sample properties, is given by

$$F(\omega) = \mathbf{e}_i^\dagger \mathbf{U}_2^\dagger \mathbf{U}_1(\omega) \mathbf{e}_s. \quad (5.16)$$

The parameter $\mathcal{V}_{\text{BS}} = 2(|r|^2|t|^2)/(|r|^4 + |t|^4)$ in Eq. (5.13) represents a visibility factor for a lossless beam splitter with arbitrary transmittance ($\mathcal{V}_{\text{BS}} = 1$ when $|r| = |t| = 1$).

Equation (5.15) is a generalization of Eq. (8) in Ref. [Abouraddy et al.(2002b)Abouraddy, Nasr, Saleh, Sergienko, and Teich], where the function F contains polarization-dependent information about the sample.

It is clear from Eq. (5.15) that the sample is simultaneously probed at two frequencies, $\omega_0 + \Omega$ and $\omega_0 - \Omega$, and that for a frequency-entangled two-photon state such that produced by SPDC, even-order dispersion from the sample is cancelled in PS-QOCT. It is apparent that the delay τ can be adjusted to target specific regions in the sample from which polarization information can be extracted by scanning the parameters of the user-selected polarization rotator \mathbf{U}_2 . This experimental method is similar to those used in quantum ellipsometry, as discussed in Ref. [Abouraddy et al.(2002c)Abouraddy, Toussaint, Jr., Saleh, Sergienko, and Teich].

In the following section, we consider a specific construct for Eq. (5.4) that defines the optics in the experimental setup represented in Fig. 5.2. Once we derive an expression valid for an arbitrary sample, we consider several special cases in an effort to understand the nature of the information contained in the quantum interferogram.

5.3 Role of polarization in PS-QOCT

To facilitate the description of PS-QOCT, we make use of the Pauli spin matrices

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma}_1 = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad \boldsymbol{\sigma}_2 = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & -i \\ i & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad \boldsymbol{\sigma}_3 = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 \end{bmatrix}, \quad (5.17)$$

from which any 2 x 2 Hermitian matrix can be defined as $\mathbf{A} = c_0 \mathbf{I} + \mathbf{c} \cdot \boldsymbol{\sigma}$, where $\mathbf{c} \equiv (c_1, c_2, c_3)$, $\boldsymbol{\sigma} \equiv (\boldsymbol{\sigma}_1, \boldsymbol{\sigma}_2, \boldsymbol{\sigma}_3)$, and $\mathbf{c} \cdot \boldsymbol{\sigma}$ denotes the scalar product of vectors \mathbf{c} and $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$. We

first define Eq. (5.4) for N reflective layers, where each reflection is assumed to be isotropic, then consider the special cases of a single and double reflector.

5.3.1 N reflective layers

We begin with a sample comprised of N reflective layers, each with an interface defined by a reflectance matrix $\mathbf{r}_m(\omega)$, as shown in Fig. 5.3. The material properties of each layer are represented by a Jones matrix \mathbf{S}_m that is assumed to be deterministic. The Jones matrix \mathbf{S}_m is a product of: an average phase delay; rotation matrices \mathbf{R}_m to account for the orientation α_m of the fast axis of the sample with respect to the horizontal axis; and the Jones matrix \mathbf{b}_m for a linear retarder with its fast axis oriented along the horizontal axis [de Boer et al.(2001)de Boer, Srinivas, Nelson, Milner, and Ducros]. If we ignore losses due to absorption, then for a single layer that spans $z = z_{m-1}$ to $z = z_m$, the Jones matrix is given by

$$\begin{aligned}\mathbf{S}_m(z, \alpha_m, \omega) &= e^{i\Delta_m(z, \omega)} \mathbf{R}_m(\alpha_m) \mathbf{b}_m(\delta_m) \mathbf{R}_m^\dagger(\alpha_m) \\ &\equiv e^{i\Delta_m(z, \omega)} \mathbf{B}_m(z, \alpha_m, \omega)\end{aligned}\quad (5.18)$$

where $\Delta_m(z, \omega) = \omega \bar{n} z/c$ is the average phase delay of the signal photon at angular frequency ω attained by propagating through a layer with average refractive index $\bar{n} = (n_o + n_e)/2$. The single-pass retardation in the layer is given by $\delta_m(z, \omega) = \omega \Delta n z/c$ where $\Delta n = |n_o - n_e|$ is the difference in refractive indices along the fast and slow axes of the medium. The rotation matrix $\mathbf{R}_m(\alpha_m)$ and the Jones matrix $\mathbf{b}_m(\delta_m)$ for the linear retarder are given by

$$\mathbf{R}_m(\alpha_m) = e^{-i\alpha_m} \boldsymbol{\sigma}_2 \quad \text{and} \quad \mathbf{b}_m(\delta_m) = e^{i(\delta_m/2)} \boldsymbol{\sigma}_3, \quad (5.19)$$

respectively, where in general $e^{-i\gamma\boldsymbol{\sigma}} = (\cos \gamma) \mathbf{I} - (i \sin \gamma) \boldsymbol{\sigma}$.

Figure 5.3: Sample comprised of N reflective layers. The probe beam is incident at the right. Each interface at position z_m is described by a reflectance matrix $\mathbf{r}_m(\omega)$. The optical properties of the sample layers between interfaces are described by the Jones matrix \mathbf{S}_m .

A complete transfer function describing the entire sample in Fig. 5.3 is therefore constructed as

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{H}(\omega) &= \sum_{m=0}^N \mathbf{S}_1 \mathbf{S}_2 \cdots \mathbf{S}_{m-1} \mathbf{S}_m \mathbf{r}_m \tilde{\mathbf{S}}_m \tilde{\mathbf{S}}_{m-1} \cdots \tilde{\mathbf{S}}_2 \tilde{\mathbf{S}}_1 \\ &= \sum_{m=0}^N e^{i2\varphi^{(m)}} \mathbf{B}^{(m)} \mathbf{r}_m \tilde{\mathbf{B}}^{(m)}, \end{aligned} \quad (5.20)$$

where $\varphi^{(0)} = 0$, $\mathbf{B}^{(0)} = \mathbf{I}$, and the tilde operation denotes a matrix that takes an argument at a negative angle, viz. $\tilde{\mathbf{S}}_m(\alpha) = \mathbf{S}_m(-\alpha)$. The accumulation of all phases up to interface m is given by

$$\varphi^{(m)} = \sum_{l=1}^m \Delta_l(z_l, \omega) \quad (5.21)$$

and the accumulated effect of birefringence up to interface m is expressed via

$$\mathbf{B}^{(m)} = \prod_{l=1}^m \mathbf{B}_l(z_l, \alpha_l, \omega). \quad (5.22)$$

Since the principal axes of the layers are generally unknown, a quarter-wave plate (Q) set at 45° is used to convert the signal photon to left circularly polarized light. A quarter-wave plate is a polarization element, so that we must also include its Jones matrix in the final expression for $\mathbf{U}_1(\omega)$ (see Fig. 5.1),

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{U}_1(\omega) &= \mathbf{Q}(45) \mathbf{H}(\omega) \mathbf{Q}^\dagger(45) \\ &= \sum_{m=0}^N e^{i2\varphi^{(m)}} \mathbf{Q}(45) \mathbf{B}^{(m)} \mathbf{r}_m \tilde{\mathbf{B}}^{(m)} \mathbf{Q}^\dagger(45), \end{aligned} \quad (5.23)$$

where the quarter-wave plate at 45° is defined as $\mathbf{Q}(45) = e^{i\frac{\pi}{4}} \boldsymbol{\sigma}_1$ and $\mathbf{Q}^\dagger(45) = \mathbf{Q}(-45) = e^{-i\frac{\pi}{4}} \boldsymbol{\sigma}_1$.

The reference arm only contains a half-wave plate that can be set at an angle 2θ to the horizontal axis (see Fig. 5.2), so that \mathbf{U}_2 can be written as

$$\mathbf{U}_2(\omega') = \mathbf{R}(\theta) e^{i\frac{\pi}{2}} \boldsymbol{\sigma}_3 \mathbf{R}^\dagger(\theta), \quad (5.24)$$

where, for example, given a vertical input polarization, $2\theta = 0^\circ$ selects vertical polarization and $2\theta = 90^\circ$ selects horizontal polarization.

We can now write the expression in Eq. (5.16), assuming frequency-independent isotropic reflection, i.e. $\mathbf{r}_m = r_m \boldsymbol{\sigma}_3$, as

$$\begin{aligned} F(\omega) &= \mathbf{e}_1^\dagger \mathbf{U}_2^\dagger \sum_{m=0}^N e^{i2\varphi^{(m)}} \mathbf{Q}(45) \mathbf{B}^{(m)} \mathbf{r}_m \tilde{\mathbf{B}}^{(m)} \mathbf{Q}^\dagger(45) \mathbf{e}_s \\ &= \mathbf{e}_1^\dagger \mathbf{U}_2^\dagger \sum_{m=0}^N e^{i2\varphi^{(m)}} r_m \mathbf{u}_m(\omega) \end{aligned} \quad (5.25)$$

where $\mathbf{u}_m(\omega) = \mathbf{Q}(45) \mathbf{B}^{(m)} \boldsymbol{\sigma}_3 \tilde{\mathbf{B}}^{(m)} \mathbf{Q}^\dagger(45) \mathbf{e}_s$. From Eqs. (5.14) and (5.15), this leads to

$$\Lambda_0 = \sum_{m=0}^N \sum_{n=0}^N r_n^* r_m \int d\Omega |\Phi(\Omega)|^2 e^{i2[\varphi^{(m)}(\omega_0+\Omega) - \varphi^{(n)}(\omega_0+\Omega)]} \mathbf{u}_n^\dagger(\omega_0 + \Omega) \mathbf{u}_m(\omega_0 + \Omega), \quad (5.26)$$

and

$$\Lambda(\tau) = \sum_{m=0}^N \sum_{n=0}^N r_n^* r_m \int d\Omega |\Phi(\Omega)|^2 e^{i2[\varphi^{(m)}(\omega_0+\Omega) - \varphi^{(n)}(\omega_0-\Omega)]} F_n^*(\omega_0 - \Omega) F_m(\omega_0 + \Omega) e^{i\Omega\tau}, \quad (5.27)$$

where $F_m(\omega) = \mathbf{e}_1^\dagger \mathbf{U}_2^\dagger \mathbf{u}_m(\omega)$. By substituting Eqs. (5.26) and (5.27) into Eq. (5.13), we construct the final expression for the quantum interferogram. In the following sections, we investigate several special samples to explain the features contained in the quantum interferogram and to determine a method for extracting sample information.

5.3.2 Single reflective layer

If we consider the special case of a single isotropic reflector buried under a birefringent layer of thickness z_1 , Eq. (5.20) can be written as

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{H}(\omega) &= \mathbf{S}_1 \mathbf{r}_1 \tilde{\mathbf{S}}_1 \\ &= e^{i2\Delta_1} \mathbf{B}_1 \mathbf{r}_1 \tilde{\mathbf{B}}_1 \end{aligned} \quad (5.28)$$

whereupon Eq. (5.16) becomes

$$\begin{aligned} F(\omega) &= i r_1 e^{i2\Delta_1} (\mathbf{e}_i^\dagger \mathbf{U}_2^\dagger [(i \sin \delta \sin 2\alpha_1) \mathbf{I} + (\cos \delta) \boldsymbol{\sigma}_1 + (\sin \delta \cos 2\alpha_1) \boldsymbol{\sigma}_3] \mathbf{e}_s) \\ &= i r_1 e^{i2\Delta_1} F_1(\omega), \end{aligned} \quad (5.29)$$

with

$$F_1(\omega) = \cos \delta(\omega) \cos 2\theta + \sin \delta(\omega) \sin 2\theta e^{2i\alpha_1}. \quad (5.30)$$

We have made use of the properties of the Pauli spin matrices and the fact that $\mathbf{e}_s = \boldsymbol{\sigma}_3 \mathbf{e}_s$ and $\mathbf{e}_i = \boldsymbol{\sigma}_1 \mathbf{e}_s$.

For a single reflector, Eqs. (5.26) and (5.27) therefore become

$$\Lambda_0 = |r_1|^2 \int d\Omega |\Phi(\Omega)|^2 \quad (5.31)$$

and

$$\Lambda(\tau) = |r_1|^2 \int d\Omega |\Phi(\Omega)|^2 e^{i2[\Delta_1(\omega_0+\Omega)-\Delta_1(\omega_0-\Omega)]} F_1(\omega_0 + \Omega) F_1^*(\omega_0 - \Omega) e^{-i\Omega\tau}, \quad (5.32)$$

respectively. The varying term can be further simplified if we expand the propagation constant $\beta(\omega)$ in the expression for the phase delay, $\Delta_1(\omega) = \omega \bar{n} z_1/c = \beta(\omega) z_1$. The quantity $\beta(\omega_0 + \Omega)$ is expanded to second order in Ω so that $\beta(\omega_0 + \Omega) \approx \beta_0 + \beta' \Omega + \frac{1}{2} \beta'' \Omega^2$, where β' is the average inverse of the group velocities v_o and v_e at ω_0 , and β'' represents the average group velocity dispersion (GVD). It is clear that second-order dispersion is cancelled in the simplified expression for the varying term, which is given by

$$\Lambda(\tau) = |r_1|^2 \int d\Omega |\Phi(\Omega)|^2 F_1(\omega_0 + \Omega) F_1^*(\omega_0 - \Omega) e^{-i\Omega(\tau+4\beta'z_1)}. \quad (5.33)$$

Figure 5.4 displays the expected curves for a single reflector buried beneath 120 μm of quartz with $n_e = 1.54661$, $n_o = 1.53773$, and $|r_1|^2 = 1$, using the scheme shown in Fig. 5.2. For this simulation, we make the assumption that $\int d\Omega |\Phi(\Omega)|^2 = 1$ and the fast axis of the quartz sample is aligned with the horizontal axis in the laboratory frame so that $\alpha_1 = 0$. The top two curves represent the expected coincidence rate, normalized by Λ_0 , when the sample photon is mixed with a vertically polarized (R_V , dash-dot curve) or a horizontally polarized (R_H , dashed curve) photon from the reference arm. The solid curve represents the re-normalized total coincidence rate [$R_T = (R_V + R_H - \Lambda_0)/\Lambda_0$] from which the reflectance of the layer can be recovered.

Figure 5.4: Simulation results for a single reflector buried beneath $120 \mu\text{m}$ of quartz with $n_e = 1.54661$, $n_o = 1.53773$, and $|r_1|^2 = 1$, using the scheme shown in Fig. 5.2. The optical axis of the quartz sample is aligned with the horizontal axis in the laboratory frame so that $\alpha_1 = 0$. The top two curves represent the normalized coincidence rate when the sample photon is mixed with a vertically polarized (R_V , dash-dot curve) or a horizontally polarized (R_H , dashed curve) reference photon. The solid curve represents the total coincidence rate (R_T) from which the reflectance of the layer can be recovered.

The material properties are revealed by the relative coincidence rates, R_V and R_H , at the value $\tau = -4\beta'z_1$. At this value of τ , the path-length difference between the arms of the interferometer is zero and there is maximal quantum interference. If we neglect any frequency dependence in the birefringence, we can substitute

Eq. (5.30) into Eq. (5.33) and write an expression for the coincidence rate at the center of the dip as

$$R_T = |F_1|^2 = |\cos \delta \cos 2\theta + \sin \delta \sin 2\theta e^{2i\alpha_1}|^2. \quad (5.34)$$

In the particular case when we select the linear-rotator angle 2θ to be either 0° or 90° , corresponding to a polarization of the reference photon that is horizontal or vertical, respectively, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} R_H &= \cos^2 \delta \\ R_V &= \sin^2 \delta. \end{aligned} \quad (5.35)$$

It is possible to determine the value of δ , or the birefringence Δn , by forming a ratio of these rates at $\Delta z = 0$:

$$\delta = \tan^{-1} \left[\frac{R_V}{R_H} \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} = \omega \Delta n z_1 / c. \quad (5.36)$$

Since we choose the linear-rotator angles 2θ to be either 0° or 90° , any dependency of the coincidence rate according to the orientation angle α_1 is lost. It is possible, however, to extract the value of α_1 by using a technique that is analogous to null ellipsometry. In the reference arm, if we combine the linear-rotator used to rotate the linear input polarization state \mathbf{e}_i with a quarter-wave plate to transform the linear polarization into a general elliptical state, it is possible to exactly match any polarization state in the sample arm. This

transformation is given by

$$\mathbf{U}_2 \mathbf{e}_i = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{bmatrix} \cos 2\theta + i \cos 2(\phi - \theta) \\ \sin 2\theta + i \sin 2(\phi - \theta) \end{bmatrix}, \quad (5.37)$$

where ϕ is the angle of the quarter-wave plate and θ is the angle of the linear rotator fast axes with respect to the horizontal axis. In the special case when $\phi = 2\theta$, we revert to the case of a single linear rotator as in our previous example.

When the polarization in the reference arm is selected by this cascade of polarization elements, we can write Eq. (5.30) as

$$F_1(\omega) = \{ \cos \delta(\omega) [\cos 2\theta - i \cos 2(\phi - \theta)] + \sin \delta(\omega) [\sin 2\theta - i \sin 2(\phi - \theta)] e^{2i\alpha_1} \}. \quad (5.38)$$

If the values of ϕ and θ are adjusted so that the polarization state in the reference arm is exactly orthogonal to that in the sample arm, $|F_1|^2 = 0$ and the coincidence count rate will be maximized. The value for α can then be determined by solving the following conditions of orthonormality, namely, the real and/or imaginary parts of Eq. (5.38) must equal zero

$$\begin{aligned} \cos \delta \cos 2\theta + \sin \delta \sin 2\theta \cos 2\alpha_1 - \sin \delta \sin 2(\phi - \theta) \sin 2\alpha_1 &= 0 \quad (5.39) \\ -\cos \delta \cos 2(\phi - \theta) + \sin \delta \sin 2\theta \sin 2\alpha_1 - \sin \delta \sin 2(\phi - \theta) \cos 2\alpha_1 &= 0. \end{aligned}$$

If the value of δ is known, then only one of these equations is required.

5.3.3 Two reflective layers

A sample with reflections from two surfaces separated by a birefringent material can be expressed as

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{H}(\omega) &= \mathbf{r}_0 + \mathbf{S}_1 \mathbf{r}_1 \tilde{\mathbf{S}}_1 \\ &= \mathbf{r}_0 + e^{i2\Delta_1} \mathbf{B}_1 \mathbf{r}_1 \tilde{\mathbf{B}}_1 \end{aligned} \quad (5.40)$$

where the subscripts 0 and 1 denote the first and second boundaries, respectively. In this case, the function in Eq. (5.16) becomes

$$F(\omega) = i r_0 F_0 + i r_1 e^{i2\Delta_1} F_1, \quad (5.41)$$

where $F_0 = \cos 2\theta$ and F_1 has been provided in Eq. (5.30).

For two reflectors separated by a birefringent medium, the constant and varying contributions from Eqs. (5.26) and (5.27) become

$$\begin{aligned} \Lambda_0 = & |r_0|^2 \int d\Omega |\Phi(\Omega)|^2 + |r_1|^2 \int d\Omega |\Phi(\Omega)|^2 + \\ & + r_0^* r_1 e^{i2\beta_0 z_1} \int d\Omega |\Phi(\Omega)|^2 \mathbf{u}_0^\dagger \mathbf{u}_1(\omega_0 + \Omega) e^{i2(\beta'\Omega + \beta''\Omega^2)z_1} + cc. \end{aligned} \quad (5.42)$$

and

$$\Lambda(\tau) = |r_0|^2 g^{(0)}(\tau) + |r_1|^2 g^{(1)}(\tau - 4\beta' z_1) + r_0^* r_1 g_d^{(01)}(\tau - 2\beta' z_1) e^{i2\beta_0 z_1} + cc., \quad (5.43)$$

respectively, where the subscript d denotes a contribution that is subject to even-order dispersion, *cc* indicates the complex conjugate,

$$g^{(m)}(\tau) = \int d\Omega |\Phi(\Omega)|^2 F_m(\omega_0 + \Omega) F_m^*(\omega_0 - \Omega) e^{-i\Omega\tau}$$

and

$$g_d^{(mn)}(\tau) = \int d\Omega |\Phi(\Omega)|^2 F_m(\omega_0 + \Omega) F_n^*(\omega_0 - \Omega) e^{i2z_1\beta''\Omega^2} e^{-i\Omega\tau} .,$$

The first two terms in Eq. (5.42) are contributions to the constant coincidence rate arising from each of the two interfaces in the material. The third term introduces a contribution only when these interfaces have a separation that is less than the coherence length of the signal photon. The first two terms in Eq. (5.43) represent dips arising from reflections from the first and second surfaces. The third term, which appears midway between these dips,

arises from the interference between probability amplitudes associated with each of these reflections.

Figure 5.5 provides numerical results for a 145- μm quartz sample with reflections from each of the two surfaces. For this calculation, again $n_e = 1.54661$, $n_o = 1.53773$, and the fast axis of the quartz plate is aligned with the horizontal axis in the laboratory frame so that $\alpha_1 = 0$. The magnitude of the reflectance from each surface is assumed to be the same so that $|r_0|^2 = |r_1|^2$. The top two plots represent the expected rate of coincidence when the sample photon is mixed with a horizontally polarized (R_H) or a vertically polarized (R_V) reference photon. The bottom trace represents the re-normalized total coincidence rate [$R_T = (R_V + R_H - \Lambda_0)/\Lambda_0$] from which the relative reflectance and positions of each interface can be determined.

In the R_V curve (middle trace), there is no dip at the first interface since the polarization mode reflected from this interface is solely horizontal. The polarization state is altered via propagation through the birefringent material and contains both vertically and horizontally polarized photons at reflection from the second interface. The peak between the two interfaces in R_H (top trace) and R_T (bottom trace) is result of interference between each layer. This peak (which can alternatively become a dip depending on the phase accumulated between the layers) is susceptible to dispersion in the sample, unlike the dips that correspond to sample layers. Thus the dispersion properties of the material can be extracted from this feature.

In summary, we ascertain that three experiments are required to completely determine the sample properties. We first select the reference arm polarization to be horizontal (H) and measure the quantum interferogram R_H by recording the coincidence rate of photons

Figure 5.5: Simulation results for a 145- μm quartz sample with reflections from each interface using the scheme shown in Fig. 5.2. For this calculation, $n_e = 1.54661$, $n_o = 1.53773$, and $|r_0|^2 = |r_1|^2$. The optical axis of the quartz is aligned with the horizontal axis in the laboratory frame so that $\alpha_1 = 0$. The top two plots represent the normalized coincidence rate when the sample photon is mixed with a horizontally polarized (R_H) or a vertically polarized (R_V) reference photon. The bottom trace represents the total coincidence rate (R_T) from which the relative reflectance of each interface can be recovered. The separation of the dips is given by the optical path length of the quartz $\bar{n}L \simeq 224 \mu\text{m}$.

arriving at the two detectors as the path-length delay $c\tau$ is scanned. The reference arm polarization is then rotated into the orthogonal vertical (V) polarization and a second measurement is made to measure the quantum interferogram R_V . The third measurement is made by selecting a value of $c\tau$ that coincides with the position of a layer. The angles of the polarization elements in the reference arm are then adjusted to maximize the coincidence rate.

The sample properties are found as follows: by forming a ratio of R_V and R_H at a value of $c\tau$ that coincides with the position of a layer, we can determine the value of the birefringence contained in the parameter δ ; using the angles from the polarization elements in the reference arm, α can be found from solving the equations for orthonormality. This technique is similar to nulling techniques in ellipsometry; and the total quantum interferogram R_T can be computed from the sum of R_H and R_V , then readjusted for the dc offset given by the constant term Λ_0 , i.e. $R_T = (R_V + R_H - \Lambda_0)/\Lambda_0$. The R_T curve provides the path-length delay between the interfaces as well as the ratio of the relative reflectance from each layer.

5.4 Conclusion

We have set forth a new polarization-sensitive QOCT (PS-QOCT) scheme and provide a general Jones matrix theory for analyzing its operation. PS-QOCT provides a means for determining information about the optical path length between isotropic reflectors, the relative magnitude of the reflectance from each interface, the birefringence of the material between the interfaces, and the orientation of the optical axis α of the sample. Owing to the fact that PS-QOCT is immune to sample dispersion, measurements are permitted at

depths greater than those accessible via ordinary optical coherence tomography.

6 Type-II QOCT Experiments

The dispersion immunity of QOCT in comparison to standard OCT has recently been experimentally demonstrated using a continuous wave (cw) laser source and type-I SPDC [Nasr et al.(2003)Nasr, Saleh, Sergienko, and Teich]. The dispersion immunity afforded by QOCT turns out to be related to the matching of each spectral component above the center frequency in one beam to the anti-correlated spectral component below the center frequency in its companion beam. For a cw pump beam with a single frequency ω_p , the spectral envelope of the pump becomes a delta function $\delta(\omega_s + \omega_i - \omega_p)$, where the subscripts (p, s, i) denote the pump, signal, and idler, respectively. Since energy conservation requires that the down-converted signal and idler photon frequencies always sum to that of the pump frequency ω_p , the signal and idler photons are perfectly anti-correlated in frequency and any deviations cancel through the interference of both beams at the final beam splitter.

In our effort to demonstrate PS-QOCT, we have constructed an experimental set-up that utilizes a pulsed laser source and type-II SPDC. For a pulsed pump, the same condition of energy conservation must still be maintained but there is a broad range of frequencies available in the spectral envelope of the pump. The signal and idler frequencies need not sum to a constant value and as such are no longer exactly anti-correlated [Grice and Walmsley(1997)]. An uncertainty in the anti-correlation of signal and idler frequency components is therefore introduced via the bandwidth of the pump beam used for down-conversion. This effect acts to degrade the immunity of the QOCT technique to sample dispersion.

In this chapter, we present experimental data for a nonlinear crystal (NLC) that is pumped by a femtosecond-pulsed laser. This broad spectral bandwidth of this pump laser

leads to imperfect frequency anti-correlation of the signal and idler and the loss of even-order dispersion cancellation. It turns out, however, that when the nonlinear crystal is pumped by a picosecond-pulsed laser, the dispersion immunity can be recovered.

These first type-II QOCT experiments have exposed several obstacles which must be addressed before our setup can be utilized for making measurements on realistic biological samples. We present an effort to overcome the problem of non-parallel interfaces and conclude the chapter with preliminary data for a sample with reflections from two interfaces.

6.1 Pulse-pumped type-II QOCT

The setup for pulse-pumped type-II QOCT is presented in Fig. 5.2. In this setup, a pulsed-pump laser at a center wavelength of 400 nm pumps a β -barium borate (BBO) crystal oriented for type-II, collinear SPDC with a center wavelength of 800 nm. The pump beam is removed from the SDPC by use of a highly reflective mirror (HR 400) centered at the pump wavelength concatenated with a long pass filter (LP 695). The signal (vertically polarized) and idler (horizontally polarized) photons are separated by a polarizing beam splitter (PBS) into the reference arm and sample arm (see Fig. 5.2) of a Mach-Zehnder interferometer. The reference arm consists of a variable path-length delay comprised of a half-wave plate (HWP), a polarizing beam splitter (PBS), quarter-wave plate (Q), and a translational mirror. The polarization in the reference beam can be selected by the user via a linear rotator prior to the final beam splitter (BS). For the experiments presented here, the polarization in the reference arm is set to be horizontal (indicated by \odot). The sample arm consists of a beam splitter (BS) and a quarter-wave plate (Q) so that circularly polarized

light is normally incident on the sample. The back-scattered light from the sample mixes with the delayed reference beam at the final beam splitter (BS). The outputs are directed through pinholes (not shown) to two single-photon counting detectors. The coincidence rate $R(\tau)$ for photons arriving at the two detectors, as a function of the path-length delay $c\tau$, are recorded in a time window determined by a coincidence-counting detection circuit (indicated by \otimes).

Figure 6.1: Experimental setup for type-II QOCT with a pulsed pump. The details of the setup are provided in the text.

To test the dispersion-cancellation capability of our pulse-pumped, type-II QOCT system, we place the sample beneath 6 mm of zinc selenide (ZnSe). At 800 nm, this highly

dispersive material has a GVD coefficient that is more than 10 times greater than that for BBO as determined from the curves presented in Fig. 6.2. This increased GVD in the sample arm has the effect of delaying frequency components in the spectrum of the signal photon prior to the sample.

Figure 6.2: GVD parameter versus wavelength for zinc selenide (ZnSe, solid curve) and β -barium borate (BBO, dashed curve). At 800 nm, the GVD coefficient for ZnSe is more than 10 times greater than that for BBO.

6.1.1 Femtosecond-pulsed pump

Using the experimental setup presented above, we conducted a set of experiments using a femtosecond-pulsed pump and a 0.5-mm-thick BBO crystal. The measured spectral bandwidth of the pump laser at a center wavelength of 400 nm was found to be $\Delta\lambda = 2$ nm. The

Figure 6.3: Type-II QOCT with a femtosecond-pulsed pump for the case (a) without zinc selenide and (b) with 6 mm of zinc selenide in the sample arm. The solid curve represents a gaussian fit to the quantum-interference dip and the measured full-width-half-minimum (FWHM) value is indicated by the arrow.

results are provided in Fig. 6.3 for the case (a) without zinc selenide and (b) with 6 mm of zinc selenide in the sample arm. Each data point represents the number of coincidences measured during a 10-second integration time as the path-delay difference between the sample and reference arms was scanned via a translational mirror on a motorized stage (Melles Griot Nanomover). As the path-delay difference becomes zero at ~ 10.53 mm, quantum destructive interference at the beam splitter causes a decrease in the measured coincidence rate and a resulting dip in the curve of $R(\tau)$. The solid curve represents a gaussian fit to the quantum-interference dip and the measured full-width-half-minimum (FWHM) value is indicated by the arrow.

In the case without zinc selenide, the width of the dip is found to be $10.4 \mu\text{m}$. However, when 6 mm of zinc selenide is placed in the sample arm, the resulting quantum interference dip is broadened to $28 \mu\text{m}$. In the event of even-order dispersion cancellation, the width of the dip would be unaffected by the presence of the zinc selenide. These experimental results demonstrate the absence of dispersion cancellation when using a femtosecond-pulsed pump for SPDC.

6.1.2 Picosecond-pulsed pump

A similar set of experiments were also performed after reconfiguring the titanium:sapphire for picosecond pulse operation. Since a picosecond-pulsed laser can be considered a quasi-cw source, we expect that even-order dispersion immunity should be restored. The output power in picosecond operation is reduced owing to the reduced second-harmonic efficiency for the 400-nm pump wavelength, hence we provide results for a 1.5 mm BBO crystal in Fig. 6.4 for the case (a) without zinc selenide and (b) with 6 mm of zinc selenide in the

Figure 6.4: Type-II QOCT with a picosecond-pulsed pump for the case (a) without zinc selenide and (b) with 6 mm of zinc selenide in the sample arm. The solid curve connects the data points to guide the eye and the measured full-width-half-minimum (FWHM) value is indicated by the arrow.

sample arm.

The width of the dip in both cases (a) and (b) is found to be $30\ \mu\text{m}$. The width of the dip is unaffected by the presence of the zinc selenide as expected in a QOCT that is immune to dispersion.

6.2 Problem of non-parallel surfaces

We have seen that QOCT is an interferometric technique that relies on the interference of two spatial/polarization modes at the final beam splitter. If the overlap of these modes is not ideal, then the quality of the measured interference pattern will be degraded via a reduction in the visibility of the dip. In a non-ideal sample, each interface between layers of our sample will not be perpendicular to the input probe beam and the back-scattered light will not return along the sample beam path to the final beam splitter. To eliminate this problem, it is necessary to collect the back-scattered light via a lens above the sample.

We conducted an experiment using the setup in Fig. 6.1 except that a 3-cm was placed before the mirror sample. The experimental results are presented in Fig. 6.5 for a perpendicular mirror sample or normal incidence of the probe beam (circles), horizontal mirror tilt (squares), and vertical mirror tilt (triangles). The solid curve in the plot represents a gaussian fit to the data for normal incidence. It is clear from the experimental data that the sample mirror could be tilted by more than 5 mrad in both the horizontal and vertical directions without affecting the quantum interference. The overall visibility, however, has been reduced ($\sim 25\%$) most likely as a result of the lens causing imbalance in the interferometer. While the lens eliminates the problem of sample orientation, it causes a mismatch

in the overlap of spatial modes at the final beam splitter. This effect can be overcome by placing an identical lens in the reference arm, or by placing a lens before the interferometer in a position before the first polarizing beam splitter.

Figure 6.5: QOCT interferogram of a single reflector with a 3-cm sample lens. Data are presented for a perpendicular mirror sample or normal incidence of the probe beam (circles), horizontal mirror tilt (squares), and vertical mirror tilt (triangles). The solid curve in the plot represents a gaussian fit to the data for normal incidence. The sample mirror was tilted by 5.83 mrad in the horizontal direction and by 8.00 rad in vertical direction without affecting the quantum interference visibility.

In Fig. 6.6, we present data where a 20 cm lens has been placed before the first beam splitter. In this way, the spatial modes in the sample and reference arms are affected in identical ways and the interference visibility has been restored. This plot illustrates the

current type-II QOCT system performance. A maximum visibility of $\sim 85\%$ can be readily achieved with a count rate of 200 coincidences/second. While the 20 cm lens does not allow for the sample to be tilted by more than ~ 0.5 mrad, it does increase the overall count rate via better mode matching at the fiber-coupled single-photon counting detectors. We leave the task of configuring the system with a matched set of lenses in the sample and reference arms for our future work.

Figure 6.6: Type-II QOCT interferogram of a single reflector. This QOCT interferogram represents the current system performance where a maximum visibility of $\sim 85\%$ can be readily achieved with a count rate of 200 coincidences/second.

6.3 2-layer sample

Using the experimental system presented in Fig. 6.1 with a 20-cm lens before the first polarizing beam splitter, we conducted an experiment using a 100 μm thick silica sample. For this sample, we expect there to be two dips in the interferogram arising from reflections at each of the two interfaces [see Eq. (5.43) in the previous section]. These dips should have equal visibility since the reflections from each interface are equal $|r_0|^2 = |r_1|^2 = 0.04$. Midway between the dips we expect a feature that arises from the interference between the probability amplitudes associated with each of the interface reflections. This feature can be a peak or a dip depending on the values of the pump frequency ω_p , the average refractive index \bar{n} , the nonlinear crystal length L , and the arguments of the reflection coefficients r_0 and r_1 .

The QOCT interferogram for the silica sample is shown in Fig. 6.7. The data indicated by squares represent the coincidence count rate acquired over 4 minutes whereas the circles represent a re-normalized coincidence count rate acquired over 1 minute. The interferogram is constructed in this way due to operational problems with the titanium:sapphire pump laser which prevented a single acquisition over the entire scan range. Although the experimental system could not be optimized, it is possible to see the interference dips resulting from each interfaces. These dips are separated by the optical path length of the sample $nL = 145 \mu\text{m}$ however do not exhibit equal visibility due to alignment errors. The dashed curve in the plot indicates the expected shape of the dips for each interface. In between the dips that indicate the front and back surfaces of the silica, a dip is present as a result of the interference between layers. The features of this dip can be used to extract information

Figure 6.7: Type-II QOCT interferogram of a silica sample. The data indicated by squares represent the coincidence count rate acquired over 4 minutes whereas the circles represent a re-normalized coincidence count rate acquired over 1 minute. The interference dips are separated by the optical path length of the sample $nL = 145 \mu\text{m}$ however do not exhibit equal visibility due to alignment errors. The dashed curve in the plot indicates the expected shape of the dips for each interface.

about the silica sample. For example, by comparison of the FWHM of this intermediate dip to the dips that correspond to the sample interface, information can be extracted about the dispersive properties of the material. This is possible since the interference dips are immune to dispersion, whereas dips (or peaks) between interfaces are susceptible to dispersion. We discuss this feature of QOCT in the remaining chapter.

6.4 Conclusion

We have presented the first experimental type-II QOCT data for a nonlinear crystal that is pumped by a pulsed laser. We found that when the crystal is pumped by a picosecond-pulsed laser, dispersion immunity can be recovered in the QOCT interferogram. These type-II QOCT experiments have exposed several obstacles which must be addressed before our setup can be utilized for making measurements on realistic biological samples. By using a focussing lens in the experimental system, the problem of non-parallel interfaces can be addressed. We have also presented preliminary data for a sample with reflections from two interfaces.

7 Future Work in PS-QOCT

In this chapter, several areas for future work in quantum-optical coherence tomography are outlined.

7.1 Proposed PS-QOCT experiments

To demonstrate the polarization-sensitive QOCT system, it is first necessary to replace the polarizing beam splitter (PBS) in the sample arm (see Fig. 5.2). In this way, all of the polarization information will return along the sample path to the final beam splitter. As a first demonstration, we propose the idealized samples illustrated in Fig. 7.1. In (a) the sample is comprised of a quartz plate and a highly reflective mirror, whereas in (b) a 50/50 beam splitter is also included. These two idealized samples will test the predictions made for one- and two-layer reflectors presented in chapter 5 (see Figs. 5.4 and 5.5).

The use of a highly reflective mirror in Fig. 7.1(a) and a 50/50 beam splitter and mirror in Fig. 7.1(b) will swamp the weaker reflections ($|r|^2 = 0.04$) from the surfaces of the quartz plate. This will avoid the need for extended integration times in the quantum interference measurement, as was the case for the silica sample experiment in the last chapter (see Fig. 6.7). From a set of three measurements, the quartz thickness, birefringent properties, and orientation angle should be easily determined.

Figure 7.1: Proposed samples for investigating PS-QOCT in (a) one layer and (b) two layers. The sample in (a) can be realized by using a quartz plate and a highly reflective mirror, whereas sample (b) can be realized using adding a 50/50 beam splitter to sample (a). The probe light is incident from the right.

7.2 Improving resolution

We also plan to construct a system in which the lateral (transverse) resolution of the tomographic imaging system is enhanced by the use of high numerical aperture (NA) focusing optics in the sample arm. With these high NA optics, however, the axial resolution is not established solely by the source bandwidth; the imaging optics plays a role as well. We have seen in the previous chapter that a single focusing lens can affect the integrity of the quantum interference dip so the use of matched lenses in both interferometer arms must be

implemented. Also, constructing a system of this type necessitates the use of combined and coordinated scanning of the focusing lens in the sample arm and the interferometric delay to create the two-dimensional image. Although an increase in resolution can be achieved, there is increased cost in complexity of the scanning mechanism. One method of coordinating the sample and reference arm scanning is to place the focusing objective and interferometric delay on the same mechanical stage, as has been done in optical coherence microscopy [Izatt et al.(1994)Izatt, Hee, Owen, Swanson, and Fujimoto].

7.3 Interstitial-layer dispersion characterization

In the presence of moderate dispersion, the interferogram in conventional OCT can be inaccurate and difficult to interpret. The degradation in resolution that arises from dispersion results in the positions of the sample layers being ambiguous or indeterminate. QOCT, on the other hand, will always yield high-resolution dispersion-cancelled coincidence-rate dips at delays corresponding to reflections from the layers.

The QOCT system can also be operated to reveal information about dispersion between layers. The peak (or dip) in a QOCT signal that caused by interference between the reflection amplitudes arising from the two surfaces contains interstitial-layer dispersion information. This is in contrast to the narrow dips that result from quantum interference between the probability amplitudes arising from reflection at each surface independently. The breadth of the middle feature is determined only by the dispersion of the medium residing between the two reflective surfaces and not by the nature of the material under which they are buried. It is clear, therefore, that the dispersion of the region between the

two surfaces may be determined by measuring the broadening of the middle peak (or dip) in comparison with the two dispersion-cancelled dips.

It is important to note that dispersion cancellation occurs for all even powers of the expansion of $\beta(\omega)$. Thus if the phases of reflection from the surfaces are random, which provides a model for transmission through a turbid or turbulent medium, only the middle peak will wash out, while the dips arising from reflections from the surfaces of interest are unaffected. In OCT, such random phase variations serve to deteriorate, and possibly destroy, information about the sample. If we can extract information about the dispersion of the interstitial layers of the sample using QOCT, it would also be possible to use this information for the dispersion-compensation techniques that are currently used in OCT, but require knowledge of such dispersion values to successfully implement their algorithms.

7.4 QOCT source optimization

In both OCT and QOCT imaging, the transverse and axial resolutions are determined by different mechanisms. The transverse resolution is determined by the focusing properties of the optical system [Nasr et al.(2002)Nasr, Abouraddy, Booth, Saleh, Sergienko, Teich, Kempe, and Wollenschensky], as in standard microscopy. The axial resolution, on the other hand, is determined by the temporal-coherence characteristics of the source probe beam and for QOCT is determined by half the spatial width of the correlation of the photon-pair wave function. This value is often referred to as the entanglement time T_e , which defines the time uncertainty between arrival of the members that comprise an entangled-photon pair. If the spectral profile of the source is approximated by a Gaussian, then the axial resolution is

twice that given by Eq. (1.1) for the same source bandwidth. The use of entangled photons as a conventional OCT source adds to an expanding field of broadband source development in OCT.

Since the axial resolution is inversely proportional to the bandwidth of the source for both OCT and QOCT, the development of the QOCT source will naturally also benefit conventional OCT. By designing the source to minimize the entanglement time T_e , and thereby maximizing the source bandwidth, a resolution enhancement for both QOCT and OCT will be realized. It should be pointed out that currently available photon-pair sources are weak so that strongly scattering samples will require long integration times for reliable detection. Nevertheless, this disadvantage will often be counterbalanced by the advantages outlined, particularly for highly dispersive media. Furthermore, we expect to improve the efficiency of our QOCT source by utilizing periodically poled nonlinear crystals that have been used to substantially enhance twin-photon generation rates [Di Giuseppe et al.(2002)Di Giuseppe, Atatüre, Shaw, Sergienko, Saleh, and Teich, Booth et al.(2002)Booth, Atatüre, Di Giuseppe, Sergienko, Saleh, and Teich].

7.5 Modelling and simulation

In the preliminary work carried out to date to evaluate the potential of the QOCT technique, we employed a highly simplified model for the specimen, in which the layers are separated by transparent but dispersive media. Future work should extend this model to accurately account for a number of other properties prevalent in biological tissue.

Depletion of the probe beam. Our preliminary model assumes that the incoming probe

beam is undepleted following reflection at each boundary. This assumption is widely made throughout the literature in OCT. However, QOCT offers the ability to probe more deeply into tissue, so that the depletion of the probe beam becomes important and must be accounted for in the model. We propose to carry out numerical simulation and analysis based on coupled-wave equations to accommodate probe-beam depletion in deep layers. These simulations are an extension of work in our laboratory that models beam propagation through periodic and aperiodic structures in physical media such as photonic-crystal structures.

Frequency- and polarization-dependent reflection coefficients. Our preliminary model assumes that the reflection coefficients at each boundary are both frequency- and polarization-independent, i.e. the amplitude reflection coefficient r has no spectral dependence and that reflection is insensitive to the probe-beam polarization. We propose to explore the utility of our QOCT technique in carrying out spectral reflectometry akin to the field of hyperspectral imaging and polarization-sensitive measurements. These features should be included in our model to enable the correct interpretation of their manifestation in the interferometric signal.

Scattering and absorption. Our preliminary model, which is based on parallel reflective layers, does not properly account for scattering. Furthermore, we have neglected the effects of absorption in the interstitial layers of the tissue. We propose to develop a more refined model that accommodates both absorption and scattering. Such a model would account for backscattered light that follows an appropriate angular distribution within the collection optics of the probe beam.

8 Summary

In the preceding chapters, we have outlined two non-classical two-photon imaging techniques, namely entangled-photon microscopy and polarization-sensitive quantum-optical coherence tomography (PS-QOCT). Each of these imaging modalities provides advantages over current techniques in biomedical imaging because of the unique properties entangled-photon pairs. We have evaluated the usefulness of these techniques for studying biological samples.

The outlook for entangled-photon microscopy is presently uncertain. Our efforts to observe entangled-photon photoemission, an obvious precursor to the use of entangled photons for exciting fluorescence in microscopy, have been unsuccessful. To date, there is no published work that claims to have measured entangled-photon photoemission. In this work, we have described a sound experimental method for measuring and analyzing photoemission, however, until future advances and design of more powerful SPDC sources are realized, the observation of entangled-photon photoemission will most likely remain elusive.

The use of entangled photons for quantum-optical coherence tomography is more promising. We have set forth a new polarization-sensitive QOCT (PS-QOCT) scheme, provided preliminary experimental data for idealized samples, and identified many future areas of research. Once fully realized, it is expected that PS-QOCT will augment current OCT techniques, provide new tools to extract physiologically relevant properties of tissue, and extend the available range of techniques in biomedical imaging science.

Bibliography

- [Teich and Saleh(1988)] M. C. Teich and B. E. A. Saleh, *Photon Bunching and Antibunching* (North-Holland, Amsterdam, 1988), vol. 26 of *Progress in Optics*, chap. 1, pp. 1–104.
- [Teich and Saleh(1990)] M. C. Teich and B. E. A. Saleh, *Physics Today* **43**, 26 (1990).
- [Klyshko(1967)] D. N. Klyshko, Pis'ma v Zhurnal Eksperimental'noi i Teoreticheskoi Fiziki **6**, 490 (1967), [*Journal of Experimental and Theoretical Physics Letters* **6**, 23-25 (1967)].
- [Harris et al.(1967)Harris, Oshman, and Byer] S. E. Harris, M. K. Oshman, and R. L. Byer, *Physical Review Letters* **18**, 732 (1967).
- [Giallorenzi and Tang(1968)] T. G. Giallorenzi and C. L. Tang, *Physical Review* **166**, 225 (1968).
- [Kleinman(1968)] D. A. Kleinman, *Physical Review* **174**, 1027 (1968).
- [Burnham and Weinberg(1970)] D. C. Burnham and D. L. Weinberg, *Physical Review Letters* **25**, 84 (1970).
- [Klyshko(1988)] D. N. Klyshko, *Zhurnal Eksperimental'noi i Teoreticheskoi Fiziki* **94**, 82 (1988).
- [Larchuk et al.(1995a)Larchuk, Teich, and Saleh] T. S. Larchuk, M. C. Teich, and B. E. A. Saleh, *Annals of the New York Academy of Sciences* **755**, 680 (1995a).
- [Ghosh et al.(1986)Ghosh, Hong, Ou, and Mandel] R. Ghosh, C. K. Hong, Z. Y. Ou, and L. Mandel, *Physical Review A* **34**, 3962 (1986).
- [Ghosh and Mandel(1987)] R. Ghosh and L. Mandel, *Physical Review Letters* **59**, 1903 (1987).
- [Hong et al.(1987)Hong, Ou, and Mandel] C. K. Hong, Z. Y. Ou, and L. Mandel, *Physical Review Letters* **59**, 2044 (1987).
- [Rarity et al.(1990)Rarity, Tapster, Jakeman, Larchuk, Campos, Teich, and Saleh] J. G. Rarity, P. R. Tapster, E. Jakeman, T. S. Larchuk, R. A. Campos, M. C. Teich, and B. E. A. Saleh, *Physical Review Letters* **60**, 1348 (1990).
- [Zeilinger(1999)] A. Zeilinger, *Reviews of Modern Physics* **71**, S288 (1999).
- [Fry and Walther(2000)] E. S. Fry and T. Walther, *Fundamental Tests of Quantum Mechanics* (Academic, Boston, 2000), vol. 42 of *Advances in Atomic, Molecular, and Optical Physics*, pp. 1–27.
- [Klyshko(1977)] D. N. Klyshko, *Kvantovaya Elektron* **4**, 1056 (1977).

- [Migdall et al.(1998)Migdall, Datla, Sergienko, Orszak, and Shih] A. Migdall, R. Datla, A. Sergienko, J. S. Orszak, and Y. Shih, *Applied Optics* **37**, 3455 (1998).
- [Saleh et al.(1998)Saleh, Jost, Fei, and Teich] B. E. A. Saleh, B. M. Jost, H.-B. Fei, and M. C. Teich, *Physical Review Letters* **80**, 3483 (1998).
- [Fei et al.(1997)Fei, Jost, Popescu, Saleh, and Teich] H.-B. Fei, B. M. Jost, S. Popescu, B. E. A. Saleh, and M. C. Teich, *Physical Review Letters* **78**, 1679 (1997).
- [Jost et al.(1998)Jost, Sergienko, Abouraddy, Saleh, and Teich] B. M. Jost, A. V. Sergienko, A. F. Abouraddy, B. E. A. Saleh, and M. C. Teich, *Optics Express* **3**, 81 (1998).
- [Saleh et al.(2000)Saleh, Abouraddy, Sergienko, and Teich] B. E. A. Saleh, A. F. Abouraddy, A. V. Sergienko, and M. C. Teich, *Physical Review A* **62**, 043816 (2000).
- [Abouraddy et al.(2001a)Abouraddy, Saleh, Sergienko, and Teich] A. F. Abouraddy, B. E. A. Saleh, A. V. Sergienko, and M. C. Teich, *Physical Review Letters* **87**, 123602 (2001a).
- [Abouraddy et al.(2001b)Abouraddy, Saleh, Sergienko, and Teich] A. F. Abouraddy, B. E. A. Saleh, A. V. Sergienko, and M. C. Teich, *Optics Express* **9**, 498 (2001b).
- [Abouraddy et al.(2002a)Abouraddy, Saleh, Sergienko, and Teich] A. F. Abouraddy, B. E. A. Saleh, A. V. Sergienko, and M. C. Teich, *Journal of the Optical Society of America B* **19**, 1174 (2002a).
- [Lugiato et al.(2002)Lugiato, Gatti, and Brambilla] L. A. Lugiato, A. Gatti, and E. Brambilla, *Journal of Optics B: Quantum and Semiclassical Optics* **4**, S176 (2002).
- [Ekert(1991)] A. K. Ekert, *Physical Review Letters* **67**, 661 (1991).
- [Ekert et al.(1992)Ekert, Rarity, Tapster, and Palma] A. K. Ekert, J. G. Rarity, P. R. Tapster, and G. M. Palma, *Physical Review Letters* **69**, 1293 (1992).
- [Rarity and Tapster(1996)] J. Rarity and P. Tapster, *Defence Science Journal* **1**, 388 (1996).
- [Brendel et al.(1999)Brendel, Gisin, Tittel, and Zbinden] J. Brendel, N. Gisin, W. Tittel, and H. Zbinden, *Physical Review Letters* **82**, 2594 (1999).
- [Sergienko et al.(1999)Sergienko, Atatüre, Walton, Jaeger, Saleh, and Teich] A. V. Sergienko, M. Atatüre, Z. Walton, G. Jaeger, B. E. A. Saleh, and M. C. Teich, *Physical Review A* **60**, R2622 (1999).
- [Jennewein et al.(2000)Jennewein, Simon, Weihs, Weinfurter, and Zeilinger] T. Jennewein, C. Simon, G. Weihs, H. Weinfurter, and A. Zeilinger, *Physical Review Letters* **84**, 4729 (2000).
- [Booth et al.(2003a)Booth, Sergienko, Saleh, and Teich] M. C. Booth, A. V. Sergienko, B. E. A. Saleh, and M. C. Teich, *Physical Review A* (2003a), in preparation.

- [Booth et al.(2002)Booth, Atatüre, Di Giuseppe, Sergienko, Saleh, and Teich] M. C. Booth, M. Atatüre, G. Di Giuseppe, A. V. Sergienko, B. E. A. Saleh, and M. C. Teich, *Physical Review A* **66**, 023815 (2002).
- [Abouraddy et al.(2002b)Abouraddy, Nasr, Saleh, Sergienko, and Teich] A. F. Abouraddy, M. B. Nasr, B. E. A. Saleh, A. V. Sergienko, and M. C. Teich, *Physical Review A* **65**, 053817 (2002b).
- [Nasr et al.(2003)Nasr, Saleh, Sergienko, and Teich] M. B. Nasr, B. E. A. Saleh, A. V. Sergienko, and M. C. Teich, *Physical Review Letters* **91**, 083601 (2003).
- [Booth et al.(2003b)Booth, Di Giuseppe, Sergienko, Saleh, and Teich] M. C. Booth, G. Di Giuseppe, A. V. Sergienko, B. E. A. Saleh, and M. C. Teich, *Physical Review A* (2003b), in preparation.
- [Minsky(1957)] M. Minsky, *Microscopy apparatus*, U.S. Patent 3 013 467 (1957).
- [Denk et al.(1990)Denk, Strickler, and Webb] W. Denk, J. H. Strickler, and W. W. Webb, *Science* **248**, 73 (1990).
- [Potter et al.(1996)Potter, Fraser, and Pine] S. M. Potter, S. E. Fraser, and J. Pine, *Scanning* **18**, 147 (1996).
- [Schneckenburger et al.(2000)Schneckenburger, Hendinger, Sailer, Gschwend, Strauss, Bauer, and Schütze] H. Schneckenburger, A. Hendinger, R. Sailer, M. H. Gschwend, W. S. L. Strauss, M. Bauer, and K. Schütze, *Journal of Biomedical Optics* **5**, 40 (2000).
- [Ridsdale and Webb(1993)] J. A. Ridsdale and W. W. Webb, *Biophysical Journal* **64**, A109 (1993).
- [König et al.(1995)König, Liang, Berns, and Tromberg] K. König, H. Liang, M. W. Berns, and B. J. Tromberg, *Nature* **377**, 20 (1995).
- [Albota et al.(1998)Albota, Xu, and Webb] M. A. Albota, C. Xu, and W. W. Webb, *Applied Optics* **37**, 7352 (1998).
- [Hell et al.(1998)Hell, Booth, Wilms, Schnetter, Kirsch, Arndt-Jovin, and Jovin] S. W. Hell, M. Booth, S. Wilms, C. M. Schnetter, A. K. Kirsch, D. J. Arndt-Jovin, and T. M. Jovin, *Optics Letters* **23**, 1238 (1998).
- [Teich and Saleh(1998)] M. C. Teich and B. E. A. Saleh, *Entangled-photon microscopy, spectroscopy, and imaging*, U.S. Patent 5 796 477 (1998).
- [Huang et al.(1991)Huang, Swanson, Lin, Schuman, Stinson, Chang, Hee, Flotte, Gregory, Puliafito et al.] D. Huang, E. A. Swanson, C. P. Lin, J. S. Schuman, W. G. Stinson, W. Chang, M. R. Hee, T. Flotte, K. Gregory, C. A. Puliafito, et al., *Science* **254**, 1178 (1991).
- [Fujimoto et al.(1995)Fujimoto, Brezinski, Tearney, Boppart, Bouma, Hee, Southern, and Swanson] J. G. Fujimoto, M. E. Brezinski, G. J. Tearney, S. A. Boppart, B. E. Bouma, M. R. Hee, J. F. Southern, and E. A. Swanson, *Nature Medicine* **1**, 970 (1995).

- [Fercher(1996)] A. F. Fercher, *Journal of Biomedical Optics* **1**, 157 (1996).
- [Schmidt(1999)] J. M. Schmidt, *IEEE Journal of Selected Topics in Quantum Electronics* **5**, 1205 (1999).
- [Hee et al.(1995)Hee, Izatt, Swanson, Huang, Schuman, Lin, Puliafito, and Fujimoto] M. R. Hee, J. A. Izatt, E. A. Swanson, D. Huang, J. S. Schuman, C. P. Lin, C. A. Puliafito, and J. G. Fujimoto, *Archives of Ophthalmology (Chicago)* **113**, 325 (1995).
- [Brezinski and Fujimoto(1999)] M. Brezinski and J. G. Fujimoto, *IEEE Journal of Selected Topics in Quantum Electronics* **5**, 1185 (1999).
- [Fujimoto et al.(1999)Fujimoto, Boppart, Tearney, Bouma, Pitris, and Brezinski] J. G. Fujimoto, S. A. Boppart, G. J. Tearney, B. E. Bouma, C. Pitris, and M. E. Brezinski, *Heart* **82**, 128 (1999).
- [Hee et al.(1992)Hee, Huang, Swanson, and Fujimoto] M. R. Hee, D. Huang, E. A. Swanson, and J. G. Fujimoto, *Journal of the Optical Society of America B* **9**, 903 (1992).
- [de Boer et al.(1999)de Boer, Srinivas, Park, Pham, Chen, Milner, and Nelson] J. F. de Boer, S. M. Srinivas, B. H. Park, T. H. Pham, Z. Chen, T. E. Milner, and J. S. Nelson, *IEEE Journal of Selected Topics in Quantum Electronics* **5**, 1200 (1999).
- [Paschotta et al.(1997)Paschotta, Nilsson, Tropper, and Hanna] R. Paschotta, J. Nilsson, A. C. Tropper, and D. C. Hanna, *IEEE Journal of Selected Topics in Quantum Electronics* **3**, 1097 (1997).
- [Drexler et al.(1999)Drexler, Morgner, Kärtner, Pitris, Boppart, Li, Ippen, and Fujimoto] W. Drexler, U. Morgner, F. X. Kärtner, C. Pitris, S. A. Boppart, X. D. Li, E. P. Ippen, and J. G. Fujimoto, *Optics Letters* **24**, 1221 (1999).
- [Povazay et al.(2002)Povazay, Bizheva, Unterhuber, Hermann, Sattamann, Fercher, Drexler, Apolonski, W. B. Povazay, K. Bizheva, A. Unterhuber, B. Hermann, H. Sattamann, A. F. Fercher, W. Drexler, A. Apolonski, W. J. Wadsworth, J. C. Knight, et al., *Optics Letters* **27**, 1800 (2002).
- [Drexler et al.(2001)Drexler, Morgner, Ghanta, Kärtner, Schuman, and Fujimoto] W. Drexler, U. Morgner, R. K. Ghanta, F. X. Kärtner, J. S. Schuman, and J. G. Fujimoto, *Nature Medicine* **7**, 502 (2001).
- [Hitzenberger et al.(1999)Hitzenberger, Baumgartner, Drexler, and Fercher] C. K. Hitzenberger, A. Baumgartner, W. Drexler, and A. F. Fercher, *Journal of Biomedical Optics* **4**, 144 (1999).
- [Hitzenberger et al.(2002)Hitzenberger, Baumgartner, Drexler, and Fercher] C. K. Hitzenberger, A. Baumgartner, W. Drexler, and A. F. Fercher, *Optics Communications* **204**, 67 (2002).
- [Smith et al.(2002)Smith, Zvyagin, and Sampson] E. D. J. Smith, A. V. Zvyagin, and D. D. Sampson, *Optics Letters* **27**, 1998 (2002).

- [Fercher et al.(2001)Fercher, Hitzenberger, Sticker, Zawadzki, Karamata, and Lasser] A. F. Fercher, C. K. Hitzenberger, M. Sticker, R. Zawadzki, B. Karamata, and T. Lasser, *Optics Express* **9**, 610 (2001).
- [Fercher et al.(2002)Fercher, Hitzenberger, Sticker, Zawadzki, Karamata, and Lasser] A. F. Fercher, C. K. Hitzenberger, M. Sticker, R. Zawadzki, B. Karamata, and T. Lasser, *Optics Communications* **204**, 67 (2002).
- [Franson(1992)] J. D. Franson, *Physical Review A* **45**, 3126 (1992).
- [Steinberg et al.(1992)Steinberg, Kwiat, and Chiao] A. M. Steinberg, P. G. Kwiat, and R. Y. Chiao, *Physical Review Letters* **68**, 2421 (1992).
- [Larchuk et al.(1995b)Larchuk, Teich, and Saleh] T. S. Larchuk, M. C. Teich, and B. E. A. Saleh, *Physical Review A* **52**, 4145 (1995b).
- [Peřina et al.(1994)Peřina, Hradil, and Jurčo] J. Peřina, Z. Hradil, and B. Jurčo, *Quantum Optics and Fundamentals of Physics* (Kluwer, Boston, 1994), chap. 7 and 8.
- [Giordmaine(1962)] J. A. Giordmaine, *Physical Review Letters* **8**, 19 (1962).
- [Maker et al.(1962)Maker, Terhune, Nisenoff, and Savage] P. D. Maker, R. W. Terhune, M. Nisenoff, and C. M. Savage, *Physical Review Letters* **8**, 21 (1962).
- [Dmitriev et al.(1995)Dmitriev, Gurzadyan, and Nikogosyan] V. G. Dmitriev, G. G. Gurzadyan, and D. N. Nikogosyan, *The Handbook of Nonlinear Optical Crystals* (Springer-Verlag, New York, 1995), vol. 64 of *Springer Series in Optical Sciences*, chap. 3, 2nd ed.
- [Göppert-Mayer(1931)] M. Göppert-Mayer, *Annalen der Physik* **9**, 273 (1931).
- [Sonnenberg et al.(1964)Sonnenberg, Heffner, and Spicer] H. Sonnenberg, H. Heffner, and W. Spicer, *Applied Physics Letters* **5**, 95 (1964).
- [Teich et al.(1964)Teich, Schroer, and Wolga] M. C. Teich, J. M. Schroer, and G. J. Wolga, *Physical Review Letters* **13**, 611 (1964).
- [Einstein(1905)] A. Einstein, *Annalen der Physik* **17**, 5 (1905).
- [Grum and Becherer(1979)] F. Grum and R. J. Becherer, *Radiometry* (Academic Press, Inc., New York, 1979), vol. 1 of *Optical Radiation Measurements*, chap. 6, pp. 173–192, 1st ed.
- [Saleh and Teich(1991a)] B. E. A. Saleh and M. C. Teich, *Fundamentals of Photonics* (Wiley, New York, 1991a), chap. 17.
- [PMT(1998)] *Photomultiplier Tubes, Sales Catalog*, Hamamatsu Photonics K.K., Japan, revised ed. (1998).
- [Teich and Wolga(1967)] M. C. Teich and G. J. Wolga, *Journal of the Optical Society of America* **57**, 542 (1967).

- [Hattori et al.(2000)Hattori, Kawashima, Daikoku, Inouye, and Nakatsuka] T. Hattori, Y. Kawashima, M. Daikoku, H. Inouye, and H. Nakatsuka, *Japanese Journal of Applied Physics* **39**, 4793 (2000).
- [Schuppler et al.(1992)Schuppler, Fischer, Fauster, and Steinmann] S. Schuppler, N. Fischer, T. Fauster, and W. Steinmann, *Physical Review B* **46**, 13539 (1992).
- [Wang et al.(1995)Wang, Paiella, and Osgood, Jr.] X. Y. Wang, R. Paiella, and R. M. Osgood, Jr., *Physical Review B* **51**, 17035 (1995).
- [Fauster(2002)] T. Fauster, *Surface Science* **507**, 256 (2002).
- [Töben et al.(2003)Töben, Hannappel, Eichberger, Möller, Gundlach, Ernstorfer, and Willig] L. Töben, T. Hannappel, R. Eichberger, K. Möller, L. Gundlach, R. Ernstorfer, and F. Willig, *Journal of Crystal Growth* **248**, 206 (2003).
- [Teich and Wolga(1968)] M. C. Teich and G. J. Wolga, *Physical Review* **171**, 809 (1968).
- [Ghosh(1980)] C. Ghosh, *Physical Review B* **22**, 1972 (1980).
- [Friberg et al.(1985)Friberg, Hong, and Mandel] S. Friberg, C. K. Hong, and L. Mandel, *Optics Communications* **54**, 311 (1985).
- [Javanainen and Gould(1990)] J. Javanainen and P. L. Gould, *Physical Review A* **41**, 5088 (1990).
- [Tanzilli et al.(2001)Tanzilli, Riedmatten, Tittel, Zbinden, Baldi, Micheli, Ostrowsky, and Gisin] S. Tanzilli, H. D. Riedmatten, W. Tittel, H. Zbinden, P. Baldi, M. D. Micheli, D. B. Ostrowsky, and N. Gisin, *Electronic Letters* **37**, 26 (2001).
- [Banaszek et al.(2001)Banaszek, U'Ren, and Walmsley] K. Banaszek, A. B. U'Ren, and I. A. Walmsley, *Optics Letters* **26**, 1367 (2001).
- [Shen(1984)] Y. R. Shen, *The Principles of Nonlinear Optics* (Wiley, New York, 1984), chap. 3, 7 and 9.
- [Armstrong et al.(1962)Armstrong, Bloembergen, Ducuing, and Pershan] J. A. Armstrong, N. Bloembergen, J. Ducuing, and P. S. Pershan, *Physical Review* **127**, 1918 (1962).
- [Franken and Ward(1963)] P. A. Franken and J. F. Ward, *Reviews of Modern Physics* **35**, 23 (1963).
- [Baldi et al.(1995)Baldi, Aschieri, Nouh, Micheli, Ostrowsky, Delacourt, and Papuchon] P. Baldi, P. Aschieri, S. Nouh, M. D. Micheli, D. B. Ostrowsky, D. Delacourt, and M. Papuchon, *IEEE Journal of Quantum Electronics* **31**, 997 (1995).
- [Myers et al.(1995)Myers, Eckardt, Fejer, Byer, Bosenberg, and Pierce] L. E. Myers, R. C. Eckardt, M. M. Fejer, R. L. Byer, W. R. Bosenberg, and J. W. Pierce, *Journal of the Optical Society of America B* **12**, 2102 (1995).

- [Fejer et al.(1992)Fejer, Magel, Jundt, and Byer] M. M. Fejer, G. A. Magel, D. H. Jundt, and R. L. Byer, *IEEE Journal of Quantum Electronics* **28**, 2631 (1992).
- [Mandel and Wolf(1995)] L. Mandel and E. Wolf, *Optical Coherence and Quantum Optics* (Cambridge Univ. Press, Cambridge, 1995), chap. 22.
- [Rossi and Berger(2002)] A. D. Rossi and V. Berger, *Physical Review Letters* **88**, 043901 (2002).
- [Atatüre et al.(2002)Atatüre, Di Giuseppe, Shaw, Saleh, Sergienko, and Teich] M. Atatüre, G. Di Giuseppe, M. D. Shaw, B. E. A. Saleh, A. V. Sergienko, and M. C. Teich, *Physical Review A* **66**, 023822 (2002).
- [Klyshko(1980)] D. N. Klyshko, *Photons and Nonlinear Optics* (Nauka, Moscow, 1980), chap. 1 and 6, [Translation: Gordon and Breach, 1988].
- [Di Giuseppe et al.(2002)Di Giuseppe, Atatüre, Shaw, Sergienko, Saleh, and Teich] G. Di Giuseppe, M. Atatüre, M. D. Shaw, A. V. Sergienko, B. E. A. Saleh, and M. C. Teich, *Physical Review A* **66**, 013801 (2002).
- [Saleh and Teich(1991b)] B. E. A. Saleh and M. C. Teich, *Fundamentals of Photonics* (Wiley, New York, 1991b), chap. 7.
- [Batchko et al.(1999)Batchko, Fejer, Byer, Woll, Wallenstein, Shur, and Erman] R. G. Batchko, M. M. Fejer, R. L. Byer, D. Woll, R. Wallenstein, V. Y. Shur, and L. Erman, *Optics Letters* **24**, 1293 (1999).
- [Ding et al.(1995)Ding, Lee, and Khurgin] Y. J. Ding, S. J. Lee, and J. B. Khurgin, *Physical Review Letters* **75**, 429 (1995).
- [Ghatak and Thyagarajan(1998)] A. Ghatak and K. Thyagarajan, *Introduction to Fiber Optics* (Cambridge, New York, 1998), chap. 7.
- [Bonfrate et al.(1999)Bonfrate, Pruneri, Kazansky, Tapster, and Rarity] G. Bonfrate, V. Pruneri, P. G. Kazansky, P. Tapster, and J. G. Rarity, *Applied Physics Letters* **16**, 2356 (1999).
- [Kazansky and Pruneri(1997)] P. G. Kazansky and V. Pruneri, *Journal of the Optical Society of America B* **14**, 3170 (1997).
- [Wang et al.(1999)Wang, Pasiskevivius, Hellström, Laurell, and Karlsson] S. Wang, V. Pasiskevivius, J. Hellström, F. Laurell, and H. Karlsson, *Optics Letters* **24**, 978 (1999).
- [Abouraddy et al.(2002c)Abouraddy, Toussaint, Jr., Saleh, Sergienko, and Teich] A. F. Abouraddy, K. C. Toussaint, Jr., B. E. A. Saleh, A. V. Sergienko, and M. C. Teich, *Journal of the Optical Society of America B* **19**, 656 (2002c).
- [de Boer et al.(2001)de Boer, Srinivas, Nelson, Milner, and Ducros] J. F. de Boer, S. M. Srinivas, J. S. Nelson, T. E. Milner, and M. G. Ducros, *Handbook of Optical Coherence Tomography* (Marcel Dekker, New York, 2001), chap. 9, pp. 237–243.

- [Grice and Walmsley(1997)] W. P. Grice and I. A. Walmsley, Physical Review A **56**, 1627 (1997).
- [Izatt et al.(1994)Izatt, Hee, Owen, Swanson, and Fujimoto] J. A. Izatt, M. R. Hee, G. M. Owen, E. A. Swanson, and J. G. Fujimoto, Optics Letters **19**, 590 (1994).
- [Nasr et al.(2002)Nasr, Abouraddy, Booth, Saleh, Sergienko, Teich, Kempe, and Wollenschensky] M. B. Nasr, A. F. Abouraddy, M. C. Booth, B. E. A. Saleh, A. V. Sergienko, M. C. Teich, M. Kempe, and R. Wollenschensky, Physical Review A **65**, 023816 (2002).

Curriculum Vitae

MARK CHRISTIAN BOOTH

3446-F North Druid Hills Road
Decatur, Georgia 30033

EDUCATION

Boston University, College of Engineering **2001 - present**

Boston, Massachusetts

Ph.D. Candidate in Biomedical Engineering, expected completion September 2003
Dissertation: "Quantum Imaging of Biological Specimens using Entangled Photons"
Advisor: Malvin C. Teich

Boston University, College of Engineering **May 2001**

Boston, Massachusetts

M.S. in Biomedical Engineering
Thesis: "Entangled-Photon Photoemission and Microscopy"
Advisor: Malvin C. Teich

University of California, Irvine **March 1995**

Irvine, California

B.S. in Biological Sciences, Minor in German Language
Thesis: "Receptor-Mediated Drug Delivery for Photodynamic Therapy of Intimal Hyperplasia"
Advisor: Bruce J. Tromberg

University of Vienna **1992 - 1993**

Vienna, Austria

University of California, Education Abroad Program

WORK EXPERIENCE

Graduate Research Assistant **1997 - present**

Quantum Imaging Laboratory, Boston University, Massachusetts

- Experience in all facets of U.S. government and privately funded optics research programs, including proposal writing, attending and presenting work at scientific conferences, computer support, purchasing, and conducting research towards a doctoral degree in biomedical engineering.
- Optics experience with spontaneous parametric down-conversion (SPDC), nonlinear optics, three-wave mixing, fiber optics, single-photon counting, optical detection, optical diagnostics, and various microscopy modalities, including confocal and two-photon microscopy techniques.
- Alignment and installation of Spectra-Physics titanium:sapphire (Tsunami), argon, and Millennia X laser systems; Coherent titanium:sapphire (Mira) and Innova krypton ion laser systems; Installation and use of Rees Instrument's laser spectrum analyzer, and other laser diagnostic hardware.
- Experience in photomultiplier tube installation and operation; single-photon avalanche photodiode (APD) photon counting modules; Canberra digital signal processor; digital and analog lock-in amplifiers; electronic counting circuits and other detection electronics; GPIB instrument control and graphical user interface design with MATLAB.

- Developed a direct-detection scheme for absorption measurements; tested the feasibility of using entangled photons as a source for imaging biological samples by multi-photon microscopy and tomography.
- Designed and supervised project to test the efficacy of two-photon photoemission in several commercially available photomultiplier tube detectors.
- Managed research collaboration between Boston University, Quantum Imaging Laboratory and Carl Zeiss, Jena, Germany.
- Supervised summer research by Boston University Freshman Research Orientation Program students and visiting senior undergraduates from the University College, Dublin, Ireland.
- Advised faculty in the Boston University, School of Biology on laser system purchase for multi-photon microscopy.
- Reviewed scientific journal articles submitted for publication in the IEEE Journal of Quantum Electronics.

Research Associate

1995 - 1996

Beckman Laser Institute and Medical Clinic, University of California, Irvine, California

- Experience in fluorescence image acquisition with liquid- and TE-cooled CCD cameras in conventional and confocal microscope systems; image processing and quantitative evaluation using IPLab software; image overlays, 3D visualization, and animation; data analysis and presentation; assisted university and corporate affiliates with microscope system operation.
- Cell culture experience with: CHO (Chinese Hamster Ovary); monocyte-macrophage (P388 D1); 3T3 /SVT2 (normal and transformed mouse fibroblast); MCF7 (human mammary adenocarcinoma); tumor retrieval and preparation; cloning assays; drug uptake evaluation in vitro.
- Developed experimental system to evaluate antibody-binding kinetics using laser-cutting and trapping microscope system at the Beckman Laser Institute.

Emergency Medical Technician

1995 - 1996

Medix Ambulance Service, Mission Viejo, California

- Ambulance driver and attendant for 911 emergency coverage and critical patient transport.
- Supervised Emergency Medical Technician ambulance personnel during 24-hour shifts of emergency-911 coverage.

International Peer Advisor

1993 - 1994

University of California, Irvine, California

- Mentored and counselled college students on international study programs.

COMPUTER SKILLS

- Experience with Microsoft Windows, Macintosh, Unix, and Linux operating systems.
- Extensive experience with Microsoft Word, PowerPoint, Excel, L^AT_EX (publishing software), Origin (statistical analysis software), MATLAB (scientific simulation software), LabVIEW, Adobe Photoshop, Corel Draw (desktop publishing).
- Extensive knowledge of HTML, MATLAB, and C programming languages.
- Implemented and maintain Quantum Imaging Laboratory active directory network system in Microsoft Windows, including scheduled fileserver backup and printer services.
- Developed and maintain websites for university research group and commercial painting company, including Flash media effects, and online quote requests.

- Developed automated GPIB computer control of a multi-instrument system with a graphical user interface in MATLAB software.
- Developed a complete scientific bibliography in BibT_EX for the Quantum Imaging Laboratory, Boston University.

HONORS AND AWARDS

- International Quantum Electronics Conference Student Travel Grant (2002)
- IEEE-LEOS Student Travel Grant (2002)
- Best Poster in Session, Optical Society of America Annual Meeting (1998)
- Dean's Honor List 10 of 11 quarters while attending University of California, Irvine
- Biological Sciences Excellence in Research Program (1994)
- Honorable Mention for Poster Presentation in Excellence in Research Program (1994)
- Summer Fellowship, Beckman Laser Institute (Summer 1994)
- German Department Academic Book Award, University of California, Irvine (1992 & 1994)

SOCIETIES AND MEMBERSHIPS

- Phi Beta Kappa (1994 -)
- Golden Key National Honor Society (1993 -)
- Alpha Eta Mu Beta, National Biomedical Engineering Honor Society (AEMB)
- Optical Society of America (OSA)
- Institute for Electrical and Electronics Engineers (IEEE)
- Lasers & Electro-Optics Society (LEOS)

REVIEWED PUBLICATIONS

1. Mark C. Booth, Giovanni Di Giuseppe, Alexander V. Sergienko, Bahaa E. A. Saleh, and Malvin C. Teich, "Polarization-sensitive quantum optical coherence tomography," *Physical Review A*, to be submitted (2003).
2. Mark C. Booth, Alexander V. Sergienko, Bahaa E. A. Saleh, and Malvin C. Teich, "Entangled-Photon Photoemission," *Physical Review A*, to be submitted (2003).
3. Mark C. Booth, Alexander V. Sergienko, Bahaa E. A. Saleh, and Malvin C. Teich, "Temperature and wavelength dependence of one- and two-photon photoemission from multialkali semiconductors," *Physical Review B*, to be submitted (2003).
4. Zachary D. Walton, Mark C. Booth, Alexander V. Sergienko, Bahaa E. A. Saleh, and Malvin C. Teich, "Controllable frequency entanglement via auto-phase-matched spontaneous parametric down-conversion," *Physical Review A* **67**, 053810 (2003).
5. Mark C. Booth, Mete Atatüre, Giovanni Di Giuseppe, Alexander V. Sergienko, Bahaa E. A. Saleh, and Malvin C. Teich, "Counterpropagating entangled photons from a waveguide with periodic nonlinearity," *Physical Review A* **66**, 023815 (2002).
6. Maged B. Nasr, Ayman F. Abouraddy, Mark C. Booth, Bahaa E. A. Saleh, Alexander V. Sergienko, and Malvin C. Teich (Boston University), M. Kempe and R. Wolleschensky (Carl Zeiss, GmbH), "Biphoton focusing for two-photon excitation," *Physical Review A* **65**, 023816 (2002).

7. Mark C. Booth, Bruce. J. Tromberg, Ph.D., Tsuneyuki Nagae, M.D. "Receptor-mediated drug delivery for photodynamic therapy (PDT) of intimal hyperplasia," *Journal of Undergraduate Research in the Biological Sciences* **24**, pp. 637-644 (1994).

ORAL PRESENTATIONS

1. M. C. Booth, M. Atatüre, G. Di Giuseppe, A. V. Sergienko, B. E. A. Saleh, and M. C. Teich, "Counterpropagating entangled photons in a periodically poled nonlinear waveguide," The 15th Annual Meeting of the IEEE Lasers & Electro-Optics Society, Glasgow, Scotland (November 2002).
2. M. C. Booth, M. Atatüre, G. Di Giuseppe, A. V. Sergienko, B. E. A. Saleh, and M. C. Teich, "Counterpropagating entangled photons from a waveguide with periodic nonlinearity," International Quantum Electronics Conference/Lasers, Applications & Technologies: Quantum Optics, Moscow, Russia (June 2002).
3. Mark C. Booth, Bahaa E. A. Saleh, Alexander V. Sergienko, and Malvin C. Teich, "Entangled-photon absorption," *Digest of the Optical Society of America Annual Meeting*, presentation MU3 (October 2000).
4. Malvin C. Teich, Mark C. Booth, Bahaa E. A. Saleh, and Alexander V. Sergienko, "Entangled-photon photoemission," Invited Lecture, Fifth International Conference on Quantum Communication, Measurement & Computing, Capri, Italy (July 2000).
5. Malvin C. Teich, Mark C. Booth, Alexander V. Sergienko, and Bahaa E. A. Saleh, "Entanglement microscopy," Annual Meeting of the Optical Society of America, Invited Lecture, Santa Clara, CA (September 1999).

POSTER PRESENTATIONS

1. M. C. Booth, G. Di Giuseppe, B. E. A. Saleh, A. V. Sergienko, and M. C. Teich, "Quantum optical coherence tomography and applications to biological imaging," Conference on Lasers and Electro-Optics/Quantum Electronics and Laser Science Conference, Baltimore, Maryland (June 2003).
2. M. C. Booth, M. Atatüre, G. Di Giuseppe, A. V. Sergienko, B. E. A. Saleh, and M. C. Teich, "Counterpropagating entangled photons in a waveguide with periodic nonlinearity," The Sixth International Conference on Quantum Communication, Measurement, and Computing, Cambridge, MA (July 2002).
3. M. C. Booth, A. V. Sergienko, B. E. A. Saleh, and M. C. Teich, "PPLN source of high-flux entangled photons for microscopy," CenSSIS Research and Industrial Collaboration Conference, Northeastern University, Boston, MA (January 2002).
4. M. C. Booth, B. E. A. Saleh, A. V. Sergienko, K. M. Harris, and M. C. Teich, "Entangled-photon Microscopy," Boston University Graduate Research Science Day, Boston, MA (March 2000).
5. Mark C. Booth, Mete Atatüre, Bradley M. Jost, Alexander V. Sergienko, Bahaa E. A. Saleh, Malvin C. Teich "Experiments in entangled-photon absorption," *Digest of the Optical Society of America Annual Meeting*, paper MBB5, p. 69 (October 1998).

PROVISIONAL PATENTS

1. Mark C. Booth, Mete Atatüre, Giovanni Di Giuseppe, Alexander V. Sergienko, Bahaa E. A. Saleh, and Malvin C. Teich, "Counterpropagating entangled photons from a waveguide with periodic nonlinearity," submitted United States Patent Office (January 2002).

2. Malvin C. Teich, Bahaa E. A. Saleh, Alexander V. Sergienko, Mark C. Booth (Boston University), John T. Fourkas (Boston College), Michael Kempe and Ralf Wolleschensky, (Carl Zeiss, GmbH), "High-Flux Entangled-Photon Generation via Parametric Processes in a Laser Cavity," submitted United States Patent Office (November 2001).
3. Magued B. Nasr, Ayman F. Abouraddy, Mark C. Booth, Bahaa E. A. Saleh, Alexander V. Sergienko, and Malvin C. Teich (Boston University), Michael Kempe and Ralf Wolleschensky (Carl Zeiss, GmbH), "Method and/or Apparatus for Microscopic Imaging," submitted German Patent Office (August 2001).

OTHER PUBLICATIONS

1. Mark C. Booth, B.S., Bruce J. Tromberg, Ph.D., Tatiana B. Krasieva, Ph.D., Z.Z. Ho, Ph.D. "Optical Trap ImmunoSensor (OTIS)," Experiment Report for Corporate Affiliate (May 1996).
2. Mark C. Booth, "Making the LEAP into Biomedical Engineering," Science Magazine's Online Journal - Next Wave (December 1998).